

**A HISTORY OF TRADITIONAL CONFLICT RESOLUTION MECHANISMS IN
OKITIPUPA TOWN OF ONDO STATE UP TO 2022**

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CERTIFICATION

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DEDICATION

This project is dedicated to Almighty God for His love, protection and guidance over my life and for seeing me throughout this programme.

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ABBREVIATIONS

ADR	Alternative Dispute Resolution
ATR	African Traditional Religion
CSR	Corporate Social Responsibility
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic Acid
ISCRC	Ikale Supreme Civil Rights Council
NA	Native Authority
NSCDC	Nigeria Security and Civil Defence Corps
OOP PLC	Okitipupa Oil Palm Plc
OPC	Oodua People's Congress

ABSTRACT

The marginalisation of traditional conflict resolution mechanisms due to the dominance of Western legal systems presents a challenge to maintaining social harmony in many Nigerian communities. In Okitipupa, Ondo State, these indigenous practices continue to hold cultural importance despite the pressures of colonialism, modernisation, and formal legal systems. This study examined the historical evolution of these mechanisms, showcasing their resilience and relevance in addressing conflicts and fostering unity within the community.

By employing the historical approach using both primary and secondary sources, the research highlighted the important role of community leaders, elders, and customary laws in resolving disputes and maintaining peace. These figures use their wisdom to guide the community through reconciliation and consensus-building processes. Tools such as collaborative discussions and symbolic sanctions like oath-taking resolved conflicts and strengthened social bonds, ensuring that resolutions aligned with communal values and promoted unity.

Unlike formal legal systems that prioritised punishment and legal formalities, traditional methods in Okitipupa emphasised healing, reconciliation, and addressing the root causes of discord. The study revealed a deep connection between these practices and the broader social fabric, showing their adaptability in navigating complex social dynamics. However, these traditional systems faced increasing challenges from external legal pressures and the encroachment of modern legal institutions.

To address these challenges, the study argued for a synergy between traditional and formal legal systems, proposing an integrated approach to conflict resolution. This approach would balance the strengths of both systems, preserving cultural heritage while ensuring compliance with modern legal standards. Such a framework offers a sustainable path forward, promoting social cohesion, peace, and justice in Okitipupa.

Keywords: Customary law, Indigenous practices, Okitipupa, traditional conflict resolution.

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

Background to the Study

Generally, conflicts are accepted as inevitable phenomena in human relationships and society. It is a natural incidence among human beings. Hence, whenever people gather in social, political, religious, communal, ethnic and family groups, conflicts abound.¹ Since men are competitive and aggressive, there will always be conflicts among them, especially when scarce resources are unequally distributed among competitors and inequality is reflected in cultural and political relationships between groups.² Conflicts are a part of everyday life which is reflected in human close relations, at a societal level and on the international level.³ The universality and inevitability of conflict, throughout all known ages of the world, from the pre-historic to proto-historic and historic epochs, arguably, is no longer a subject of debate. Conflict is like one's shadow, one cannot run away from it; the more one tries to avoid it, the more it is being embraced.⁴

In traditional African society, conflict may generally exist whenever or wherever incompatible events occur and may result in "win-lose character". The resolution, transformation and management of conflict may however produce a win-win situation too.⁵ Conflict had been prevalent in traditional African society before the advent of colonialism and it can be traced to many aspects of African's cultural life, which tends to dictate their actions. Within every societal conflict, there is always a beneficiary who intends to use conflict as a resource for power control. Battles were fought and won; there were conquests, conversions, cessions, concessions and betrayals within and among the early Yoruba empires.⁶ Before the colonial period, the various ethnic nationalities which made up the present Nigeria existed as separate and distinct political

¹ Umezurike, G. 2016. "Traditional Society and Conflict Resolution in Nigeria: An Appraisal of Igbo Traditional Method of Conflict Resolution", in *Idosr Journal of Current Issues in Social Sciences*, Vol. 2, No. 1, 68.

² Alagoa E. J., 2001. "Conflict Resolution: The Nigerian Perspective", in *KIABARA: Journal of Humanities*, vol.7, No.1, 8.

³ Vestergaard, B., Helvard, E. and Sorensen, R. 2011. "Conflict Resolution – working with conflicts" A publication of Danish Centre for Conflict Resolution, 3.

⁴ Adeniyi, J. A. 2019. "Peace and Conflict Management in Traditional Yoruba Society", in *Journal of Living Together*, Vol. 6, No. 1, 203.

⁵ Anene, C. P. and Duru, S. S. 2019. "Conflict Resolution in the Traditional African Societies: The Nigerian and South African Examples", *Ulysses International Journal of Humanities and Contemporary Studies*, Vol. 1, No. 1, 94.

⁶ Anene, C. P. and Duru, S. S. 2019. "Conflict Resolution in the Traditional African Societies: The Nigerian and South African Examples", 95.

entities. This implies that they were distinct and had their different political, social, religious, cultural and traditional systems before the colonial masters merged them into what is now known as Nigeria. This means that each of these ethnic groups had their traditional methods/approaches to conflict resolution. Notable among the different ethnic groups in Nigeria are: Hausa, Fulani, Yoruba, and Igbo.⁷

Group structure cannot be said to be static in any given society as there is always a continuous interaction among the individuals and groups that make up the society. One group tends to dominate the other probably due to the constantly changing pattern of vested and competing interests. Under such a situation, groups in such societies tend to protect their values for survival and advancement of their aspirations.⁸ Everyone thus has a vested interest in the continuity and prosperity of his/her family or community. A society that is made up of such dominant group tendencies is bound to possess keen competition, rivalry and conflict about their values. This is because the interests of one group are most often inconsistent with that of another. A political system that is dominated by these egocentric competitive tendencies often finds its segments or groups at loggerheads and so can hardly survive the test of time. The problems of peaceful co-existence which pervaded the life of the Yoruba and Igbo during the pre-colonial period were the result of a multiplicity of political, social and economic factors which included land ownership, territorial boundaries, murder and inheritance among others.⁹

It has been considered that the various communities in pre-colonial Nigeria had varied conventions aimed at mitigating inter-human, intra- and inter-communal conflicts. These conventions were backed by taboos which must be observed for peaceful regulation of human activities. However, pre-colonial African societies are reputed to hold secrets of peacemaking and conflict resolution embedded in their customs and traditions before the disruptive activities brought about by colonisation.¹⁰

⁷ Umezurike, G. 2016. "Traditional Society and Conflict Resolution in Nigeria: An Appraisal of Igbo Traditional Method of Conflict Resolution", in *Idosr Journal of Current Issues in Social Sciences* Vol. 2, No. 1, 69.

⁸ Umezurike, G. 2016. "Traditional Society and Conflict Resolution in Nigeria: An Appraisal of Igbo Traditional Method of Conflict Resolution", 69.

⁹ Ezenwoko, F. A. and Osagie, J. I. 2014. "Conflict and Conflict Resolution in Pre-Colonial Igbo Society of Nigeria", in *Journal of Studies in Social Sciences* Vol. 9, No. 1, 139.

¹⁰ Oguntomisin G.O. 2004. "The Processes of Peacekeeping and Peacemaking in Pre-Colonial Nigeria", Ibadan: John Archers Publishers, 55

Essentially, conflicts have been experienced in Nigerian society for decades. The causes of conflicts in Nigerian society are diverse and are premised on a broad spectrum of factors which include competition over goals and interests that cannot be shared, usurpation or attempt to usurp the authority and position of one component by another component of society, inconsistencies in goals, increasing desire for autonomy or authority by the different individuals or groups in the community, scarcity or inadequacy of resources to meet the needs of the various components, various kinds of communication breakdown among others.¹¹

In traditional African societies, the enforcement of laws rested within the purview of various entities, including law enforcement agents, traditional police, and local courts. Disputants commonly sought resolution through the guidance of elders and neighbourhood mediators, who adeptly handled conflicts with swiftness and familiarity, often using the local language and adhering to established norms. Notably, among the Yoruba people, indigenous law finds its foundation in deeply rooted customs and age-old traditions.¹² Literacy was not associated only with the written word but also with verbal art and remembrance. Although the legal traditions of the Yoruba were predominantly oral, they were meticulously preserved and passed down through vibrant performances, ensuring their accessibility and vitality. Within the traditional Yoruba society, which fostered an environment conducive to sustained performance, adjudication was drawn from collective wisdom and ancestral knowledge, often dramatised for clarity and understanding. This period was characterised by elders convening beneath a sacred tree, and engaging in discussions until consensus was reached. Elders, revered for their age and seniority, embodied the cornerstone of order and decorum within the traditional framework, underscoring their crucial role as repositories of wisdom and knowledge within Yoruba culture.¹³

Cases of fighting among adolescents or young people were in the past accorded an impromptu settlement by the passers-by who normally ensured restoration of peace and harmony. ¹⁴There existed various community associations and guilds saddled with the responsibility of maintaining peace and order in marketing operations, stealing, debt and fraud. In

¹¹ Olaoba, O.B. 2005. "Ancestral Focus and the process of conflict resolution in Traditional African societies": Albert, A. O. (ed.) in *Perspectives on Peace and Conflict in Africa in Essays in Honour of General (Dr) Abdul Salam Abubakar*, Ibadan: John Archers Ltd, 22.

¹² Olaoba, O.B. 2001. "An Introduction to Africa Legal Culture. Ibadan: Hope Publications", 1-2.

¹³ Olaoba, O.B. 2001. "An Introduction to Africa Legal Culture, 2.

¹⁴ Olaoba, O.B. 2001. "An Introduction to Africa Legal Culture, 2.

certain circumstances, gods and ancestors (the living dead) are called upon, their spirits invoked and everyone especially the disputants is reminded of the aftermath of their wrath if they refuse to tell the truth. In the markets, and the palace (court) spirit is present. The spirit could be malevolent/benevolent.¹⁵

In Africa, there were levels or phases of conflict resolution, there were dispute resolutions at the interpersonal or family level, the extended family level and the village or town level (chief-in-council). These tiers represent the political units making up the community. The smallest unit called *Idile* (Nuclear family) is headed by a *Baale* (Head of Household). The next unit is the *Ebi*, (extended family) headed by *Mogaji/Olori Ebi* (compound head) who is the most influential or usually the eldest person in the extended family.¹⁶ The extended family includes all people who have blood ties. The last tier of the units is the ‘quarter’ which comprises several family compounds and is headed by a *Baale*, (The household includes the man’s immediate family, consisting of a wife or wives and children).¹⁷ Cases resolved by *Baale* include conflicts among co-wives, brothers and sisters, truants, and street fights involving his children and his foster children or dependents. Swift resolution of conflicts involves addressing minor issues by reprimanding the instigators and reconciling with those who were offended. It is imperative for the mediator to personally visit the aggrieved party, expressing gratitude for their willingness to accept an amicable resolution to the conflict. The *Baale* must call together his household and warn them to desist from making any more trouble.¹⁸

Disputes are addressed within local community courts, with the option for conflicting parties to file appeals. Notably, appeals can be escalated from the initial court to a secondary authority known as the court of the ward chief (*Ile-ejo ijoye Adugbo*). This court primarily handles civil cases and possesses the jurisdiction to conduct preliminary investigations into criminal matters before referring them to the court of the king (*Ile-ejo Oba*).¹⁹ *Baale* also controls the relationship between members of his family and outsiders. Once a matter is resolved, emphasis is

¹⁵ Olaoba, O.B. 2005. “Ancestral Focus and the process of conflict resolution in Traditional African societies”: Albert, A. O. (ed.) in *Perspectives on Peace and Conflict in Africa in Essays in Honour of General (Dr) Abdul Salam Abubakar*, Ibadan: John Archers Ltd, 22.

¹⁶ Albert, I. O. 2001. *Introduction to Third-Party Intervention in Community Conflict*. Ibadan: John Archers Publishers Ltd, Ibadan, 32.

¹⁷ Albert, I. O. 2001. *Introduction to Third-Party Intervention in Community Conflict*. 32.

¹⁸ Oguntomisin, G.O. 2004. *The Processes of Peace Keeping and Peace-Making in Pre-Colonial Nigeria*. Ibadan: John Archers, 10.

¹⁹ Oguntomisin, G.O. 2004. *The Processes of Peace Keeping and Peace-Making in Pre-Colonial Nigeria*. 11.

put on how good neighbourliness can be achieved and preserved. Land disputes, lack of good care for women and children by the husband, infidelity by the women, and inheritance disputes are the commonest in this category. However, dispute resolution by the Chief-in-council (*Igbimo Ilu*) in Yoruba land was the highest traditional institution for conflict resolution. In the pre-colonial era, the council had the power to pass a death sentence on any offender brought before it. The court of the king was the highest. It was also the last court to which an appeal could be made but, among Egba and Ijebu, the *Ogboni* and *Osugbo* court seemed to be the last court of appeal.²⁰ In customary dispute resolutions, there exists a traditional protocol wherein a woman typically begins by assuming a kneeling position and offering traditional greetings, unless the chief specifically grants permission to stand. Conversely, a man typically initiates the process by prostrating as a form of traditional greeting. Subsequently, whatever judgment is rendered is universally accepted.

In the traditional judiciary system of Yorubaland, mediators typically refrain from imposing fines for damages in civil cases. Instead, their primary objective is to foster peaceful resolution by amicably settling disputes. The paramount focus lies in restoring harmony within the community. However, on occasion, mediators may opt to levy modest fines as a preventive measure against specific antisocial behaviours.²¹ This could be requested in the form of kola nuts or local gins, both holding ritual significance. Portions of the kola nuts are often broken and circulated among participants, symbolising the commemoration of conflict resolution. Similarly, a communal drink is shared for all to partake. Should gin or palm wine not be accessible, regular drinking water suffices. In certain traditional contexts, palm wine or gin is ceremonially poured as a libation to honour the deities and ancestors connected to the disputants.²² These rituals serve to strengthen the bonds of reconciliation.

The methods of performing conflict resolution in traditional African societies are as follows: mediation, adjudication, reconciliation, arbitration and negotiation. It also includes employing extra-judicial devices and the usage of legal maxims to persuade or convince the disputants about the implication or otherwise of their behaviour. These methods have been effective in traditional African Society. Mediation is an old method of conflict management

²⁰ Oguntomisin, G.O. 2004. *The Processes of Peace Keeping and Peace-Making in Pre-Colonial Nigeria*: Ibadan: John Archers, 11.

²¹ Oguntomisin, G.O. 2004. *The Processes of Peace Keeping and Peace-Making in Pre-Colonial Nigeria*”, 11.

²² Oguntomisin, G.O. 2004. *The Processes of Peace Keeping and Peace-Making in Pre-Colonial Nigeria*, 11.

surrounded by secrecy. It involves the non-coercive intervention of the mediators(s), called the third party either to reduce, go beyond or bring conflict to a peaceful settlement.²³ Mediators are sought from within the communities or societies of the parties concerned. Elders are respected as trustworthy mediators all over Africa, because of their accumulated experiences and wisdom. Their roles depend on traditions, circumstances and personalities, accordingly. These roles include pressurising, making recommendations, giving assessments, conveying suggestions on behalf of the parties, emphasising relevant norms and rules, envisaging the situation if an agreement is not reached, or repeating the agreement already attained.²⁴

In traditional African society, adjudication involves bringing all disputants in the conflict to a meeting usually in the chambers or compounds of family heads, quarter heads and palace court as the case may be. Dialogue was linked with the adjudicatory processes. Reconciliation is the most significant aspect of conflict resolution. It is the end product of adjudication. After the disputants had been persuaded to end the dispute, peace was restored. This restoration of peace and harmony was always anchored on the principle of giving a little and getting a little. This idea buttresses the idea of the disputing parties to give concessions. A feast was usually organised to confirm the readiness of the conflicting parties towards reaching points of compromise.²⁵

Arbitration stands out as a prominent method for resolving conflicts in African traditional societies. This approach involves the intervention of a respected authority figure who serves as a mediator between conflicting parties. This mediator possesses the authority to make decisions that are binding on both parties involved. However, the primary aim is not merely to issue legal judgments but rather to facilitate reconciliation between the conflicting parties and their respective norms. The connection between this authority figure and the community is strengthened by the presence of community representatives who offer counsel and guidance to the authority figure. These representatives play a crucial role in ensuring that the decisions made align with the values and interests of the community as a whole.²⁶

²³ Ajayi, A. T. and Buhari, L. O. 2014. "Methods of Conflict Resolution in African Traditional Society" in *International Multidisciplinary Journal*, Vol. 8, No. 2, 138-149 .

²⁴ Bright-Brock, U. 2001. *Indigenous Conflict Resolution in Africa*. Institute of Educational Research, University of Oslo, 8- 11.

²⁵Olaoba, O.B. 2005. "Ancestral Focus and the process of conflict resolution in Traditional African societies": Albert, A. O. (ed.) in *Perspectives on Peace and Conflict in Africa in Essays in Honour of General (Dr) Abdul Salam Abubakar*, Ibadan: John Archers Ltd, 220-221.

In the art of negotiation, success lies in aligning the interests of all parties involved. Even in cases where conflict arises between an individual and society, the focus remains on restoring harmony and reintegrating the errant member into the social fabric. The rehabilitation of a dissenting member serves not only to reconcile differences but also to reinforce the unity and coherence of the community. Thus, effective conflict management seeks to address the concerns of both sides.²⁷ In traditional Yoruba society, peace was attained through negotiation. Central to this process was the act of apologising for transgressions committed against both individuals and the community as a whole. These apologies were typically conveyed through esteemed figures such as Yoruba elders, community leaders, and respected chiefs. Acting as representatives, these figures facilitated conflict resolution through dialogue and reconciliation. The role of the *Babaogun* (patron), was focal in this process, embodying the spirit of conflict resolution and mediation.²⁸

Conflict resolution through traditional mechanisms with its evolutionary dynamism and history, became pronounced in Okitipupa town in the pre-colonial period with the official presentation of instruments for resolving conflicts and ensuring peace in the town and the Yoruba society generally. The traditional conflict resolution ensures a state of tranquillity and serenity in Yorubaland. This period is important to the history of Okitipupa town as it changed the socio-political atmosphere of the town and promoted peace and development among the indigenous people of Okitipupa, its neighbouring towns and Yorubaland in general. As it is commonly said and believed by the Yoruba people; *Ibere Ogun lan 'ri, Enikan kan o mo ipari ogun*, meaning: 'The beginning of a conflict is witnessed, but no one can predict the outcome of the conflict'. This is aptly true that no one can justify the aftermath of a conflict whether it will be a win-to-win conflict or a win-or-lose conflict. No one can even predict which of the rival parties will be the victim. Conflict resolution performs a healing function in African societies. It provides an opportunity for the examination of alternative positive decisions to resolve differences. The inability to address conflicts arising from the competition for vital and shared resources, as well as differing

²⁶ Williams, Z. I. 2000. "Traditional Cures for Modern Conflict": *African Conflict Medicine*, Lynne Reiner Publisher Inc, 22-23.

²⁷ Olaoba, O.B. 2005. "Ancestral Focus and the process of conflict resolution in Traditional African societies": Albert, A. O. (ed.) in *Perspectives on Peace and Conflict in Africa in Essays in Honour of General (Dr) Abdul Salam Abubakar*, Ibadan: John Archers Ltd, 220-231.

²⁸ Olaoba, O.B. 2005. "Ancestral Focus and the Process of Conflict Resolution in Traditional African Societies": Albert, A. O. (ed.) 220-231

viewpoints on socio-political circumstances, carries a significant risk of escalating into acts of genocide or fratricide, as tragically witnessed in the historical conflict between the Ife and Modakeke communities in Yorubaland.²⁹

Statement of the Problem

Every research project explores a specific issue by adding new insights, reassessing existing knowledge, or suggesting practical solutions. Studies on Okitipupa have mainly focused on migration, settlement development, intergroup relations, and socio-economic activities. In terms of conflict resolution, past research highlights the positive role of traditional leaders and customs in settling social, economic, ethnic, communal, and political disputes. However, while these methods are recognized as effective and important, their deeper indigenous significance in Okitipupa remains largely unexplored.

Therefore, this research addressed existing gaps in knowledge by undertaking a comprehensive examination of the historical evolution and indigenous significance of conflict resolution mechanisms in Okitipupa town, situated in Ondo state, up to the year 2022. This investigation sought to enrich our understanding of the local dynamics shaping conflict resolution practices and their enduring relevance in the socio-cultural fabric of the community.

Objectives of the Study

The general objective of this study is to examine the history of traditional conflict resolution mechanisms in Okitipupa town of Ondo state up to 2022. The specific objectives include:

1. Discuss the nature and causes of the conflicts among the Okitipupa people.
2. Assess the traditional conflict resolution mechanisms in Okitipupa.
3. Analyse the changes and continuity in traditional conflict resolution mechanisms in Okitipupa.
4. Discuss the challenges facing traditional conflict resolution mechanisms in Okitipupa.

Research Questions

To achieve the objectives of this study, the researchers raised the following questions;

²⁹ Punier, G. 1995. *The Rwanda Crisis: History of Genocide*. New York: Columbia University Press, 55.

1. What were the nature and causes of the conflicts among the Okitipupa people?
2. What were the traditional conflict resolution mechanisms in Okitipupa?
3. What were the changes and continuity in traditional conflict resolution mechanisms in Okitipupa?
4. What were the challenges facing traditional conflict resolution mechanisms in Okitipupa?

Justification of the Study

Research plays a crucial role in contemporary society, addressing gaps in knowledge and offering insights into the mysteries that intrigue individuals deeply attuned to their surroundings. It serves as a gateway to understanding both the known and the unexplored, enriching our comprehension of history and equipping us with the tools to navigate the complexities of the present. This study aims to explore the enduring relevance of traditional conflict resolution mechanisms in Okitipupa town of Ondo State, up to 2022. Against the backdrop of the often contentious nature of traditional conflict resolution methods across Nigerian communities, this research serves as a poignant reminder of the significance of these age-old practices. It sheds light on the cultural values that underpin traditional institutions, emphasising their focal role in fostering social cohesion and communal harmony. By elucidating the efficacy of these institutions as pillars of enduring stability, this study not only contributes to the preservation of traditional wisdom but also holds promise for bolstering the foundations of nation-building and societal development.

Scope of the Study

This study focuses on Okitipupa, a town in Ondo State, as its area of investigation. By narrowing the scope to this specific location, the research provides an in-depth analysis of traditional conflict resolution mechanisms while considering unique local practices and variations. The study examines changes, adaptations, and enduring traditions in these mechanisms up to the year 2022. This timeframe is particularly significant as it coincides with the twentieth coronation anniversary of the *Jegun* of Okitipupa, offering a valuable context for understanding the evolution of these customs. By setting this temporal boundary, the research captures both historical developments and contemporary practices, shedding light on the continuity and transformation of traditional conflict resolution in the Okitipupa community.

Review of Related Literature

A lot has been written on Okitipupa town by scholars and writers of different affiliations and callings. This does not, however, remove the fact that there is a paucity of literature directly related to the focus of this study. Having said this, some scholarly works have been carefully selected for review within the content and interpretation of this study. There is no gainsaying that the Yoruba as a group has been well and severely researched by scholars of diverse persuasions. Asiwaju rightly observes this much when he states that there is perhaps no other single African people who have quite commanded as much attention of scholars of all disciplines as the Yoruba.³⁰

The perspective put forth by Asiwaju finds reinforcement in a collaborative work by Arifalo and Ogen titled ‘The Yoruba in History up to 1987’.³¹ In this piece, they assert that the Yoruba ethnic group is one of the most extensively studied worldwide. By 1976, despite notable omissions, the literature on the Yoruba numbered 3,488 titles, a testament to the substantial and unparalleled depth of research in sub-Saharan Africa.³² However, despite the considerable breadth of existing literature on various aspects of Yoruba history, discerning scholars and readers may find certain gaps that render the current body of work unsatisfactory. History, after all, is an ongoing dialogue, emphasising the concept of continuity. It is worth noting that while significant attention has been directed towards the central and other parts of Yorubaland, the northern and northeastern regions have yet to receive commensurate scholarly focus.

Moreover, the available primary and secondary literature concerning these areas is not only limited in quantity but also lacks valid discussions on essential topics, such as the perpetuation of conflict resolution traditions in locales like Okitipupa town. Existing studies on Okitipupa primarily delve into its origins, the diminishing role of traditional political institutions, disputes over kingship and chieftaincy, and debates regarding the relevance of traditional institutions vis-à-vis contemporary governance structures. Regrettably, these discussions often overlook the traditional methods of conflict resolution, failing to acknowledge their significance in preserving cultural heritage and historical narratives. This study aims to address these lacunae, particularly

³⁰ Asiwaju, A.I. 1983. “The Dynamics of Yoruba Studies” in Olusanya G.O. (ed.) *Studies in Yoruba History and Culture: Essays in Honour of Professor S.O. Biobaku*, Ibadan University Press Limited. 26.

³¹ Arifalo S.O. and Ogen O. 2003. *The Yoruba in History up to 1987*, Lagos: First Academic Publisher. 1. They rely on details available in Falola Toyin, *Yoruba Gurus: Indigenous Production of Knowledge in Africa*, Treton: African World Press, 15. Cited in Okajare, S. T. 2012. “The Akoko-Yoruba and Their Neighbours, 1800-1960: A Study in Inter-Group Relations” “ a PhD thesis submitted to the Department of History and International Studies, Ekiti State University, Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria. 7.

³² Arifalo S.O. and Ogen O. 2003. *The Yoruba in History up to 1987*, Lagos: First Academic Publisher. 1.

within the context of Okitipupa. Various relevant works, available in print and serving as valuable reference materials, are reviewed herein and categorised into sub-themes to facilitate a comprehensive historical analysis.

‘The History of the Yorubas’³³ by Reverend Samuel Johnson comprehensively chronicles vital aspects of Yoruba history, thus offering general and contextual background information for the present study. The book discusses the Yoruba as a people, their land, belief system, dress codes, festivals, economy, aesthetics, social organisations and entertainment, political organisation, the process of state formation, and inter-state relations. The book is highly invaluable. All these details are useful information about aspects of Yoruba history. Yet, there is a notable lacuna in the work as no satisfactory mention is made of Okitipupa which developed fairly well within the period covered by the author. Johnson’s work makes no considerable mention of the Okitipupa axis of Yorubaland and largely constitutes an account of Oyo history, presented sweepingly as the larger Yoruba history. However, despite these obvious inadequacies, the book is of huge importance to the study of Yoruba history, and of course, the present inquiry since the political history of Okitipupa town cannot be discussed in isolation of the larger Yoruba macro-political milieu. Consequently, the work opens a vista for further inquiry, a part of which the present study is. This work is closely related to the study as Okitipupa town forms part of Yoruba towns. However, the work does not cover the town precisely in terms of conflict and its traditional resolving methods.

Ajisafe Moore in his work titled ‘The Laws and Customs of the Yoruba People’,³⁴ Validates the strength of the customs and native laws of the Yoruba ethnic group as the most subject focus can readily be likened to prevailing contemporary customs and laws. The twenty-four chapters of laws and customs are organised thematically, with each chapter presenting one aspect of the custom or native law of the Yoruba people spanning marriage and family life including widowhood, civil and social relationships, government structure, civic responsibility to society, property rights, dispute resolution and sanctions for wrongdoings, security for credit, traditional medicine and divination, animal husbandry, funeral, widowhood and so on. The work closes with a rich supplement which provides additional customary practices relating to property rights, tenancy rights, secret societies, hospitality, and salutation, especially force holders. The author starts by outlining the family structure of the Yoruba, unlike the Western contemporary custom,

³³ Johnson, S. 1921. *The History of the Yorubas*, Lagos: CSS Bookshop, 12.

³⁴ Ajisafe, M. 2010. *The Laws and Customs of the Yoruba People*, Abeokuta: Ola Fola Bookshops, 66.

family among the Yoruba transcends the nuclear family and encompasses a person's kith and kin or clan (*idile*) as well as a well-behaved servant who has lived long with his master. He notes the wide brotherhood and sisterhood norm which probably accounts for why there is no single Yoruba word for an uncle, aunt, cousin, nephew or niece. However, he highlights a custom of respect with the use of the words, 'elder' or 'senior' (*egbon*) and 'younger' or 'junior' (*aburo*) alongside other words to correctly describe a person's relationship with another. The study covers the political and social life of the Yoruba starting from the communal living of the people with their indigenous laws and customs which provide a state of serenity among the people and ensure conflict resolution.³⁵ However, the work did not x-ray the traditional conflict resolution mechanism in Okitipupa town of Ondo State.

Biobaku, in his work titled, 'Sources of the Yoruba History',³⁶ examines the history of the Yoruba concerning the *Ifa* cult, proverbs, songs and poems, as well as ceremonies in Yorubaland. He also points to the political and social structure of the Yoruba people with their different weapons of warfare. The work also x-rays the mask from Ikorodu for the *Magbo* cult, the *Agbo* mask of the Ijebu Ekine cult, the *Ifa* bowl from Ijebu-Ode and a detailed account of several carved doors by *Olowe* of Ise Ekiti. The writer lays more emphasis on Oyo, Bini, Ikere-Ekiti and other towns in Yorubaland. The work however, provides us with background knowledge on the socio-cultural and political lifestyle of some Yoruba towns and cities and their traditions which forms an important part of this research, but fails to emphasise conflict resolution mechanisms in some towns and communities such as Okitipupa town.

Olubunmi gives a detailed account of 'The Rise and Fall of the Yoruba Race'.³⁷ The work explains vividly the genesis of the Yoruba, racing its origin from the Ile-Ife. According to his assertion, there were no human beings before the presence of the proto-Yoruba. It was from this Yoruba prototype that others developed form. This proto (original) Yoruba skeleton is dated to have lived between 10,000 and 8000 BC. The current discourse stands to gain significantly from his inclusion of additional evidence from the field of linguistics, supporting the assertion that the Yoruba language has been spoken in the region of Ile-Ife for over 4000 years. He also discusses the geographical location of the Yoruba-speaking people, the composition of the group, and the

³⁵ Ajisafe, M. 2010. *The Laws and Customs of the Yoruba People*, 66.

³⁶ Biobaku, S. O. 1973. *Source of the Yoruba History*, Oxford: Clarendon Press, 34.

³⁷ Olubunmi, A. O. (ed). 2007. *The Rise and Fall of the Yoruba Race*, Ilorin: Longman Group Limited, 16.

various dialects spoken by the sub-groups. More to that, general aspects of Yoruba history like traditions of origin, their socio-cultural life, political structure, and the rise and fall of kingdoms were adequately discussed leaving another aspect of the Yoruba history untouched or not adequately treated. The information in this work enriches the work understudy and provides additional information about the development of the Yoruba race and also how different kingdoms and empires fell and most kingdoms fell through conflict. However, the conflict resolution mechanism in Okitipupa town is not featured in the work.

Robert S. Sydney in his work 'The Kingdom of the Yoruba' also brings awareness to how the Yoruba ethnic group came into being. He started with the evolution of the Yoruba people, linking it to Ile-Ife as their traditional home. The writer also examines some major factors that prompted the establishment of many Yoruba communities today. These included amongst others, economic pursuit, political aspiration, migration, conflict and war, inter-marriages etc. The work discusses conflict among Yoruba societies. He asserted that many Yoruba communities today, were once a settlement of hunters, farmers, and others who settled there as resting points for their economic pursuit which is the central focus of this research. Also, he discusses some towns like Owo and Ondo that are near Okitipupa, but the work did not discuss issues relating to the history of conflict resolution mechanisms in Okitipupa town.

The work of Atanda, titled 'An Introduction to Yoruba History',³⁸ addresses the people of Yorubaland. The author focuses on various modes of economy in Yorubaland which include: agriculture, trade and indigenous industry. On agriculture, the writer maintains that it was the most important economic activity of the people which was not only carried out for a mere purpose but also, for profit motive. In addition, he argues that there are occupations that equally caught people's attention and served as means of livelihood such as cloth weaving, dyeing, food production, household utensils, leather works, calabash carving, and basket weaving, to mention but a few. This work is of great significance to the study as it reveals the economic system and other aspects of the Yoruba people, under which Okitipupa belongs. However, the work does not focus on the present study.

³⁸ Atanda, J. A. 1980. *An Introduction to Yoruba History*, Ibadan: Ibadan University Press, 35.

The work by Adepeju and Ayeni, 'The Yoruba Culture of Nigeria',³⁹ discusses the origin of the Yoruba. The writers claim that the Yoruba hailed from Ile-Ife founded by Oduduwa who had sixteen sons who later played important roles in founding other communities and towns that make up the Yoruba kingdom. Furthermore, the writers give attention to the Yoruba pre-colonial government, conflict, music and dance, traditional marriage, and some other aspects that depict the Yoruba culture and traditions. This work covers the Yoruba culture, which Okitipupa town is a part of, but does not dwell on the conflict resolution of the town itself.

Oguntomisin in his edited work titled, 'A Comprehensive History of the Yoruba People up to 1800',⁴⁰ explores the origin, culture and tradition of the Yoruba; it highlights the politics and government of some Yoruba kingdoms and particularly the Oyo empire, the Owu, Ijebu, Egba, Ketu and Sabe. The work also addresses the political traditions, laws and customs guiding the affairs of the indigenous Yoruba. Though Okitipupa town is not discussed, the work remains significant as it answers certain fundamental questions on the political life of the Yoruba involving conflict, to which the people of Okitipupa belong.

Akinjogbin in his book, 'Milestones and Concepts in Yoruba History and Culture',⁴¹ argues that the Yoruba have not described themselves, their language, and their land as Yoruba people, Yorubaland, or Yoruba culture, but that the different groups that made up contemporary Yorubaland were, until the closing quarters of the nineteenth century were independent of one another and, as such, went by their different names such as Oyo, Ijebu, Ife, Ondo, Sabe, etc. While this is incontestable, Isaac Akinjogbin, however, maintains that the different polities recognised each other as a commonwealth of related brothers/kingdoms. He wrote extensively on the history and cultural lifestyle of the Yoruba nation but did not draw attention to the history of conflict resolution among the people of Okitipupa.

Afolayan's 'Kingdoms of the Yoruba: Socio-political Development Before 1800',⁴² reveals the uniqueness that is featured in the evolutionary history of kingship institutions in Yorubaland

³⁹Adepeju, O. and Ayeni, O. 2013. "Yoruba Culture of Nigeria Creating Space for an Endangered Species" *Journal of Cross-Cultural Communication*, Vol. 9, No. 4, 58.

⁴⁰ Atanda, J. A. 2007. "A Comprehensive History of the Yoruba People up to 1800" in Oguntomisin, G.O. (ed.) *An Introduction in Yoruba History*, Ibadan: John Archers Publishers, 87.

⁴¹ Akinjogbin, I.A. 2002. *Milestones and Concepts in Yoruba History and Culture*, Ibadan: Longman Press, 102.

⁴²Afolayan, F. 1998. "Kingdoms of the Yoruba: Socio-Political Development before 1800" in Ogunremi D. and Adediran B. (eds.), *Culture and Society in Yorubaland*. Ibadan: Rex Charles Publication, 14-26

before 1800 and the impacts of traditional institutions on conflict resolution. Admitting that the Yoruba socio-political history was characterised by the existence of several kingdoms, the author discusses these kingdoms in turn and links each of them with Ile-Ife, which in extant Yoruba tradition is recognised as the source of origin (*orirun*). The kingdoms covered include Owu, Oyo, Ijesa, Ekiti (discussed as a country with some kingdoms), Igbomina, Owo, Ondo, Ijebu, Egba, Egbado and Awori, among others.⁴³ Afolayan gives an incisive account of the process through which each of the states/kingdoms emerged and consolidated its power. The author further strengthens the well-known fact that despite the differences both in size and complexity among Yoruba kingdoms, their basic socio-political system followed a similar pattern with occasional local variations arising from local peculiarities. He gives a copious description of the socio-political system. This will be relevant to the present effort.

‘The Military in Nineteenth Century Yoruba Politics’, a six-chapter book edited by Toyin Falola and Dare Oguntomisin is a very useful scholarly work for this study. The book observes that the Yoruba have never come under one single political authority. It goes to aver that each of the various kingdoms founded by different groups of the Yoruba seems to have developed independently under its ruling aristocracy on which it depended for its social, economic and political organisations.⁴⁴ Consequently, the government of one Yoruba kingdom was, to some extent, structurally different from the other. Structural difference was not particularly noticeable in town governments; but as the towns developed into kingdoms with subordinate territories and central governments with varying degrees of complexities were evolved by different groups of the Yoruba, structural differences or patterns of government became more manifest. The role of women in Yoruba politics was also appraised. The work equally discussed the events that brought the military (warlords of the prolonged warfare of the nineteenth century) into playing dominant roles in the politics of Yorubaland. It concludes that the problem of insecurity to life and property that prevailed in Yorubaland in the nineteenth century was mainly responsible for the emergence of military administration in some Yoruba towns in particular and, in general, the dominant role played in politics by war chiefs in Yorubaland at this period.⁴⁵ Although the features of the different

⁴³ Afolayan, F.1998. “Kingdoms of the Yoruba: Socio-Political Development before 1800” in Ogunremi D. and Adediran B. (eds.), *Culture and Society in Yorubaland*, 14-26.

⁴⁴ Falola, T. and Oguntomisin, D. (eds.) 1984. *The Military in Nineteenth Century Yoruba Politics*, Oyo: Anchor print and Packaging Co. 118.

⁴⁵ Falola, T. and Oguntomisin, D. (eds.) 1984. *The Military in Nineteenth Century Yoruba Politics*, 118.

forms of government evolved by the military differed largely from the traditional Yoruba pattern of government, the fact that can be garnered from the emergence was that they were contingent political arrangements designed to meet the demands of the period. Even though the work made a passing reference to Okitipupa Yoruba communities, it has nevertheless helped to provide in-depth knowledge on the dynamics of the general Yoruba conflict and conflict resolution in the nineteenth century, which is directly relevant to this work.

Adebile Paul in his article, ‘The Ondo Peace Diplomacy: Disclosures on African Indigenous Conflict Resolution Culture’,⁴⁶ discusses African indigenous conflict resolution culture. It zooms in on the Ondo, a sub-ethnic entity among the Yoruba; one of Africa’s largest cultural stalks, and discloses the traditional conflict resolution ethos of the Ondo cultural element. The work contends that before colonial ideological infiltrations, there existed home-grown approaches for resolving conflicts within the several but distinct traditional African states. Findings from the article reveal that home-grown methods of this sort have proven suitable and effective in the resolution of conflict situations within Ondoland as it were, and are still being used in the settlement of disputes which appear intractable with contemporary Western approaches. This work is very relevant to this research as Okitipupa is within the same state as Ondoland.

‘Conflict and Conflict Resolution in Pre-Colonial Igbo Society of Nigeria’ by Ezenwoko and Osagie⁴⁷ examines conflict and conflict resolution among the Igbo of Nigeria in the pre-colonial period. The work portrays the fact that conflicts have always been part of human societies. As long as individuals or societies interact, conflicts are inevitable due to the diverse interests among them. In pre-colonial Igbo society, various types of conflicts manifested. These included inter-personal, intra-community and inter-community conflicts, some of which led to wars. However, there were various means by which these conflicts were resolved to the satisfaction of the warring parties. The writers note that the conflict resolution mechanism was an integral part of pre-colonial Igbo village democracy. The absence of a centralised system of government among the people in the pre-colonial period did not mean that the people were in a state of anarchy. As in most pre-colonial African societies, there were bound to be conflicts amongst individuals and

⁴⁶ Adebile, O.P. 2023. ‘The Ondo Peace Diplomacy: Disclosures on African Indigenous Conflict Resolution Culture’. *Humanus Discourse: Journal of Faculty of Humanities*, Redeemer’s University Ede, Osun State Nigeria, Vol 3, No 2, 1.

⁴⁷ Ezenwoko, F. A. and Osagie, J. I. 2014 “Conflict and Conflict Resolution in Pre-Colonial Igbo Society of Nigeria”, in *Journal of Studies in Social Sciences* Vol. 9, No. 1, 118.

communities but there also existed traditional methods by which they were resolved to ensure that peace and order were achieved and maintained in the society. The work however examines the traditional conflict resolution in Nigerian society but does not launch into the interior of conflict resolution mechanisms in Okitipupa town.

The journal article of Ajayi and Buhari titled, ‘Methods of conflict resolution in African Traditional Society’,⁴⁸ explores the patterns or mechanisms for conflict resolution in traditional African societies with particular reference to Yoruba and Igbo societies in Nigeria and Pondo tribe in South Africa. The study notes that conflict resolution in traditional African societies provides an opportunity to interact with the parties concerned, it promotes consensus-building, social bridge reconstructions and enactment of order in the society. The study submits further that the Western world placed more emphasis on the judicial system presided over by council of elders, kings’ courts, people (open place), assemblies, etc; for dispute settlement and justice dispensation. It concludes that traditional conflict resolution techniques such as mediation, adjudication, reconciliation, and negotiation as well as cross-examination which were employed by Africans in the past, offer greater prospects for peaceful co-existence and harmonious relationships in post-conflict periods than the modern method of litigation settlements in law courts. The study is relevant as it examines the conflict resolution mechanisms in Yoruba society and African society in general but does not dwell upon the traditional conflict resolution mechanism of Okitipupa town in particular.

The work of Bello and Onuoha, ‘Traditional Institutions and Nation Building for Sustainable Development in Contemporary Nigeria: Roles and Challenges’,⁴⁹ examines the role of traditional institutions in nation-building. The work reveals that in the pre-colonial era, the roles of traditional institutions were more of governance; shaping appropriate policies, ordering priorities and generating revenue to meet the needs of their communities, maintaining peace and resolving issues in the society, however, the introduction of colonialism brought a shift to their functions and some of their roles. The article further explains that traditional institutions are seen

⁴⁸ Ajayi, A.T. and Buhari, L.O. 2014 “Methods of conflict resolution in African traditional society”, *International Multidisciplinary Journals; African Research Review*, Vol. 8, No. 2, 26.

⁴⁹ Bello, M.E., and Onuoha, L.C. 2021. "Traditional Institutions and Nation Building for Sustainable Development in Contemporary Nigeria: Roles and Challenges", *A Historical Scholarship, Society and Education Industry in Nigeria: A Festschrift in Honour of Professor Rasheed Ajetunmobi*, Department of History and Diplomatic Studies, Tai Solarin University of Education, Ogun State. 264-275.

as impartial arbitrators who were looked up to for the adjudication of cases and resolution of conflicts. They play significant roles in settling disputes among people in their respective domains, they make sure they settle the land-related disputes, community disputes, and religious crises before they worsen into exposed aggressions that people kill one another. The work is relevant to this study as it scrutinises the roles of traditional institutions in peacekeeping and conflict resolution, but it does not refer to how conflicts are resolved in Okutipupa.

Osayekemwen Ojo Ebenezer's 'The Role of Traditional Institutions in Conflict Resolution among Okija People'⁵⁰ identifies traditional institutions for conflict resolution in the Okija peace processes among Okija people in the Ihiala local government area of Anambra State. The study finds that the traditional institutions for conflict resolution included the *Ezi* (the family), *Okpara* (elders), *Umunna* (men who are born into the clan), *Umuada* (women who were born into a clan), or *NdiInyom* (married women), *Amala* (the Council of Elders), traditional Religious Approach secret societies, or the masquerades. The study recommends the greater inclusion of these traditional institutions in conflict resolution among people instead, as they are closer to people at the grassroots than the formal institutions for conflict resolution in the contemporary period. The study covers the history and relevance of traditional rulers in resolving conflicts and maintaining a state of peace and order among the Okija people in the Ihiala local government area of Anambra state. However, the study does not feature the history of conflict resolution among the people of Okutipupa.

Ajayi Olalekan Ezekiel and Issa Abdulraheem's 'Traditional Methods of Conflict Management and Resolutions: The Case of the Old Oyo Empire'⁵¹ looks at traditional African conflict resolution methods, specifically in Yoruba-speaking communities in Nigeria's western region. According to the paper, the Old Oyo Empire used traditional conflict resolution techniques such as mediation, adjudication, and reconciliation, as well as cross-examination, to offer a chance to interact with the parties involved, promote consensus building, reconstruct social bridges, and enforce order in the society. The Western world regards these methods as superior for promoting peaceful coexistence. The traditional method of conflict management and resolution is thus

⁵⁰ Osayekemwen, O.E. 2014. "The Role of Traditional Institutions in Conflict Resolution among Okija People": *Department of Sociology and Anthropology*, Baze University, Abuja.

⁵¹ Ajayi, O. E. and Issa, A. 2022. "Traditional Methods of Conflict Management and Resolutions: The Case of the Old Oyo Empire" in *European Journal of Management and Marketing*. Vol. 7, No. 4, 23.

recommended because it is less expensive and friendlier, and further national research into the causes of the 16-year-long inter-border war Ekiti-Parapo, popularly known as the Kiriji War, is also recommended for further finding. The content of this scholarly article is relevant to this study as it bridges the gap of knowledge about traditional conflict resolution in Oyo, one of the indigenous towns in Yorubaland, although the study did not examine the traditional methods of conflict resolution among the people of Okitipupa.

Abdulsalam et.al, in their journal article ‘Roles of Traditional Rulers in Conflict Resolution for Sustainable Democracy in Nigeria’,⁵² highlight the roles of traditional rulers in conflict resolution in Kwara State, Nigeria. The study explains that traditional rulers maintain law and order, ensure security, manage, control and resolve conflicts among individuals and groups in Nigerian society. The roles of traditional rulers in conflict resolution include reconciling and integrating both parties in conflicts, maintaining law and order in the communities, promoting the use of informal settlements, checks and balances in the society, managing improper communication and interaction breakdowns among their subjects, fostering communal solidarity and unity, engendering peaceful co-existence of people of different religious, ethnic and social background, dealing with pressures from external forces outside the community that results in breeding internal pressures as well as facilitating socio-cultural bridge reconstructions in post-conflict situation. This work is useful to this research as it reveals the roles of traditional rulers in the conflict resolution process.

On the whole, there are many written works done on the history of Yoruba and its migration patterns to which Okitipupa town belongs. The various works on the Yoruba race share certain relevance with the study under investigation, and this research stands to benefit a lot from the reviewed literature as the extent of knowledge and the gap(s) to be filled have been identified through the available works. Given this, it is important to note that there is no single text dedicated to the history of traditional conflict resolution mechanisms in Okitipupa town, which is one of the most promising communities in Ondo State. There is therefore the need to examine the history of traditional conflict resolution mechanisms in Okitipupa in Okitipupa Local Government Area of Ondo State to bridge the gap(s) in the present knowledge of the town.

⁵² Abdulsalam, A. A., Olokooba I. N., Okafor, I. P. and Adedoyin, C. A. 2020. “Roles of Traditional Rulers in Conflict Resolution for Sustainable Democracy in Nigeria” in *Nigerian Journal of Social Studies*, Vol.23, No.23, 114.

Methodology

The historical approach was adopted in this research, and both primary and secondary sources were utilised. The reconstruction of the Okitipupa community history demands that all forms of available sources are cautiously consulted and professionally employed for analysis. This is to allow for proper appreciation of the dialogue that existed between the past and the present and how they have been interpreted and represented.

The primary sources were derived from in-depth interviews conducted with twenty-five purposively selected respondents based on their knowledge of the history of traditional conflict resolution among the people of Okitipupa, as well as assessments reports from the National Archives, Ibadan. Secondary sources used were books, journal articles, monographs, national dailies, dissertations, theses and materials from the internet. All data were subjected to historical analysis.

CHAPTER TWO

HISTORICAL FOUNDATION OF OKITIPUPA TOWN

The Land and People of Okitipupa

Okitipupa is one of the major towns and administrative headquarters of Okitipupa Local Government Area of Ondo State, with neighbouring communities such as Ode-Erinje, Ikoya, Ode-Aye, Ayila, Araromi, Igbodan-Lisa, Okanmo, Ayeka, Ode-Idepe, among others.⁵³ The people of Okitipupa also share certain economic, social and political relationships with these neighbouring towns. Okitipupa has always been the central town for the inhabitants of Ondo South Senatorial District of Ondo State, comprising Okitipupa, Irele, Ilaje, Ese-Odo, Odigbo and Ile-Oluji/Oke-Igbo Local Governments respectively.⁵⁴ The town lies on the longitude 4° 48' 9.06"E and latitude 6° 29' 43.14"N.⁵⁵ It comprises the Ikale-speaking nation in Ondo State and has an estimated population of three hundred thousand (300,000) people.⁵⁶ The weather conditions of the town vary between the two seasons, that is, the rainy (May-October) and the dry seasons (November-April). The Harmattan dust also accompanies the dry season.⁵⁷

⁵³ Interview held with Mr. Akingbe Ayo, Age 47, Farmer, at Ogbole Street, Okitipupa on the 12th of March, 2024.

⁵⁴ Interview held with Mr. Akingbe Ayo, Age 47, Farmer, at Ogbole Street, Okitipupa on the 12th of March, 2024.

⁵⁵ https://www.longitude-latitude-maps.com/city/156_760,Okitipupa,Ondo,Nigeria Accessed on the 14th of March, 2024

⁵⁶ <https://web.archive.org/web/20091007011423/http://www.nipost.gov.ng/PostCode.aspx> Accessed on the 14th of March, 2024.

⁵⁷ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Okitipupa> Accessed on the 14th of March, 2024.

Map of Ondo State showing the study area (Okitipupa).

Sources: https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Map-of-Ondo-State-showing-the-study-area-Okitipupa_fig1_364131940
(Accessed on the 12th of March, 2024).

Okitipupa has a favourable climatic condition. The availability of the fine climate has broadly enhanced the cultivation of arable and cash crops, which has further contributed to the economic development of the area. The major source of occupation in the town is agriculture. Agriculture provides income and employment for about 80% of the populace. Natives of Okitipupa are predominantly farmers, the major crops known to them are, palm, rubber and cassava. They also cultivated yams, beans, okra, pepper, melon and vegetables. Their staple food includes, baked cassava, popularly known as *pupuru*, yam, rice, yam flour and cassava flakes (*garri*), among others. The town has its major market known as *Oja* Okitipupa, a periodic market which is opened every five days.⁵⁸ Various traders frequented the market, offering a diverse array of goods such as

⁵⁸ Interview held with Mrs. Olotu Esther, Age 49+, Trader, at Ewi-Oke Street, Okitipupa on the 14th of April, 2024.

farm produce, crafts, bush meats, fish, and other merchandise. Both sellers and buyers found the market appealing, as it fostered robust trading relationships within the community, earning it a reputation for its significant role in promoting commerce. Moreover, the majority of traders were affiliated with guilds, facilitating their presence within the market and enhancing their ability to locate one another during trading activities. This guild membership not only fostered a sense of camaraderie among traders but also facilitated the establishment of cooperative societies, wherein they shared social responsibilities beyond commerce.⁵⁹ Other markets in the town, such as *Oja* Obulumore and *Oja* Ogbotako, significantly bolstered the local economy. These bustling hubs attract many customers, both residents and visitors from afar. However, it is noteworthy that *Oja* Okitipupa stands out with its extensive network of traders and unparalleled patronage.⁶⁰

Okitipupa is also known as Idepe, and it is acknowledged as the headquarters of the Ikale people. During the colonial era, the town served as the divisional headquarters of the then Okitipupa Division which comprised four major subgroups: the Ikale, the Ilaje, the Apoi and the Arogbo. In terms of its socio-political structure, the Idepe kingdom is made up of a conglomeration of several lineages (*ebi*); each *ebi* has its own village or farm settlement (*egunre*). The various *ebi* making up the Idepe kingdom are united under a common Idepe identity and a common capital, *ode* - where all the federating *ebi* also have their parcels of land - common festivals, rituals and a single monarch, the *Jegun* of Idepe.⁶¹

The people of Okitipupa are renowned for their distinctiveness in embracing traditional religion, particularly the African Traditional Religion (ATR), predating the era of colonial influence. Their spiritual practices revolve around various deities or gods, revered to foster harmony and prosperity within their community while seeking blessings and auspiciousness for themselves and future generations. It is noteworthy that each deity is honoured annually through traditional festivals such as *Esu*, *Ogun*, *Oro*, *Ogigi*, *Ere* (Masquerade), and *Iwo*, among others.⁶² Despite the impact of the introduction of Islam and Christianity on traditional religious beliefs,

⁵⁹ Interview held with Mrs. Olotu Esther, Age 49+, Trader, at Ewi-Oke Street, Okitipupa on the 14th of March, 2024.

⁶⁰ Interview held with Mrs. Olotu Esther, Age 49+, Trader, at Ewi-Oke Street, Okitipupa on the 14th of March, 2024.

⁶¹ National Archives Ibadan (NAI) Ondo Prof. CSO 26/4 30030, Assessment Report on the Ikale District of Okitipupa Division by B.J.A Mathews, 1932, 175-176. As cited in Ogen, O. 2012. 'Exploring the Potential of Praise Poems for Historical Reconstruction among the Idepe-Ikale in Southeastern Yorubaland'. *History in Africa*, Vol 12, 80.

⁶² Interview held with Chief Adeola Akinloye, Age 70, Traditionalist, at Ewi-Isale Street, Okitipupa on the 14th of March, 2024.

certain traditionalists in the town persist in their worship and celebration of their ancestral deities. They maintain a steadfast belief that these deities have historically and will continue to provide protection and support for them and their families.⁶³

Tradition of Origin of Okitipupa

According to oral tradition, Okitipupa traces its origins back to its earlier name, Ode-Idepe. The transition to Okitipupa occurred through a confluence of factors: the geographical features of elevated terrain, the settlement of the people in a new area, and the distinct reddish hue of the soil, known as *pupa* in the Ikale dialect. The term *Okiti* signifies “hilly land”, with *pupa* denoting the characteristic red colouration. This amalgamation of the Ikale Yoruba words, *Okiti* and *pupa*, gradually evolved into the appellation “Okitipupa”, which came to identify the town, particularly as a trading hub in its central market.⁶⁴ Historical narratives suggest that colonial settlers encountering the striking red hills were captivated, leading to the designation of Idepe as the “red hill community”. Over time, this designation underwent linguistic interpretation, culminating in the amalgamation of *Okiti* (hills) and *pupa* (red) to form “Okitipupa”. Nonetheless, within the local populace, the interchangeability of the town's name with Ode-Idepe persisted.⁶⁵

The origin of Idepe is shrouded in various historical narratives, each offering distinct perspectives. These divergent accounts stem from a scarcity of written records detailing early events in Idepe and the broader Ikale community. Multiple factors contribute to this historiographical gap, notably the delayed arrival of Christian missionaries to the region and the limited access to modern education until the early twentieth century. Additionally, the colonial era solidified historical and historiographical paradigms that prioritised centres like the precolonial Oyo Empire and the ancient city-state of Ile-Ife as the nucleus of the Yoruba nation, overshadowing peripheral Yoruba states, such as those under the sway of neighbouring powers.

Consequently, Ikale's origins and ethnic identity were often subsumed under hegemonic narratives, particularly those stemming from the period of Benin imperialism in the seventeenth century and later reinforced during colonial rule. These dominant narratives have perpetuated the

⁶³ Interview held with Mr Akingbe Ayo, Age 47, Farmer, at Ogbole Street, Okitipupa on the 12th of March, 2024.

⁶⁴ Interview held with Chief Adeola Akinloye, Age 70, Traditionalist, at Ewi-Isale Street, Okitipupa on the 14th of March, 2024.

⁶⁵ Interview held with Chief Adeola Akinloye, Age 70, Traditionalist, at Ewi-Isale Street, Okitipupa on the 14th of March 2024.

perception that Idepe and the broader IkaIe populace, despite their cultural and linguistic Yoruba heritage, trace their origins to Benin, categorising them as “Edoid” rather than “Yoruboid”.⁶⁶

The migration trends observed in Okitipupa were in accordance with the historical pattern of socio-economic advancement within the Benin kingdom. According to oral tradition,⁶⁷ during the reign of *Oba* Esigie, lasting forty-six years, a significant event occurred when two of his wives, one from the Edo community and the other from outside, bore children on the same day. Remarkably, the non-Edo wife gave birth to a son, followed shortly by the Edo wife, who also delivered a son. Intriguingly, the announcement of the Edo woman's childbirth took precedence, adhering to a tradition where the first announcement determined the heir-apparent. Thus, Orhogbua, whose birth was proclaimed first, ascended to the throne immediately after Esigie's reign, ruling from 1550 to 1578.⁶⁸ The individual denied his rightful claim to the Benin throne and was identified as Abodi Jabado. Historical accounts suggest that he was clandestinely concealed upon birth, prioritising the public acknowledgement of the child born to a non-Edo woman. This woman, purportedly not of Edo descent, was reportedly discreetly escorted out of Benin town along with her child. The term *Abodi* derives from the Ìkálè language, where *a bò ó* translates to “we hide it”, and *dì í* signifies “close it up” or “seal it up”. Hence, the name *Abodi* carries the connotation of “a hidden phenomenon”.⁶⁹

When Àbodi reached maturity, he was purportedly bestowed with the authority to establish his kingdom beyond the confines of Benin. Alongside this delegation of power, he received ceremonial regalia, including a crown symbolising his royal status, a wooden staff known as *Opá-idikòbà* representing his authority, as well as a sword (*adá*) and a flat sword (*abènrèn*), both emblematic of his sovereign rule. Departing from Benin, he made a stop at Àrògbò-Ilé before proceeding to Àkótógbò. History has it that the destruction of Àrògbò-Ilé by the Portuguese led to the founding of Àkótógbò.⁷⁰ Journeying further, Àbodi arrived at Òde-Ìrèlè, where he encountered river Pẹ̀pẹ̀n and settled along its banks, approximately two kilometres from the settlement of

⁶⁶ Ogen, O. 2012. ‘Exploring the Potential of Praise Poems for Historical Reconstruction among the Idepe-IkaIe in Southeastern Yorubaland’. *History in Africa*, Vol 12, 82.

⁶⁷ Interview with Chief Olaniyan Egburen, Age 60+, Traditional Political Leader, at Adeolu, Okitipupa on the 14th of March, 2024.

⁶⁸ Sheba, Eben. 2007. ‘The IkaIe (Yoruba, Nigeria) Migration Theories and Insignia’, *History in Africa*, Vol. 34, 462.

⁶⁹ Interview with High Chief I. Medunoye, Traditional Spiritual Leader, at Medunoye's Compound, Aja Quarters, Ode-Idepe on the 15th of March, 2024.

⁷⁰ Interview with High Chief I. Medunoye, Traditional Leader, at Medunoye's Compound, Aja Quarters

Olófun Jagbójú and his followers. Subsequently, Pághá Lúmùrè arrived in the vicinity and established residence in what is now known as Petu Quarters in Òde-Ìrèlè, having wed Lóbímitán, the daughter of Òrúnbèmékún. However, their marriage, which did not yield children, was short-lived. Ògìdìgbó Akínyókùn Àjànùwà later arrived and settled in the present-day Òbámóyègún Quarters in Òde-Ìrèlè, taking Lóbímitán, the forsaken wife of Lúmùrè, as his own. Lóbímitán was noted for her abundant hair and beauty.⁷¹

Lóbímitán bore two sons and a daughter with Akínyókùn Àjànùwà: Jagbójú, Oyèénúhì, and Ikúlámókùn, a daughter. Eventually, Ògìdìgbó Akínyókùn Àjànùwà ascended to the esteemed position of the first *Òbágbèrumè* of Igbódìgò. It was during this time that Àbòdì Jabadó contemplated relocating from Àkótógbò to Òde-Ìrèlè, accompanied by Ògúndùbujà Jègun. However, Jègun awaited the arrival of his family from Benin. Upon their arrival, he opted to join Àbòdì Jabadó in Òde-Ìrèlè. Initially unprepared to depart with Àbòdì Jabadó, Jègun's initial settlement was dubbed *Èdè tì pé* or *Èdèpé* (discord). Later, it was renamed *Ìdèpé* (Okitipupa).⁷²

In his research entitled “Exploring the Potential of Praise Poems for Historical Reconstruction among the Idepe-Ikale in Southeastern Yorubaland”, Olukoya Ogen presents a compelling argument countering the assertion that Okitipupa (Idepe) traces its origins to the Benin kingdom. Ogen supports his contention by analysing the Idepe lineage *Oriki*, revealing that the ancestral roots of the Idepe people can be traced back to Usen, an ancient Edo town.⁷³

*Omajegun a beyan meji, Onoja ke he e waro
 Ji irere ti le uba bi ne, n'ode usoyen (Usen)
 Omajegunyomi Abejoye
 Oge fifun ye se Oba Usen*⁷⁴

Meaning

We are the descendants of Jegun
 We were born at Ode-Usoyen (Usen)
 by the white-robed Jegunyomi
 the Oba of Usen

Ogen revealed that despite the widespread recognition of this *oriki* in Idepe, pinpointing the precise location of Usen proved elusive. Those consulted could only explain that Usen was an

⁷¹ Interview with High Chief I. Medunoye, Traditional Leader, at Medunoye's Compound, Aja Quarters

⁷² Interview with High Chief I. Medunoye, Traditional Leader, at Medunoye's Compound, Aja Quarters

⁷³ Ogen, O. 2012. ‘Exploring the Potential of Praise Poems for Historical Reconstruction among the Idepe-Ikale in Southeastern Yorubaland’. *History in Africa*, Vol 12, 84.

⁷⁴ Ogen, O. 2012. ‘Exploring the Potential of Praise Poems for Historical Reconstruction among the Idepe-Ikale in Southeastern Yorubaland’, 85.

ancient Edo village, where the Jegun of Idepe initially settled after departing from Benin before eventually establishing residence in the Ikale region. It was suggested that this village had ceased to exist.⁷⁵ However, further investigation conducted in Ikaleland and various parts of Edo State unveiled Usen's location within the Ovia South-East Local Government Area of Edo State. Positioned approximately seven kilometres from Okada and forty-four kilometres from Benin City, Usen is bordered by prominent Edo villages such as Iguomon, Ofunmwegbe, and Ogbede. Unlike these neighbouring Edo villages, where the Edo language and culture predominate, Usen stands out remarkably.⁷⁶ Here, the inhabitants not only converse in the Yoruba language but also fluently speak the pure Ikale dialect, a significant Yoruba dialect. Consequently, Usen emerges as an authentic Yoruba community nestled within the heart of the Edo cultural sphere, surrounded by numerous Edo settlements.⁷⁷

The similarities between Usen's socio-cultural and political structures and those of the mainstream Ikale people are highly notable. It has been observed that the conventional *ode* prefix, which is characteristic of the nomenclature of the capital of the Idepe kingdom, is also utilised in reference to Usen, denoted as Ode-Usen or Ode-Awure. Usen's historical narrative holds significant importance in Idepe's historical chronicles, serving as an ancient foundational settlement from which numerous progenitors of the Idepe nation dispersed.⁷⁸ From the foregoing, it is evident that the ancestral or lineage *oriki* of Idepe, coupled with the obvious connections established with the ancient town of Usen, particularly in terms of linguistic, religious, and cultural parallels, along with the historical trajectory of Usen, provide substantial support for the assertion that the earliest settlers in Idepe, namely the Jegun lineage, migrated from Usen rather than from Benin, as posited by certain official circles within Idepe. The lineage *oriki* of Idepe distinctly identifies the Jegunma quarters in Ode-Usen as the ancestral cradle of the Jegun people in Idepe.

Further analysis of Idepe's *oriki orisa* reinforces the cultural bond between Idepe and Usen. Notably, the reverence for the *Uwen* deity, integral to Usen's traditional religious practices, is

⁷⁵ Ogen, O. 2012. 'Exploring the Potential of Praise Poems for Historical Reconstruction among the Idepe-Ikale in Southeastern Yorubaland', 85.

⁷⁶ Ogen, O. 2012. 'Exploring the Potential of Praise Poems for Historical Reconstruction among the Idepe-Ikale in Southeastern Yorubaland', 86.

⁷⁷ Ogen, O. 2012. 'Exploring the Potential of Praise Poems for Historical Reconstruction among the Idepe-Ikale in Southeastern Yorubaland', 86.

⁷⁸ Ogen, O. 2012. 'Exploring the Potential of Praise Poems for Historical Reconstruction among the Idepe-Ikale in Southeastern Yorubaland', 86.

mirrored in Idepe rituals. The significance of *Uwen* in Ikale cosmology is acknowledged across virtually all Ikale kingdoms. The following excerpt from Idepe's *oriki* epitomises this cultural interconnectedness:

On'oja taka gbuwen le
J'eruku maku Uwen ara
Oluwen ruwen
*Ogbori ruwen egungun*⁷⁹

Meaning

A people that constructed a stand for *Uwen*
So that dust would not gather on *Uwen*
The priest of *Uwen* must carry *Uwen*
The uninitiated must carry *Uwen* masquerades

The Usen is the seat of the *Uwen* shrine, and its priests are known as *Alaghoró*, a name that is associated with traditional religious priests in Idepe.⁸⁰ It is evident from the preceding discussion that the historical significance of Idepe *oriki* implies a direct lineage from Usen. Furthermore, these two kingdoms are distinctly separated by various dialectal sub-groups within the Yoruba and Edo-speaking communities. Additionally, the shared Ikale dialect between Usen and Idepe, despite their geographical separation of over 250 kilometres, further supports the assertions made by historical linguists regarding the relationship between language and ethnic heritage.

The Traditional Political System of Okitipupa People

The traditional *Oba* with the title of *Jegun* of Idepe-Okitipupa is the supreme traditional ruler of Okitipupa, who has in theory the power to kill and save, but in practice never acted without the advice of his councillors/ high chiefs.⁸¹ Nonetheless, the chiefs within the community are under the jurisdiction of the *Oba*. Primarily, the *Oba* oversees all ceremonies and rituals associated with the passing of traditional figures within the town. This includes orchestrating funeral rites and commemorations. Additionally, the *Oba* holds a significant role in conducting propitiatory sacrifices, known as *etutu*, which are acts of appeasement mandated by the oracle or deity in response to crises such as epidemics, famine, or war. These rituals involve the entire community under the *Oba*'s authority, highlighting the indispensable role of the king in preserving the welfare

⁷⁹ Interview with Kunle Olatumile, Age, 65, Lecturer, at 13 Ope Oluwa Street, Ode-Idepe, on the 15th of March, 2024.

⁸⁰ Interview with Kunle Olatumile, Age, 65, Lecturer.

⁸¹ Interview with High Chief Olubayo Makinde, Age, 68, Traditional Leader, at Olorode Quatres, Ode-Idepe, on the 14th of March, 2024.

of the populace during challenging times.⁸² In the governance structure of his town, the *Oba* wields a distinct authority known as reserved or prerogative veto power over his chiefs. Additionally, the succession of an *Oba* follows a hereditary pattern typically guided by the oracle (*Ifa*) and overseen by kingmakers who adhere to specific traditions and rites before the instalment of a new monarch. *Jegun* held the esteemed title of *Oloja* and later ascended to become the *Oba* of Idepe-Okitipupa. Throughout history, the town has been governed by a line of eighteen rulers, whose reigns, though unrecorded in terms of years, are commemorated through their names: Ogundubuja, Monikenehin, Rabiye, Lagboja, Japinroye, Alaro, Akinjolakun, Moghojaye, Iretolu, Aderoloye, Fabiye, Adetuwo, Lajunje, Obamonire, Akinnubi, Akindele, Enikunemehin, and *Oba Adetoye Obatuga*.⁸³

Next to the king is the Council of Chiefs also known as High Chiefs. This comprises the *Ijoye*, *Ijamu* and *Omaja*.⁸⁴ Notably, the *Ijamu* holds significant sway and commands respect within the township, given his capacity to act on behalf of the *Oba* in governing the populace and overseeing communal affairs. Collaborating closely with the *Oba*, he engages in deliberations to address conflicting matters or foster the community's overall development. Moreover, he assumes responsibility for maintaining peace and harmony among the community and its residents, often serving as the *Oba*'s proxy in his absence. Dutifully attending to the town and its inhabitants in the *Oba*'s stead, he provides updates upon the monarch's return and offers pertinent intelligence, particularly concerning pressing issues such as security, healthcare, and economic affairs.⁸⁵

Ijoye refers to a group of chiefs appointed by the *Oba* to collaborate in the governance of the town. Their role encompasses providing support to the king, offering diverse perspectives, and contributing to collective decision-making processes. The appointment to this position is at the discretion of the king, with the expectation that the appointees will prioritise the welfare of the community and uphold its peaceful coexistence. Additionally, the *Ijoye* oversee certain cases within their jurisdiction, redirecting those beyond their scope to the *Oba*. Their significance is underscored by their participation in palace meetings and gatherings among the chiefs, reflecting

⁸² Interview with High Chief Olubayo Makinde, Age, 68, Traditional Leader, at Olorode Quatres.

⁸³ Interview held with High Chief Onifeso Onabule, Age 70+, Traditionalist, at Ewi-Isale Street, Okitipupa on the 13th of March, 2024.

⁸⁴ Interview held with High Chief Onifeso Onabule, Age 70+, Traditionalist.

⁸⁵ Interview held with High Chief Onifeso Onabule, Age 70+, Traditionalist, at Ewi-Isale Street, Okitipupa on the 13th of March, 2024.

their esteemed status within the town.⁸⁶

The subsequent role within the community hierarchy was that of the *Omaja*, entrusted to an individual well-versed in the community's traditions and cultural nuances. The responsibility of appointing a suitable candidate for this pivotal role rested with the king. The *Omaja's* primary duty is to safeguard the community's traditions and culture, with any transgression potentially resulting in severe repercussions. Additionally, the *Omaja* oversee the organisation of cultural festivals, ensuring all necessary arrangements are made. Moreover, the *Omaja* play vital roles in acknowledging and honouring attendees during such celebrations, while also emphasising the significance of preserving the community's cultural heritage and fostering peaceful coexistence among its members amidst economic and social endeavours.⁸⁷

Within the town's hierarchical structure, there existed a spiritual organisation deeply ingrained in its governance system. This institution held significant political sway alongside its religious functions. Serving as the de facto parliament, decisions made within this spiritual cult carried immense weight, binding both individuals and the town collectively. Beyond its legislative role, the cult also orchestrated spiritual rituals, either to strengthen the community or to avert perceived threats to its well-being. Central to its function was the interpretation of divine will, serving as intermediaries between the people and the gods. Representatives of this cult collaborated closely with the monarchy, offering counsel on matters ranging from constitutional affairs to cultural preservation and enforcement. Their primary duty lay in upholding traditional customs and ensuring adherence to sacred rites, thereby safeguarding the town's cultural integrity.⁸⁸

Within the cult, a designated individual fulfils the role of spokesperson, serving as the conduit for communication within the group. Membership within the cult is a prerequisite for assuming this position, ensuring that information conveyed through this channel remains accurate and free from misinterpretation, thereby upholding the standards of the community. Any deviation from this mandate would be regarded as a breach of discipline. While the spokesperson may

⁸⁶ Interview with Chief Matthew Asade, Age 60+, Traditionalist, at Olorode Quatres, Ode-Idepe, on the 14th of March, 2024.

⁸⁷ Interview with High Chief Olubayo Makinde, Age 68, Traditional Leader, at Olorode Quatres.

⁸⁸ Interview held with Mr Balo Lanre, Age 72, Elder Stateman, in Jokodo Street, Okitipupa on the 16th of March, 2024.

delegate tasks to subordinates, the ultimate responsibility for the accurate transmission of messages lies with them. They are accountable for any shortcomings in this regard. Additionally, the spokesperson is entrusted with specific duties such as performing rituals and ceremonies, including offerings to the deities and fostering the preservation of the town's cultural heritage.⁸⁹

The Traditional Economic System of Okitipupa People

Okitipupa's emergence as a commercial centre dates back to the fifteenth century. Several factors contributed to its early concentration of human capital. Firstly, the town was connected by footpaths not only to Ondo and other Yoruba settlements but also to Benin. Secondly, its accessibility via creeks facilitated transportation by boat, attracting interest groups from the western coast, including those from Bendel, Lagos, and Rivers States of Nigeria. Thirdly, Okitipupa enjoyed relative peace conducive to economic and developmental activities, unlike the political and military instability prevalent in hinterland states during that era. Lastly, the region boasted abundant natural resources such as land, forests, and water, offering promising prospects for prosperous living.⁹⁰

These elements synergised to facilitate additional potential assets, thereby diversifying the local trajectory and avenues for advancement. The expansion of the communication network encompassed a network of roads and waterways, with Okitipupa emerging as the pivotal junction connecting land and sea routes.⁹¹ Consequently, Okitipupa flourished into a commercial hub and served as an economic intermediary, facilitating trade transactions that prominently featured goods such as fish, salt, and gin, alongside palm oil, agricultural produce, garri, starch, and meat sourced from both riverine communities and hinterland producers.⁹² The establishment of this initial trading hub acted as a catalyst for various occupations, including fishing, as well as the cultivation and processing of palm and agricultural products.

The economic structure of Okitipupa revolves predominantly around agriculture, forming the cornerstone of their traditional livelihood. The community primarily consists of agrarian individuals, deeply rooted in farming practices as their main source of sustenance. They have

⁸⁹ Interview held with Mr Balo Lanre, Age 72, Elder Stateman.

⁹⁰ Otite, O. 1988. 'Sources of Urban Concentration in the Nigerian Countryside'. *African Studies Review*, 31(3), 17–27.

⁹¹ Otite, O. 1988. 'Sources of Urban Concentration in the Nigerian Countryside', 17–27.

⁹² Otite, O. 1988. 'Sources of Urban Concentration in the Nigerian Countryside', 17–27.

cultivated a distinctive approach, focusing on specific crops such as cassava, plantain, and palm oil, among others. Within this agricultural framework, men typically assume the primary role, engaging in the bulk of the labour-intensive tasks. However, women and children also contribute, albeit with different responsibilities on the farm. To supplement their workforce, farmers often employ household labourers.⁹³ Consequently, the practice of polygamy is not uncommon, as having multiple wives and children ensures sufficient hands for farm work.

The rainy season holds significant importance for farmers, heralding the optimal conditions for planting and cultivation. Anticipation builds among them as they prepare to commence their farming activities, anticipating the opportunity to generate income. Meanwhile, the dry season is utilised for land preparation, and clearing fields in readiness for the forthcoming rainy season. This cyclical rhythm underscores the seasonal nature of their agricultural pursuits.⁹⁴ While certain farmers utilised the dry season for various pursuits such as hunting, fishing, and craftwork, agriculture remained the predominant occupation among the populace. Initially centred around subsistence farming, the community eventually integrated cash crops into their agricultural practices, including cassava, maize, cocoa, oil palm, plantain, and banana cultivation. Notably, Okitipupa fostered both internal and external trade connections. The town boasted three primary markets: *Oja* Okitipupa, renowned for its five-day schedule and widespread popularity, alongside *Oja* Obulumore and *Oja* Ojebotako, which operated daily and attracted patrons from neighbouring and distant locales. These markets played a vital role in fulfilling the economic needs of many individuals and the broader community. Drawing visitors from various distances, these bustling hubs facilitated the exchange of diverse commodities, including yam, kolanuts, cassava, plantain, cocoa, banana, palm oil, vegetables, and *marugbo* leaves, among others.⁹⁵

Palm oil production was a major occupation of the people in Okitipupa. The occupation could be said as one that had been in existence for a very long time. It was as old as the town itself. In the early stage, the occupation was mainly dominated by women. They were fully involved in the processing of palm oil seeds and often took risks as part of the inevitable part of the business. The palm oil seeds were mostly collected from the farmers who had planted the trees to produce

⁹³ Interview held with Mr Obeda Samuel, Age 70, Palm Oil Extractor, at Alanse Street, Okitipupa on the 17th of March, 2024.

⁹⁴ Interview held with Mr Obeda Samuel, Age 70, Palm Oil Extractor.

⁹⁵ Interview held with Mrs Olotu Esther, Age 49+, Trader, at Ewi-Oke Street, Okitipupa on the 14th of March, 2024

the palm oil. The business eventually became lucrative as both men and women became involved in palm oil extraction in Okitipupa. The method of trading between the farmers and the traders was mainly by barter rather than by money. The process involved the number of palm trees available on the farm. The farmers would count the number of palm trees on their farm and demand a keg of oil for twenty palm trees. He would continue in the same manner if the trees were more than twenty but, a keg of palm oil was the return usually given to the farmers who had allowed his palm foids to be harvested by those who would process the same oil.⁹⁶

Yam, serving as a fundamental dietary component, holds significant cultural and agricultural importance among the inhabitants of Okitipupa. Indigenous farmers traditionally prioritise yam cultivation on their lands, whether engaged in subsistence or commercial farming practices. Alongside yam, other essential crops like cocoyam also find a place in their agricultural repertoire. The introduction of cassava in the mid-fifteenth century marked a significant shift in agricultural practices, as it swiftly transitioned into a staple crop. This introduction catalysed a transformation in farming strategies, with many farmers diversifying into commercial cultivation of cassava and other cash crops. This expansion not only facilitated increased production for both sustenance and commercial ventures but also heralded a broader economic dimension to their agricultural activities.⁹⁷

The inhabitants of Okitipupa also rely on fishing and salt production, highlighting their strong dependence on water and a profound connection to aquatic elements. The women are mostly fish sellers, and they sell varieties of fish like Croacker, Tilapia, *Oluworo*, *Seke*, *Alaran*, *Yanyan* (shark), *Pete*, *Ileba*, *Akikoro*, *Doje*, *Obira*, *Faranfaran*, *Ede*, *Octopus*, *Shaworo*, etc. The Okitipupa people, along with their Ikale kinsmen, engage in maritime activities spanning high seas and shallow waters. Notably, the Okitipupa community is involved in the timber trade. Utilising waterways, they transport timber logs from Ikale and Ilaje settlements through the lagoon route to various sawmills situated along the waterfronts of Ebute-Metta, Epe in Lagos State, and Sapele in Delta State.⁹⁸ Additionally, the Okitipupa people partake in fishing-related activities, crafting fish traps (*Igere*) from raffia palms found abundantly in Ugboland. Their activities extend to the production and repair of fishing nets.

⁹⁶ Interview held with Mr. Stephen Dapo, Age 70, Farmer, at Halo Street, Okitipupa on the 17th of March, 2024

⁹⁷ Interview held with Mrs Olotu Esther, Age 49+, trader, at Ewi-Oke Street, Okitipupa on the 14th of March, 2024

⁹⁸ Interview held with Mrs Ogunmehin Toyin , 47yrs, Trader, at Okitipupa Market on 17th of March, 2024.

Hunting was also indigenous to the people. This occupation was mostly practised during the dry season. However, most farmers usually turned to hunting after the end of the rainy season, as their part-time occupation. Hunting was done by farmers to complement farming and not as their major occupation. The dry season also helped the farmers to have enough time for hunting and was considered perfect for the occupation because of the following reasons: first, the leaves would have gone dry/withered which would improve the sight of the hunters in the forest, secondly, most animals did run thirsty during the dry season and were mostly forced to come out to drink water at the bank of the river within the forest; this often made it easier for the hunters to kill them, Some of the animals hunted included: rodents, snakes, rabbits, antelopes, deer, buffalo, hyena, alligator, to mention but few.⁹⁹ These animals were either sold to food vendors or consumed. Although hunting was mostly done by farmers to complement farming, some professional hunters took hunting as their major occupation. These could stay in the forest for one or two days in search of game; they also built huts where they relaxed and refreshed themselves when they were tired. Moreover, most hunters were usually armed with supernatural powers they used to protect themselves from dangerous animals or spiritual attacks during hunting, some of their traditional tools included: knives, flint-lock guns, daggers, headlights, cap lock guns, and others.¹⁰⁰

The Traditional Socio-Cultural Systems of the People of Okitipupa

The people of Okitipupa shared common cultural traits with other Yoruba traditional societies found in the Southwestern region of Nigeria. Before modernisation and the introduction of Islam and Christianity to Okitipupa, the people had their own unique and indigenous means of dressing that defined their culture and tradition. Traditional clothes of various types and shades were worn by the people. Both male and female had their type of traditional attire that they wore. It was taboo for a man to wear a woman's dress and vice versa. The people of Ikale who were the dominant sub-group of Yoruba in Okitipupa had their women wearing a shirt and a wrapper, while the men wore a wrapper and a *buba* top and a hat with a feather affixed to one portion of the hat. However, except for special occasions, the majority of the people had adopted the traditional Yoruba manners of dressing with their men wearing clothes such as; *buba* and *sokoto*, *agbada*, *fila*, among others and their women with *buba* and *iro*, *iborun*, *ipele*, and *gele*. They also had unique traditional beads that they wore to showcase their cultural uniqueness and value. In

⁹⁹ Interview held with Mr. Odunwo Dayo, Age 61, Trader, at Ojan Street, Okitipupa, on the 16th of March, 2024

¹⁰⁰ Interview held with Mr. Stephen Dapo, Age 70, Farmer, at Halo Street, Okitipupa on the 17th of March, 2024

addition, the men barbed and shaved their hair while the women, who considered their hair as pride, plait it. Some of their hair style included; *Kolere, ipako-elede, suku, Kojusoko, Akagogo, etc.*¹⁰¹

The people of Okitipupa also had their unique food such as; *pupuru* and *obe marugbo* which were common to them. The *pupuru* was prepared from cassava and made in a manner akin to that of *fufu*. As for *obe marugbo*, it was made up of *marugbo* leaves and other greens like *efirin, akintola* or *iseleru*. The dried leaves were what would give the soup its dark green-to-black colouring. The soup was said to be medicinal due to the vegetables in its preparation. It was best served with *pupuru*. However, they also had some Yoruba diets such as; *Fufu, Eba, Ewedu, Efo-riro, and Iyan*, to mention but a few.¹⁰²

In the context of family dynamics, the family unit held significant influence over social interactions within Okitipupa. Typically structured around polygamous arrangements involving husbands, wives, and children, families aimed to cultivate support networks, particularly in agricultural endeavours, rather than relying on external labour. Within each family, an extended family network is formed, overseen by a figurehead known as the *Olori-Ebi* or *Olori-Agbole*, selected based on their experience and wisdom within the family, rather than lineage. This leadership role, often assumed by the eldest member, served to foster cohesion and resolve internal disputes, including matters related to land, property ownership, and inheritance, among other familial affairs.¹⁰³

The people of Okitipupa also strongly believe in *Olodumare* or *Olorun*, who is the supreme God, who owns heaven and earth. Before the introduction of Christianity and Islam, the people of Okitipupa believed that there was only one God. He had no second in command other than those He had chosen as His messengers who were deities (*Orisa*). They sometimes call Him the Omnipotent and Omniscience God. However, the worship of nature and functional gods was common in Okitipupa. The inhabitants worshipped deities, who they believed, to be the messengers of God and even after the introduction of Christianity and Islam, these gods/deities remained very important and were celebrated in high esteem. They celebrated these gods annually

¹⁰¹ Interview with Mrs Olunrunfemi Felicia , Age 56, Trader, at Okitipupa Market on 17th March, 2024.

¹⁰² Interview with Mrs Olunrunfemi Felicia , Age 56, Trader, at Okitipupa Market on 17th of March, 2024.

¹⁰³ Interview held with Chief Akanni Agbede, Age 70, Traditionalist, at Alo Street, Okitipupa on the 17th of March, 2024.

to show their appreciation and humbly request protection/guardians and most importantly for a peaceful society. Some of these traditional festivals were; *Ogun* (god of iron), *Oro*, *Ere* (Masquerades), *Iwo*, etc.¹⁰⁴

***Ogun* Festival**

Ogun festival was usually celebrated by indigenes of Okitipupa in large numbers. The festivals had no specific month of celebration but mostly followed an instruction/message by the diviners who often instructed those that were connected to the deity vis-à-vis their professions to prepare for the festival but, it must be celebrated at least once every year. According to Yoruba mythology, the *Ogun* festival commemorated the god of iron, a mythical warrior who was the first god to descend from earth since he possessed the tool, an iron cutlass that could clear the earth's vegetation therefore, clearing way for other deities.¹⁰⁵ In Okitipupa hunters, farmers and all other professions that make use of iron objects would be expected to appease the god of iron. It was generally believed that the deity possessed supernatural power over all the things made of iron. It should be noted that *Ogun* could be appeased anywhere apart from the central shrine of the town. Generally, they believed that anything related to iron objects had strong ties with the deity. The efficacy of this deity was demonstrated based on the fact that it was and still is used to apprehend thieves in the community; this was mostly done by asking the suspect to swear in front of the deity (*Ogun*) after which the deity would give his judgment within the next seven days. The *Ogun* festival is traditionally marked by ceremonial offerings, including sacrifices of snails, tortoises, and dogs. Participants adorn themselves with a mixture of white and blue powder on their faces, while vibrant masquerades are a common sight, moving through the streets in dance. Musical accompaniment is provided by three primary types of drums: the *Igba* drum, the *Abimbolu* drum, and the *Agogo* (gong).¹⁰⁶

***Oro* Festival**

This was and still is being celebrated at night in Okitipupa. The *Oro* was often used to send out strange forces or evil spirits from the town. According to tradition, women were not permitted

¹⁰⁴ Interview held with Chief Akanni Agbede, Age 70, Traditionalist.

¹⁰⁵ Interview held with Chief Akanni Agbede, Age 70, Traditionalist.

¹⁰⁶ Interview held with Chief Akanni Agbede, Age 70, Traditionalist, at Alo Street, Okitipupa on the 17th of March 2024.

to come out during the *Oro* procession at night. However, in some cases, *Oro* could come out in broad daylight, depending on the nature of the condition for its appeasement/celebration. The *Oro* could also be used to drive out a man or woman who had been identified as a witch or stranger who behaved contrary to the norms of the land. In addition to this, if people suspected that there were strange spirits or epidemics in the town, *Oro* might be brought out of its grove to roar around the town to ward off or clear the evil spirit. It was believed that the roaring and ear-piercing noise of the *Oro* would often scare evil spirits and drive them away from the community. As a traditional town, the use of *Oro* was very important to the people of Okitipupa to chase evil forces and ward off any bad omen from the land. They worshipped and celebrated the *Oro* festival annually and this is the habit to date. There was no specific month for the celebration of *Oro* as the festival could be announced at any given time but, mostly done between July and August every year.¹⁰⁷

***Ere* Festival**

This is an annual festival that is usually celebrated in June by the *Igodan Lisa* people of Okitipupa. *Odun Ere* as it was usually called had been a long-standing tradition that had been passed down from one generation to another. The festival was at its core a festival of feast. *Ere* itself is a meal of meshed yam, palm oil and fish. Named after this meal, the festival, with its communal sharing and eating of food, reflected the communitarian philosophy in the town. In addition, the *Ere* festival is ranked as one of the most esteemed festivals which on one hand, exposed the spiritual psyche of the people, and on the other hand, a tool kit that constantly fostered solidarity among the Ikale people in the celebration of their customs and traditions.¹⁰⁸ As partly sacred festivals, the *Ere* lent credence to the African belief in the tree supernatural stage as divinely interrelated in the rituals, masquerading and idolisation of elders. The festival was replete with entertainment, rich aesthetic qualities as well as a plethora of diverse performative and theatrical experiences which brought about harmony and highlighted the collective culture of the people. The performers and mode of performance took different faces during the festival. For instance, a three insect called the “*Ahoro*” would take the stage by invoking masquerades from the river. The leader of the sect would perform an invocation while the other two would respond in a call-and-response pattern. Further, the masquerades known as “*baralokun*” and “*Arolokun*” would

¹⁰⁷ Interview held with Chief Akanni Agbede, Age 70, Traditionalist.

¹⁰⁸ Interview held with Chief. Osifeso Onabule, Age 70, Traditionalist, at Ewi Oke Street, Okitipupa, on the 15th of March, 2024.

function as invisible audiences since the invocation from the “*Ahoro*” sect was directed at them. After a series of invocations, the masquerade would surface from their domain.¹⁰⁹

Other important aspects of the festival were the women who helped to charge the masquerades with their laudatory chants. With their creativity, use of memory, spontaneity and ingenuity, they helped to work the masquerades up into a frenzy. The masquerades would consequently intensify and heighten their dances. Keeping the audience and spectators at the edge of their seats.¹¹⁰

***Iwo* Festival**

The *Iwo* festival, deeply entrenched within the cultural heritage of Okitipupa, has endured the passage of time, its origins shrouded in antiquity. Revered as an ancient tradition, it served as a means for the community to honour and seek favour from the deities and spirits associated with the rivers. Embraced by all, it was believed that during the festival, these divine entities would grace the town with their presence. Typically observed during July and August, its timing was intricately linked to the lunar cycle, determined by the discernment of the *Logengbas*, the revered custodians of the festival. Initiated with the sighting of the moon, usually in late June or early July, preparations commenced promptly, often marked by gatherings of the *Logengba* on designated market days, engaging in divination rituals known as *Mobikale* to ascertain the precise date of the festival. The duration of the festivities could span nine, eighteen, or twenty-seven days, dictated by the insights garnered through these sacred practices.¹¹¹

About three days before the festival, the *Logengbas* would go to *Igbo-Oro* to prepare the ground for the *Oluweri* and also clear and clean up the road, predominantly called *Onakogun*, i.e. the warrior’s road. On the third day after the festival began, the *Logengba* would move around the road with healing water (*Ero*). Men were required to dip their hands in it to rub their bodies while it would be sprinkled on women’s bodies. Activities would begin in earnest in the early hours of the day with the wailing of the *Oluweri*. This was usually between the hours of 4:30 am and 5 am. This set of *Oluweri* was called *Afigbana*, literally meaning the early morning sweepers. The belief was that this type of *Oluweri* would prepare the ground for the remaining ones on the way, after a

¹⁰⁹ Interview held with Chief. Osifeso Onabule, Age 70, Traditionalist.

¹¹⁰ Interview held with Chief. Osifeso Onabule, Age 70, Traditionalist.

¹¹¹ Interview held with Chief. Osifeso Onabule, Age 70, Traditionalist, at Ewi Oke Street, Okitipupa, on the 15th of March, 2024.

couple of hours, another set of *Oluwari* would come in large numbers between the hours of 10:30 am and 2:30 pm to wail.¹¹² According to tradition, the first set would find their way to the centre of the town where the *Oba*, High chiefs and the *Logengba* would meet them (although not face to face) and to appease and pray for the progress of the town. Thereafter, the whole town would be agog with the cries of *Oluwari*. By 6:30 pm, another set of these *Oluwari* would come out to cry and continue to pray for the whole town and they would also identify themselves one after the other. Women and non-indigenes would stay indoors throughout the period *Oluwari* would be out. The directive required all the children, women and non-indigenes to stay indoors while the *Oluwari* would move around the town accompanied by the palace boys with drumming, dancing and singing. The most common foods during this festival are; yam and okra or *apan* soup, boiled groundnut and walnut. The festival usually lasted for two (2 days) and the *Oluwari* would be expected to move around the town for the two days.¹¹³

¹¹² Interview held with Chief. Osifeso Onabule, Age 70, Traditionalist.

¹¹³ Interview held with Chief. Osifeso Onabule, Age 70, Traditionalist, at Ewi Oke Street, Okitipupa, on the 15th of March, 2024.

CHAPTER THREE

TRADITIONAL CONFLICT RESOLUTION MECHANISMS IN OKITIPUPA TOWN

Conflict is an inherent aspect of both human and non-human existence. It can emerge in any society, manifesting at various levels—from individual interactions to group, community, and even national disputes. This is equally true in traditional African societies, where conflicts arise when opposing interests or actions clash. In many cases, these conflicts may take on a zero-sum nature, with one party's gain being another's loss. However, through resolution, transformation, or management, conflicts can also lead to mutually beneficial outcomes.¹¹⁴ Conflicts in Africa are characterised as often being superficially addressed or dismissed as disorganised, receiving little more than generalised sympathy or humanitarian attention, rather than being subjected to thorough political analysis. Colonial powers, through their divide-and-rule strategies, ensured the passivity of various ethnic groups, effectively protecting themselves from the threat of rebellion.¹¹⁵

Just as peace is a natural phenomenon, so too is conflict, though African perspectives on conflict often differ from global interpretations. Traditionally, conflict in African societies is viewed as a struggle for values, power, and resources, with each party striving to neutralise or overcome their opponents.¹¹⁶ In pre-colonial African societies, despite their reliance on oral traditions and the absence of formal writing systems, had well-organised political, social, and economic structures. These communities upheld systems of social control, principles of law, and a deep-rooted commitment to justice and equity. Their judicial frameworks included methods of conflict resolution through adjudication, arbitration, and mediation, even though these processes were not formally recorded in written form.¹¹⁷

It is from this foregoing that this chapter examined the root causes, nature, and traditional forms of social and cultural conflicts in Okitipupa. It also explores the major traditional institutions and actors responsible for conflict resolution and the indigenous approaches used to address disputes within the town.

¹¹⁴ Otite, O. and Albert, I.O. 2001. *Community Conflicts in Nigeria. Management, Resolution and transformation*. Ibadan, Nigeria: Spectrum Books Limited, 12.

¹¹⁵ Widnga, W. 2013. "Post- Colonial Conflict in Africa: A Study of Richard Ali's City of Memories", *International Journal of Arts and Humanities*, Vol.2 (4), S/No.8, 310.

¹¹⁶ Onigu, Otitie and Albert, I.O. 2001. *Community Conflicts in Nigeria. Management, Resolution and transformation*. 12.

¹¹⁷ Odusote, S.A. 1984. "Extra-Judicial Processes in Traditional Africa: A Case Study of Yorubaland". M.A Dissertation, University of Ibadan.

Causes and Patterns of Conflicts in Okitipupa

Throughout human history, one of the key challenges has been the inevitability of conflict arising from social interactions and relationships. In Okitipupa town, disputes have often stemmed from various social factors and conditions that benefit one group while disadvantaging another. It is important to note that traditional conflicts in Okitipupa occurred both on a bilateral level, involving two parties and on a multilateral level, involving multiple parties.

The causes and nature of these conflicts typically revolved around interactions between different social groups and categories, disputes over ownership and access to natural resources, as well as interpersonal and intergroup disagreements, among other factors.

Boundary and Land Disputes

One major source of conflict in Okitipupa town involved disputes over boundaries and land ownership. In Okitipupa, as in many other societies land was regarded as a highly valuable asset, essential for both economic stability and social status. The importance of land is particularly underscored by the role of cash crop farming in the local economy, which made the quest to control and acquire land even more intense. As farmers sought to expand their holdings and secure their livelihoods, tensions frequently arose, leading to disputes that could escalate into significant conflicts.¹¹⁸

Boundary disputes, commonly referred to in the local dialect as *Ijan*, were especially prevalent among farmers in the villages surrounding Okitipupa.¹¹⁹ These conflicts often stemmed from unclear or poorly defined property lines, resulting in neighbours contesting the extent of their land. Farmers would frequently argue over where one property ended and another began, leading to disputes that could disrupt not only agricultural activities but also community relations. Such conflicts could escalate quickly, particularly when coupled with the emotional stakes associated with land, as it represented not just a resource but also a family's legacy and future.

Another type of boundary dispute that emerged was related to the intricate issue of indigeneity.¹²⁰ The local inhabitants believed that land was inherited from their ancestors, which led them to impose fees on non-indigenous individuals and to take punitive measures against those

¹¹⁸ Interview held with Mr Timothy Liyansan Ajaka, Age 62, Land Agent, at Agbabu Street, Okitipupa on the 15th of July, 2024.

¹¹⁹ Interview held with Mr Timothy Liyansan Ajaka, Age 62, Land Agent

¹²⁰ Interview held with Mr Timothy Liyansan Ajaka, Age 62, Land Agent

who did not adhere to their requirements.¹²¹ This created tensions between the indigenous population and non-indigenous residents in Okitipupa.

On the other hand, conflicts regarding land ownership were a prevalent issue within Okitipupa, often arising when multiple parties laid claim to the same piece of property. In these cases, individuals or families would present conflicting documents or oral histories to substantiate their claims of ownership.¹²² Additionally, intra-family disputes, particularly in polygynous households, further fueled these land-related conflicts. The allocation of inheritance (referred to as *Ogun Pinpin*) and instances of deceit (known as *Iyanje*) have led to numerous conflicts both within families and among different groups in the Okitipupa community. Tensions often escalated during inheritance disputes following the death of a family head, especially when inheritors were dissatisfied with the size or location of the land they received.¹²³ After the head of the household had passed away, new beneficiaries frequently faced significant demands related to royalty payments for land used for farming. Disagreements over how these royalties should be distributed also commonly lead to conflicts among family members.¹²⁴

In the same light, conflicts frequently arose when a polygamous man did not clearly outline the distribution of his assets before his death. Even in situations where a will was established and properties were allocated according to the specified terms, disagreements could still surface if one party felt wronged or inadequately treated in the implementation of the will or any agreements made between individuals or groups. Such feelings of unfairness often bred resentment and led to prolonged disputes.¹²⁵ The competing interests of the parties involved tended to intensify these conflicts, resulting in bitter and enduring rivalries that fractured communities. These disputes often reflected more profound social dynamics, revealing the complexities of land tenure systems, which are frequently intertwined with issues of lineage, inheritance, and historical claims.

Land disputes—whether concerning boundaries or ownership—were significant contributors to conflict in Okitipupa. These issues not only affected agricultural productivity and community relations but also highlighted the intricate connections between land, identity, and social structure in the town.

¹²¹ Interview held with Mr Timothy Liyansan Ajaka, Age 62, Land Agent

¹²² Interview held with Mr Samuel Liyansan-Ajaka, Age 67, Retired Surveyor, at Agbabu Street, Okitipupa on the 15th of July, 2024.

¹²³ Interview held with Mr Samuel Liyansan-Ajaka, Age 67, Retired Surveyor

¹²⁴ Interview held with Mr Samuel Liyansan-Ajaka, Age 67, Retired Surveyor

¹²⁵ Interview held with Mr Samuel Liyansan-Ajaka, Age 67, Retired Surveyor

Resource-Based Conflicts

The issue of resource control was also a significant cause of conflict in Okitipupa. Disputes frequently arose over the ownership and use of resources among various stakeholders in Okitipupa. One major conflict identified was between Okitipupa Oil Palm Plc (OOP PLC) and the local community.¹²⁶ Adelokiki Patrick, coordinator of the Ikafe Supreme Civil Rights Council (ISCRC), accused the company of exploiting the communities by operating on their land without adequate compensation. According to him, despite an agreement made in 1954 between the company and the communities, OOP PLC had failed to honour its obligations. Meanwhile, the company was reportedly generating billions of naira in revenue from the land. The agreement, which covered approximately 50,000 hectares, was originally intended for oil palm cultivation.¹²⁷

Patrick stated that records obtained by his group showed that on March 31, 1954, an agreement was signed at the provincial office of the Native Authority of Okitipupa. Under this agreement, their forefathers had granted a large expanse of land—about 50,000 hectares—for the establishment of oil palm plantations. The agreement, made between the Western Region Government and the local communities, was structured as a lease and joint venture partnership. At the time, the cost of cultivation was estimated at 45 pounds per acre. The government had agreed to pay ten years' rent in advance to help affected farmers relocate. Additionally, after the initial ten years, further use of the land was to be converted into equity, ensuring that the community's descendants would benefit from employment opportunities and the company's Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) initiatives.¹²⁸

However, Patrick lamented that these commitments had not been fulfilled. He asserted that, despite the partnership structure, the company had failed to uphold its responsibilities to the community, effectively denying them the benefits promised in the original agreement.

Chieftaincy and Seniority Disputes

The desire for power and influence was a significant driver of conflict in Okitipupa. A prime example of this is the frequent occurrence of chieftaincy disputes, known as *Oye jije*, which typically arose when a chieftaincy position became vacant, either due to the death or the removal of the previous holder. The pressing need to fill the vacancy with a new chief often sparked

¹²⁶ Interview held with Mr Adelokiki Patrick, Age 40+, Civil Rights Activist, at Okitipupa on the 16th of July, 2024.

¹²⁷ Interview held with Mr Adelokiki Patrick, Age 40+, Civil Rights Activist

¹²⁸ Interview held with Mr Adelokiki Patrick, Age 40+, Civil Rights Activist

competition among various candidates who sought to claim the title. This competition was not always peaceful, as individuals or groups vying for the position engaged in a struggle for control, leading to conflicts that could deeply affect the town.¹²⁹

One of the main sources of tension during this process was the issue of seniority, or *Egin*, which became particularly contentious when a younger or less prominent individual was put forward as a candidate.¹³⁰ In such cases, older, wealthier, or more influential aspirants might feel slighted by the nomination and may organise opposition to the candidate, often leveraging their social and financial standing to sway public opinion against the nominee. These actions often intensified the conflict, as those with greater resources and influence sought to undermine their rivals. This competition frequently led to factions forming within the community, further escalating tensions.¹³¹

Despite these struggles, it is important to note that Okitipupa's tradition places a strong emphasis on the resolution of chieftaincy conflicts following the selection of a new chief. While the period leading up to the selection was often marked by heated competition and rivalry, once the inauguration ceremony had taken place, the various aspirants usually accepted the outcome and moved on. This acceptance is grounded in the cultural values of fate and respect for the office of the chief, which help ensure that conflicts do not persist indefinitely.¹³²

The principle of seniority, however, is not limited to chieftaincy matters alone. It also played a crucial role in everyday social relations within families and the broader community. Within families, issues of seniority often arose among siblings, with elder siblings typically holding more authority or influence. In the wider community, this hierarchy manifests among peers and various social groups, where age and social status dictate respect and leadership.¹³³ This deeply ingrained respect for seniority underscores the broader cultural dynamics in Okitipupa, where conflicts related to power and influence are often framed within the context of age, wealth, and societal standing.

Neglect of Social Responsibility

¹²⁹ Interview held with High Chief Omotola Emaye, Age 60+, *Arogun* of Idepe Okitipupa, at Okitipupa on the 16th of July, 2024.

¹³⁰ Interview held with High Chief Omotola Emaye, Age 60+, *Arogun* of Idepe Okitipupa

¹³¹ Interview held with High Chief Omotola Emaye, Age 60+, *Arogun* of Idepe Okitipupa

¹³² Interview held with High Chief Omotola Emaye, Age 60+, *Arogun* of Idepe Okitipupa

¹³³ Interview held with High Chief Omotola Emaye, Age 60+, *Arogun* of Idepe Okitipupa

The failure to fulfil social responsibilities was a critical driver of conflict in pre-colonial Okitipupa and its surrounding areas. When civil authorities, who were the traditional chiefs, neglected their duties, such as ensuring effective governance, equitable distribution of resources, and maintaining law and order, it created a sense of lawlessness and frustration within the community. This dereliction of duty weakens the social fabric, leaving the people without the necessary support or representation, and ultimately leading to feelings of marginalisation. In such situations, community members often resorted to public demonstrations and protests as a way to express their dissatisfaction and demand accountability from the traditional leaders. These protests could quickly escalate if the grievances were not addressed, turning peaceful demonstrations into violent confrontations.¹³⁴ A notable historical example occurred in the Ondo Kingdom, where, according to oral testimonies, women organised a protest by publicly stripping nude to express their outrage against the policy requiring them to pay the *owo ori* (head tax).¹³⁵ This dramatic act of defiance underscored the depth of their frustration and highlighted the severity of neglect by the authorities.

The neglect of social responsibilities not only stirred discontent but also fostered an environment ripe for conflict. In Okitipupa, as in other parts of Ondo State, this failure to address the people's needs and concerns has repeatedly led to tension. When these tensions were not properly managed or mitigated, they spiralled into larger conflicts that disrupted the peace and stability of the region.¹³⁶

Interpersonal and Intra-Communal Conflicts

Conflict in Okitipupa often emerged from the collapse of diplomatic relations among individuals and within different social groups, leading to both interpersonal and intra-communal disputes. From 2012-2014, most conflicts in Okitipupa mainly had to do with interpersonal, criminal, and domestic violence. There was one incident in October 2014, when several people were shot by security forces for not complying during the monthly environmental sanitation exercise and resisting arrest.¹³⁷ The sources of conflict in Okitipupa, while not limited to these factors, primarily stem from these fundamental social dynamics. Understanding these causes

¹³⁴ Interview held with Chief Mrs Osutade Kehinde, Age 50+, Traditional Political Leader, at Okesare, Okitipupa on the 16th of July, 2024.

¹³⁵ Interview held with Chief Mrs Osutade Kehinde, Age 50+, Traditional Political Leader

¹³⁶ Interview held with Chief Mrs Osutade Kehinde, Age 50+, Traditional Political Leader

¹³⁷ Nigeria Conflict Bulletin: Ondo State: <https://fundforpeace.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/08/conflictbulletin-ondo-1508.pdf> Accessed on 16th July 2024.

provides valuable insights into the nature of conflict in Okitipupa and other cultural communities surrounding it. Traditional conflicts in Okitipupa were deeply rooted in their social structure, and they were not triggered by a single cause. Instead, they arose from various factors, as discussed above. Moreover, these conflicts manifested in both violent and non-violent forms. Violent conflicts involved public disturbances, open confrontations, and the use of weapons such as cutlasses (*Ada*), axes (*Dun*), knives (*Obe*), and Dane guns (*Shakabula*). In contrast, non-violent conflicts were characterised by malice, deep-seated resentment, and antagonistic behaviours.¹³⁸

Infidelity and Disputes over Paternity

One of the sources of conflict among the people of Okitipupa was related to issues of infidelity and disputes over the paternity of children.¹³⁹ This arose when either the husband or wife engaged in an extramarital affair. Such situations were not only disruptive within the family but also had wider social implications. As one respondent noted, the gravest offence to an Okitipupa man is the violation of his marital bond by another man. The respondent further explained that instances of infidelity, locally referred to as “*Ale yin yan*”, have escalated to violent confrontations, some of which have tragically resulted in loss of life.¹⁴⁰

A closely related issue to infidelity in Okitipupa was the conflict over the paternity of a child, where more than one man claims to be the father. Such situations may hint at a cultural undercurrent of infidelity within the town. When disputes of this nature arise, two guiding principles typically come into play.¹⁴¹ The first principle was rooted in tradition and is encapsulated in a well-known Ondo proverb:

Ini o ni gobi, o ni eso

Meaning

The owner of the wife owns the child

In Okitipupa, the cultural norm dictates that the traditional or legal husband is considered the father of the child, regardless of any external relationships the wife may have. The second perspective is more instinctive, relying on the woman's knowledge. It was assumed that the mother was best positioned to identify the true father of her child. In such cases, the determination of the

¹³⁸ Interview held with Chief Mrs Osutade Kehinde, Age 50+, Traditional Political Leader

¹³⁹ Interview held with Chief Adeola Akinloye, Age 70, Traditionalist, at Ewi-Isale Street, Okitipupa on the 14th of March, 2024.

¹⁴⁰ Interview held with Chief Adeola Akinloye, Age 70, Traditionalist.

¹⁴¹ Interview held with Chief Adeola Akinloye, Age 70, Traditionalist.

child's paternity was based on the woman's decision.¹⁴² However, issues of infidelity and disputes over child paternity have sparked violent conflicts within the Okitipupa community.

Traditional Institutions and Actors of Conflict Resolution in Okitipupa

The key to addressing social conflict lies in recognising and adopting effective conflict resolution processes, including the mechanisms used for such purposes. To fully grasp the conflict resolution systems among the people of Okitipupa, one must examine the local figures and indigenous institutions that play central roles in these processes. Conflict resolution in Okitipupa traditionally relied on the involvement of specific individuals and well-defined procedures. These individuals and structures were deeply embedded in the socio-political framework of the community.

The local institutions empowered indigenous figures like the *Agba* (elders), *Oloye* (chiefs), and *Oloriḗbi* (family heads) to play significant roles in conflict resolution, drawing their authority from traditional social norms. These mechanisms for resolving disputes were deeply rooted in cultural practices, values, and customs designed to promote peace and maintain social harmony. Essentially, these indigenous structures reflected locally developed political systems, where leadership was granted to individuals with established reputations, following the guidelines of native laws and customs.¹⁴³

In Okitipupa, a part of the Yoruba-speaking group, traditional institutions played a key role in managing and resolving conflicts. The family unit, as one such institution, served as a practical model for fostering shared goals, maintaining unity, and achieving positive outcomes.¹⁴⁴ Within this structure, the head of the family functioned as a mediator, addressing disputes and preventing conflicts through negotiation and reconciliation. Additionally, the elders, known as the *Agba*, were vital in resolving conflicts within the socio-political framework of Okitipupa.¹⁴⁵ On a broader level, Lawrence Bamikole characterises the *Agba*, or elder, as a figure of great respect, distinguished by their age and various other attributes that set them apart within their families, communities, and

¹⁴² Interview held with Chief Adeola Akinloye, Age 70, Traditionalist, at Ewi-Isale Street, Okitipupa on the 14th of July, 2024.

¹⁴³ Orji, K. E. and Olali, S. T. 2010. "Traditional Institutions and Their Dwindling Roles in Contemporary Nigeria: The Rivers State Example". In *Chieftaincy Institution in Nigeria*, Babawale, T., Alao, A. and Adesoji, B. (eds.), Lagos: Concept Publication Ltd, 402.

¹⁴⁴ Olaoba, B. 2013. *African Traditional Methods of Conflict Resolution*, ed. RemiAnifowose, PCR 731- National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN), 16 adapted from: <http://www.nou.edu.ng> Accessed on 23rd August, 2024.

¹⁴⁵ Interview held with Pa Benedict Ayadi, Age 74, Elder Stateman, at Oka Sawmill, Okitipupa, on the 16th of March, 2024.

beyond. An elder is expected to embody courage (*alakikanju*), and possess deep knowledge and wisdom while remaining open to criticism (*ologbon, oloye, afimotielomiran se*). They should demonstrate tolerance (*alamumora*) and maintain a strong sense of integrity (*olotito, olododo*). Additionally, an elder should be selfless and not driven by selfish interests (*anikanjopon*).¹⁴⁶

The *Agba* held a vital role in conflict resolution within the Okitipupa community, serving in diverse social capacities. Revered for their wisdom, they actively mediate disputes and promote harmony, ensuring peaceful relations among the people of Okitipupa.¹⁴⁷

The palace was another important socio-political institution that played a significant role in conflict resolution. In the Okitipupa socio-political structure, the king and high chiefs maintained their respective palaces, where disputes were addressed and settled. It is important to clarify the distinction between the *Agba* (elder) and the *Ijoye* (chief); while a chief could be an elder, not every elder holds the title of chief and only cases beyond the jurisdiction of the *Agba* were referred to the Palace. The governance system in Okitipupa features a sophisticated three-tier structure encompassing the executive, legislative, and judicial branches.¹⁴⁸ The *Jegun* of *Idepe*, (king of Okitipupa), acts as the supreme authority, supported by the *Ijoye, Ijama and Omaja* (council of chiefs) to facilitate effective governance within the kingdom. The king's court was the final Court of Appeal and Supreme Court for all cases.¹⁴⁹ Here, all cases, criminal and civil were brought to bear and laid to rest and it was only there that capital punishments could be pronounced upon an erring and guilty person, if and when needed. Together, the king, *Jegun* of *Idepe*-Okitipupa and his chiefs formulated laws aimed at curbing human misconduct and minimising conflicts within the community. These laws were crucial for administering justice among disputing parties, whether in the king's palace or the palaces of the high chiefs.¹⁵⁰

A key element of conflict resolution in Okitipupa has long been the role of social institutions like the *Otuor Egbe* (age-grade).¹⁵¹ The age-grade system, which was deeply embedded

¹⁴⁶ Bamikole, L.O. 2008. "Agba (Elder) as Arbitrator: A Yoruba Socio-Political Model for Conflict Resolution", paper presented at *The Afolabi Olabimtan Memorial Biennial International Conference* held at College of Humanities, Tai Solarin University of Education, Ijebu-Ode, 22nd -25th September, 2008, 12.

¹⁴⁷ Interview held with Pa Benedict Ayadi, Age 74, Elder Stateman, at Oka Sawmill, Okitipupa, on the 16th of July, 2024.

¹⁴⁸ Interview held with Chief Jeremiah Akindeyi, 60+, Traditional Political Leader, at Ode Idepe, Okitipupa, on the 15th of July 2024.

¹⁴⁹ Interview held with Chief Jeremiah Akindeyi, 60+, Traditional Political Leader

¹⁵⁰ Interview held with Chief Jeremiah Akindeyi, 60+, Traditional Political Leader

¹⁵¹ Interview held with High Chief Onifeso Onabule, Age 70+, Traditionalist, at Ewi-Isale Street, Okitipupa on the 13th of July, 2024.

in Okitipupa's culture and reflects the broader Ondo cultural practices, was designed to encompass various social groups, including hunters, market women, farmers' guilds, and youth clubs. These organisations provided a framework for resolving disputes among their members by applying wisdom and strategies to prevent conflicts from escalating. The contributions of these institutions—age-grade groups, unions, and clubs—toward fostering peace and maintaining social order in Okitipupa are significant and highly commendable.¹⁵²

From the foregoing, it is clear that traditional institutions such as the family, the palace, and the age-grade system play crucial roles in conflict resolution in Okitipupa. These socio-political structures continued to be central to managing and resolving disputes within the community.

Furthermore, traditional religious institutions played pivotal roles in conflict resolution in Okitipupa. Historical evidence indicated that religion has been one of the most influential factors in shaping human societies. Among the various traditional religious practices in Okitipupa, the veneration of *Ògún*, the deity of iron, was particularly significant in addressing disputes.¹⁵³ Religion, as a system of belief, reflects the impact of supernatural forces on human life and, within this framework, includes sacred sites such as shrines and groves where conflicts were mediated.¹⁵⁴ In Okitipupa culture, traditional religious institutions entrusted the responsibility of conflict resolution to the ancestors, gods, and deities, a practice seen as effective in maintaining peace.¹⁵⁵ These religious sites were managed by traditionalists, who acted as custodians of the respective deities or ancestral spirits and were known as chief priests.

In addition to these figures, the *Babaláwo*, or herbalists, held a prominent position in Okitipupa society for their perceived supernatural wisdom and abilities. Their knowledge of necromancy enabled them to uncover hidden truths and prevent conflicts through magical interventions, promoting peace both between individuals and within the broader community.¹⁵⁶ Therefore, it is clear that traditional religious institutions in Okitipupa were deeply involved in resolving both minor and persistent conflicts.

¹⁵² Interview held with High Chief Onifeso Onabule, Age 70+, Traditionalist, at Ewi-Isale Street, Okitipupa on the 13th of July, 2024.

¹⁵³ Interview held with Chief Akanni Agbede, Age 70+, Traditionalist, at Alo Street, Okitipupa on the 16th of July, 2024.

¹⁵⁴ Onadeko, T. 2008. "Yoruba Traditional Adjudicatory Systems". *African Study Monographs*, 29(1), 17.

¹⁵⁵ Interview held with Chief Akanni Agbede, Age 70+, Traditionalist

¹⁵⁶ Interview held with Chief Akanni Agbede, Age 70+, Traditionalist

Another important actor involved in the conflict resolution process among the Okitipupa people was the women. Their contributions to societal development are undeniable, and their involvement in promoting peace for sustainable development has positioned them as key advocates of harmony, love, and tolerance. In Okitipupa, women's participation in conflict resolution stemmed from their responsibilities both within the family and in the wider community. Their dedication to child-rearing and cultural preservation was a significant factor in their influence on peace. Okitipupa women were regarded as strong and resilient, especially in nurturing children. It was traditionally seen as their duty to instill societal values—such as patience, respect, honesty, love, transparency, diligence, and courage—through storytelling, fables, and folklore.¹⁵⁷ This early moral education helped curb selfishness, a root cause of conflict and fostered a generation of peace-oriented individuals. Consequently, women served as peace educators and were essential agents of fostering and maintaining peaceful human and social relationships.

In Okitipupa society, women, as wives and mothers, served as key intermediaries between their families and the broader community. Although they appeared to have limited public roles, their influence in private settings was profound. In situations of conflict between families, for instance, women exerted significant sway over their husbands behind closed doors, often guiding them in resolving disputes that arose during the day. While men held official authority, women acted as the *de facto* decision-makers within the household.¹⁵⁸ Additionally, their strong influence over their children enabled them to mediate and settle conflicts within the family, neighbourhood, or community. A mother's love and care made it difficult for her children to resist her efforts to reconcile disagreements.

In addition to their roles as mediators within their families, Okitipupa women also contributed to maintaining social harmony by fostering relationships and cooperation among different households and extended family networks. Through their involvement in informal gatherings, ceremonies, and other communal activities, women built social ties that reinforced unity within the community. Their ability to navigate these social networks often placed them in strategic positions to defuse tensions before they escalated into larger conflicts.¹⁵⁹

¹⁵⁷ Interview held with Chief Mrs Osutade Kehinde, Age 50+, Traditional Leader, at Okesare, Okitipupa on the 16th of July, 2024.

¹⁵⁸ Interview held with Chief Mrs Osutade Kehinde, Age 50+, Traditional Leader

¹⁵⁹ Interview held with Chief Mrs Osutade Kehinde, Age 50+, Traditional Leader

Moreover, women utilised their knowledge of traditional customs and societal expectations to subtly influence decision-making processes, not only within their own families but also in the broader community. In many cases, they acted as conduits for diplomacy, quietly negotiating peace and ensuring the continuation of communal stability.¹⁶⁰ Their deep understanding of personal dynamics, combined with their nurturing roles, enabled them to approach conflict with empathy and patience, making them highly effective peacemakers.

In essence, Okitipupa women were not merely confined to the domestic sphere but played pivotal roles in shaping the social fabric of their society. Their contributions to conflict resolution were both subtle and profound, ensuring that peace was maintained through a combination of personal influence, emotional intelligence, and the strategic use of social relationships. This highlights the often overlooked but critical role of women in sustaining communal cohesion and resolving disputes across various levels of Okitipupa's socio-political system.

Processes and Methods of Traditional Conflict Resolution in Okitipupa

Traditional African societies have utilised various methods for resolving conflicts, including mediation, adjudication, reconciliation, arbitration, and negotiation. They also make use of informal approaches and legal principles to influence disputants and highlight the consequences of their actions. These methods have consistently proven effective in maintaining harmony within traditional African settings.¹⁶¹ In the case of the Okitipupa people, like many Yoruba communities, they developed efficient homegrown strategies to address disputes within their social environment. These strategies, aimed at managing conflicts and fostering peace, are central to conflict resolution efforts and have been highly effective. Drawing from oral accounts gathered from respondents, some of these conflict resolution methods will be examined in this section.

Consensus Settlements and Alternative Dispute Resolution

In Okitipupa, a culturally rooted approach to conflict resolution known as *Iwijo* played an essential role in maintaining peace within families and the broader community.¹⁶² Derived from the Ikale dialect, *Iwijo* focused on consensus building by encouraging open, direct dialogue

¹⁶⁰ Interview held with Chief Mrs Osutade Kehinde, Age 50+, Traditional Leader

¹⁶¹ Nweke, K. 2012. "The role of traditional Institution of governance in managing social conflicts in Nigeria's Oil-Rich Niger Delta communities: Imperative of peace-building process in the post-amnesty era", *British Journal of Arts and Social Science*, Vol.5 No.2, 202-219.

¹⁶² Interview held with High Chief Omotola Emaye, Age 60+, Arogun of Idepe Okitipupa, at Okitipupa on the 16th of July, 2024.

between conflicting parties. The core principle behind this method was to foster mutual understanding and compromise, with each party expected to adjust their positions to achieve a peaceful outcome. This process often avoids the formalities of legal systems, instead prioritising personal and communal responsibility.¹⁶³

In practice, *Iwijo* was widely employed in resolving familial disputes, such as conflicts between husbands and wives or among siblings. The strength of this approach lay in its emphasis on mutual agreement and shared interest, making it effective in addressing issues where the emotional and relational ties were strong, such as within families. Beyond the domestic sphere, *Iwijo* has also proven successful in addressing broader social conflicts, particularly those involving community groups. For example, when two groups within the community have disputes over resources, land, or social obligations, the method encourages open discussion and compromise. The willingness of both sides to give up some ground for the greater good of community peace is essential for this approach to work.¹⁶⁴

When *Iwijo* failed to resolve a conflict or when the parties involved were unable to reach a consensus, a more structured form of mediation known as *Arowa* is employed. In the cultural context of Okitipupa, *Arowa* referred to an alternative dispute resolution method that involved a neutral third-party mediator, typically an elder (*Agba*) who held significant respect and authority within the community. This elder could be the head of a family or a quarter chief who has the wisdom and social standing to influence outcomes impartially.¹⁶⁵ The role of the elder in *Arowa* was not simply to impose a solution but to mediate through dialogue. The elder would listen carefully to both sides, analyse the root causes of the conflict, and then use his experience and wisdom to propose a fair solution. What set this method apart was the trust placed in the elder's judgment. The integrity of elders in Okitipupa was highly regarded, as they were known to be above corruption and free from bias. Their main objective was to promote peaceful coexistence, and they were seen as stewards of community harmony rather than enforcers of individual interests.¹⁶⁶

One key factor in the success of *Arowa* was the deep respect that the people of Okitipupa had for their elders. This respect formed the foundation of the entire conflict resolution process.

¹⁶³ Interview held with High Chief Omotola Emaye, Age 60+, Arogun of Idepe Okitipupa, at Okitipupa on the 16th of July, 2024.

¹⁶⁴ Interview held with High Chief Omotola Emaye, Age 60+, Arogun of Idepe Okitipupa

¹⁶⁵ Interview held with High Chief Omotola Emaye, Age 60+, Arogun of Idepe Okitipupa

¹⁶⁶ Interview held with High Chief Omotola Emaye, Age 60+, Arogun of Idepe Okitipupa

Whatever solution an elder proposed was typically accepted by the conflicting parties because it was viewed as impartial and in the best interest of the community. Elders were expected to be not only wise but also fair in their analysis and distribution of responsibility, ensuring that justice was served without favouritism.¹⁶⁷ This cultural respect for elder mediation ensured that disputes did not escalate into further conflict and that both parties were more likely to adhere to the proposed resolutions.

Moreover, both *Iwijo* and *Arowa* have a deep cultural significance in Okitipupa. These methods were more than just tools for conflict resolution; they were part of the social fabric that sustained community cohesion. They reflected the collective values of the society, such as the importance of family unity, respect for authority, and the prioritisation of peace over individual gain.¹⁶⁸ These indigenous methods not only resolved conflicts but also reinforced the communal ethos by encouraging dialogue, patience, and mutual respect. They could also address a wide range of conflicts, whether they involved personal relationships, property disputes, or larger social tensions within the community. Their adaptability allows them to be applied to different scales of conflict, from individual disagreements to group tensions, ensuring that peace is maintained at all levels of society.

Adjudicatory Proceedings

Adjudication in the Ikaleland, especially in Okitipupa, was not only a method for settling disputes but also deeply embedded in the region's socio-political structure. The process functioned as a mechanism to ensure order and maintain social harmony within the community. It was grounded in longstanding traditions that recognised the authority of elders and chiefs to mediate and resolve conflicts. However, when disputes could not be resolved by the elders, they were escalated to a higher authority: the king and his council of chiefs. This progression from elder mediation to the king's involvement underscores the hierarchical nature of traditional conflict resolution in Ikale society.¹⁶⁹

The traditional judicial process was conducted according to laws set by the paramount ruler, the *Jegun* of Idepe-Okitipupa, along with his council of chiefs. These laws were reflective of the values, customs, and social norms of the community, which made the system particularly

¹⁶⁷ Interview held with High Chief Omotola Emaye, Age 60+, Arogun of Idepe Okitipupa

¹⁶⁸ Interview held with High Chief Omotola Emaye, Age 60+, Arogun of Idepe Okitipupa

¹⁶⁹ Interview held with Chief Abel Akindokun, Age 60+, Yepata of Okitipupa, at Araromi-Lisa in Okitipupa on the 16th of July, 2024.

relevant to the local population. The Council of Chiefs played an advisory role, gathering information, hearing both sides of the conflict, and making recommendations. This consultation process ensured that every party had an opportunity to present their case. The *Jegun*, acting as the final authority, would then review these findings and issue a judgment. The adjudication system was considered sacrosanct; it was believed that justice, as dispensed by the king and his council, was both fair and uncorrupted, as those administering it had sworn oaths of impartiality.¹⁷⁰

One of the key objectives of this form of adjudication was not only to deliver justice but to maintain social cohesion. The resolution of disputes was intended to bring closure to both parties, ensuring that the conflict did not lead to further divisions within the community.¹⁷¹ The king's rulings were often viewed as final and binding, which meant that once a decision was made, it was expected to be respected and followed by all parties involved. This emphasis on finality helped prevent conflicts from escalating or resurfacing.

The types of disputes typically handled under this traditional judicial system were varied but often centred around issues that were central to the community's way of life. Land ownership disputes, for instance, were common, given the agrarian nature of the society. Questions of inheritance, which could determine a family's social and economic future, were also frequently adjudicated. Infidelity and child ownership were other sensitive issues that needed careful handling due to their potential to disrupt family structures. Each of these cases required a deep understanding of local customs and laws, which the king and his chiefs possessed, making the traditional adjudication system an effective tool for conflict resolution.¹⁷²

In broader terms, the adjudicatory system in Ikale culture was not static; it adapted to new circumstances and needs over time, which made it a dynamic aspect of indigenous governance and social order. It served not only as a tool for resolving conflicts but also as a way to reinforce the authority of the king and his council, solidify communal values, and ensure that justice was accessible to all members of the society. Through this system, the people of Okitipupa and the larger Ikale community were able to maintain stability and address grievances in a way that was deeply rooted in their cultural identity.

Consanguineous Method

¹⁷⁰ Interview held with Chief Abel Akindokun, Age 60+, *Yepata* of Okitipupa, at Araromi-Lisa in Okitipupa on the 16th of July, 2024.

¹⁷¹ Interview held with Chief Abel Akindokun, Age 60+, *Yepata* of Okitipupa

¹⁷² Interview held with Chief Abel Akindokun, Age 60+, *Yepata* of Okitipupa

This has to do with the involvement of unseen family ancestors, traditionally known as *Alajobi*, in conflict resolution among the Okitipupa people. *Alajobi* refers to the collective ancestors of a family, who are deeply respected and believed to possess the power to intervene in matters of justice and morality.¹⁷³ The concept of consanguinity, which signifies the deep-rooted familial bonds among members of the same lineage, plays a pivotal role in shaping the Okitipupa community's understanding of familial duty and obligation. Within this framework, *Alajobi* functions as an indigenous conflict resolution method, specifically within the family and extended family units.¹⁷⁴

Alajobi is viewed as a vital mechanism for mitigating disputes among family members. It is based on a deep cultural belief that the ancestors remain actively involved in the affairs of their descendants. This belief instils a profound sense of fear and anxiety in the hearts of family members, as they are mindful of the traditional adage that says, “*Abiamo kí gbọ ẹkún ọmo ẹ komá ta dide*” (meaning, a mother will not hear the cry of her child without responding). This dictum reflects the widely held belief that the ancestors, much like a caring parent, were always ready to defend and vindicate those who were truthful, while also punishing those who acted dishonestly. As such, invoking the ancestors in times of conflict is a powerful tool for ensuring fairness and integrity.¹⁷⁵

When phrases like “*alájòbí á da larin èmi ati ẹ*” (the ancestors will judge between you and me) were used during disputes, it signifies that the ancestors have been called upon to mediate and resolve such conflict. This invocation was taken very seriously within the Okitipupa culture, as the ancestors were perceived as just and incorruptible.¹⁷⁶ Their intervention was feared because their judgment was believed to be absolute and impartial. No one wished to have their case handed over to the ancestors, as their judgment was both swift and binding. In this way, the mere mention of *Alajobi* often prompts family members to resolve their disputes quickly, without the need for further escalation. This method has been instrumental in settling a variety of disputes in Okitipupa, ranging from chieftaincy succession conflicts to land ownership battles, as the fear of ancestral punishment outweighs the desire to continue the conflict.¹⁷⁷

¹⁷³ Interview held with Mr Adeniyi Ogundairo, Age 60+, Retired Civil Servant, at Araromi-Lisa in Okitipupa on the 16th of July, 2024.

¹⁷⁴ Interview held with Mr Adeniyi Ogundairo, Age 60+, Retired Civil Servant

¹⁷⁵ Interview held with Mr Adeniyi Ogundairo, Age 60+, Retired Civil Servant

¹⁷⁶ Interview held with Mr Adeniyi Ogundairo, Age 60+, Retired Civil Servant

¹⁷⁷ Interview held with Mr Adeniyi Ogundairo, Age 60+, Retired Civil Servant

However, despite its effectiveness, there was a growing perception among the Okitipupa people that *Alajobi's* judgment could sometimes be delayed. This sentiment was encapsulated in the saying, “*kilètó pa òsikàohun to da tibajẹ*” (before the ancestors punish the wicked, valuable things may have already been destroyed).¹⁷⁸ The proverb highlights a sense of frustration with the perceived slowness of the ancestors’ actions, particularly when the unjust party continues to act with impunity while the aggrieved parties await justice. This delay was interpreted as the ancestors giving the wrongdoers a long opportunity to correct their actions before the consequences were finally meted out. This perceived delay often leads to impatience among the affected parties, who may then resort to alternative methods of resolving the conflict—methods that are sometimes faster but could be more destructive.

Nonetheless, this criticism of *Alajobi's* perceived slowness does not negate its importance or effectiveness as a traditional conflict resolution tool. Despite the challenges, *Alajobi* continues to serve as a respected and culturally significant method for resolving disputes in Okitipupa, reinforcing the values of truthfulness, honesty, and justice that are deeply embedded in the community’s belief system. Its role in maintaining peace within families and ensuring that justice is served, even if delayed, continues to be highly regarded.

Oath Taking or Swearing

Oath-taking or swearing (*Ibura*) has been a deeply embedded practice in traditional African conflict resolution systems, including among the Okitipupa people. It is not merely a formalised ritual but a culturally significant mechanism used to settle disputes and ensure justice in situations where trust and truth are in question.¹⁷⁹ The process involved individuals or groups embroiled in conflict making serious declarations to affirm their honesty or bind themselves to specific obligations. These declarations were often made in the presence of sacred entities, including deities, to invoke supernatural validation and consequences for any deceit.

In Okitipupa, as in many African societies, the act of oath-taking held immense weight because of its spiritual implications. Swearing an oath before a deity was considered binding

¹⁷⁸ Interview held with Mr Adeniyi Ogundairo, Age 60+, Retired Civil Servant

¹⁷⁹ Interview held with Chief Akanni Agbede, Age 70, Traditionalist, at Alo Street, Okitipupa on the 17th of July 2024.

beyond human authority—it invoked divine judgment. The belief was that the gods or goddesses who witnessed these oaths would punish any party who failed to uphold their promises or who lied during the process. This punishment could take the form of illness, social ruin, and, in extreme cases, death. The belief in these supernatural consequences made *Ibura* a powerful deterrent against dishonesty or breach of agreements.¹⁸⁰

Historically, the Okitipupa people employed oath-taking as a common method to seal agreements, particularly in cases involving peace settlements or mutually obligatory arrangements. In situations where conflict had reached a point where negotiations alone could not restore peace, the conflicting parties were often required to swear before a deity to demonstrate their sincerity and commitment to the terms of the resolution. This ensured that the terms of the agreement would be respected, as no one would dare risk invoking the wrath of the gods by breaking the pact. The saying *enitobádalè á bálèlò* (anyone who betrays an agreement will die) reflects the deep-seated cultural belief that violating a sworn oath would result in divine retribution.¹⁸¹

Furthermore, *Ibura* was also employed in more contentious situations where determining guilt or innocence was difficult.¹⁸² In such cases, the conflicting parties would be required to take an oath before a deity to expose the guilty party. The belief was that the deity would reveal the truth and punish the wrongdoer, making it an effective method of conflict resolution when other methods had failed. This form of divine judgment was seen as final and irrevocable. The guilty party would often face swift punishment, whether through illness, misfortune, or death, reinforcing the fear and respect for this practice.

The practice of oath-taking was not arbitrary but involved specific deities who were considered particularly powerful and active in overseeing such matters. In Okitipupa, notable gods and goddesses, such as *Ayelala*, *Ogun le ri*, and *Ogun a se ho*, were commonly invoked during these ceremonies. These deities were believed to have the power to deliver immediate justice, making them central figures in the oath-taking process. *Ayelala*, a revered and feared deity, was known for delivering swift and decisive justice, making her an influential figure in resolving difficult disputes. As a goddess associated with truth and justice, *Ayelala's* origin could be traced back to the Ilaje kingdom, and she was also venerated by the Ikale people, including those from

¹⁸⁰ Interview held with Chief Akanni Agbede, Age 70, Traditionalist

¹⁸¹ Interview held with Chief Akanni Agbede, Age 70, Traditionalist

¹⁸² Interview held with Chief Akanni Agbede, Age 70, Traditionalist

Okitipupa. It was commonly said that an Ikale man would invoke *Ayelala's* name at least three times daily, reflecting the deep reverence they held for her.¹⁸³

Ayelala was seen as a formidable force, feared by those who committed wrongdoings. She was known for her ability to bring justice to witches, wizards, thieves, and other offenders, often leading them to publicly confess their crimes. When mysteries arose with diabolical undertones, *Ayelala* would be invoked to reveal the truth. People would bring their disputes to *Ayelala's* chief priest, seeking resolution through her divine intervention. *Ayelala* was feared and this had helped in the maintenance of peace and harmony among the people during the pre-colonial eras. The role of *Ayelala* in peace management in the Okitipupa had no rival.¹⁸⁴ In Ikale towns and villages, it was a strong belief that anyone who died under *Ayelala's* judgment would be buried in the forest along with all their possessions, whether acquired legally or otherwise. Additionally, those owing debts to such individuals were expected to settle them with the *Ayelala* priest or leave the amount where it could be found by the deceased's relatives, or else they would risk facing *Ayelala's* wrath.¹⁸⁵

In Okitipupa, traditional religious practices held deep significance, particularly regarding the roles of deities such as *Ogun le ri* and *Ogun a se ho*. These deities are revered as enforcers of justice, known for their ability to swiftly address conflicts and punish wrongdoers. Their shrines are situated in notable locations—‘*Ogun le ri*’ has a shrine in Ijamu's quarters, while ‘*Ogun a se ho*’ is venerated at Idimalo.¹⁸⁶ These deities, along with others in the community, were called upon when disputes arose, especially in cases where there was a need to expose and discipline an obstinate individual who refused to comply with agreements or social norms.¹⁸⁷

In such situations, a ritual involving the kolanut, specifically *obialáwémęta* (a kolanut with three lobes), was performed. This kolanut was considered sacred and played an important role in traditional oath-taking ceremonies. It was divided into three parts—one portion was placed at the shrine of the deity, symbolising the invocation of divine intervention. The other two parts were given to the opposing parties involved in the conflict, as a way to establish accountability before the deity.¹⁸⁸

¹⁸³ Interview held with Chief Akanni Agbede, Age 70, Traditionalist

¹⁸⁴ Interview held with Chief Akanni Agbede, Age 70, Traditionalist

¹⁸⁵ Interview held with Chief Akanni Agbede, Age 70, Traditionalist

¹⁸⁶ Interview held with Chief Akanni Agbede, Age 70, Traditionalist

¹⁸⁷ Interview held with Chief Akanni Agbede, Age 70, Traditionalist

¹⁸⁸ Interview held with Chief Akanni Agbede, Age 70, Traditionalist

According to traditional beliefs, after the oath was taken, it was only a matter of time before the guilty party was exposed and punished by the deity. The consequences were often considered severe and unavoidable, which underscored the fear and respect these deities commanded within the community. This ritual system of justice not only served to resolve conflicts but also acted as a deterrent against dishonesty and misbehaviour, maintaining social order within Okitipupa.

Ultimately, oath-taking (*Ibura*) served not only as a legal or social tool but also as a profound expression of the Okitipupa people's belief in the interconnectedness of the spiritual and physical worlds. The involvement of deities in conflict resolution ensured that justice was not merely a human affair but one overseen by higher powers, making it a method of last resort in ensuring peace, fairness, and order within the community.

Proverbial Rhetoric

In Okitipupa society, another key method of conflict resolution was deeply rooted in the use of proverbs, which were highly regarded as tools of wisdom, especially among elders. Proverbial expressions known as *Owe*, were an integral part of conflict mediation, with their origins could be traced back to the involvement of elders in dispute resolution. Elders often employ these traditional sayings to calm tensions and foster understanding between conflicting parties. A well-known proverb, “*Òweleshinòrò, tíòròbásonù, òwe la nfiwá*” (Proverbs enhance dialogue, and when misunderstandings arise, proverbs are used for resolution), underscores the vital role of proverbs in settling disputes. The essence of this saying lies in its emphasis on how proverbs can clarify misunderstandings and restore harmony.¹⁸⁹

Forgiveness and overlooking offences also played a crucial role in resolving conflicts in Okitipupa. Without a willingness to forgive, unresolved issues could escalate into further conflicts. In this view, Adeyemi Adegoju highlights two traditional proverbs that reflect the importance of forgiveness and a “forgive and forget” mindset, which he describes as embodying the spirit of magnanimity in conflict resolution. The first virtue is encapsulated in the Yoruba proverb, “*Bí a bá fi owó òtún bá omowí, à sítún fi owó òsì fà á móra*” (If we discipline a child with the right hand, we should embrace them with the left). The conditional structure in this proverb is significant. It reflects how conditional statements are often employed in rhetorical discussions on conflict

¹⁸⁹ Interview held with Mrs Idowu Akintimehin, Age 60+, Trader, at Erekiti Street, Okitipupa on the 16th of July 2024.

resolution. This sentence pattern is a hallmark of Yoruba proverbial wisdom, skillfully juxtaposing two contrasting ideas for rhetorical emphasis.¹⁹⁰

The second virtue, which reflected the principle of “forgive and forget”, acknowledged the seriousness of the offence but cautioned against retaliation, which could lead to greater harm. The proverb, “*Bí a bá rò dídùn ifòn, a ó hora dé eegun*” (If one is bothered by an itch, one may scratch down to the bone), underscored the danger of reacting impulsively to conflict. Here, scratching to the bone served as a metaphor for revenge, suggesting that pursuing vengeance could escalate the conflict to a point where it jeopardised the cohesion of the community. This proverb advocated for restraint and tolerance in managing grievances.¹⁹¹

Another proverb that powerfully conveyed the resolution of conflicts was: “*Bí a bádijúkí èniyàn burúkú kojá, a ò ní mọgbà tí ẹni rere á kojá*” (If we close our eyes to allow an evil person to pass, we will not recognise when a good person passes).¹⁹² This saying emphasised the importance of staying alert and open-minded, as ignoring those who brought harm also meant missing opportunities for positive connections. It carried a deeper message about forgiveness and tolerance, suggesting that holding onto grudges or focusing solely on negativity prevented one from experiencing kindness or goodwill from others. This proverb called for a balanced perspective—being cautious of wrongdoers but not letting them overshadow the good.

Additionally, proverbs acted as social tools for moral guidance. In moments when an individual was tempted by personal desires or influenced by bad company, the recall of a proverb served as a moment of reflection. It acted as a mental barrier that halted any wrongdoing by invoking wisdom from communal values. In this way, proverbs not only provide advice but also act as a reminder of the moral consequences of one's actions.¹⁹³

In Okitipupa, these kinds of proverbs were integral to conflict resolution, offering a structured way for communities to reconcile differences. Rather than allowing conflicts to fester or resurface, proverbs facilitate genuine reconciliation by promoting forgiveness and harmony. Disputing parties were encouraged to let go of aggression, grievances, and reservations, ensuring

¹⁹⁰ Adegaju, A. 2009. “Rhetoric in Conflict-Related Yoruba Proverbs: Guide to Constructive Conflict Resolution in Africa”, in *Africa Study Monographs*, Vol.30 (2), 65-66.

¹⁹¹ Adegaju, A. 2009. “Rhetoric in Conflict-Related Yoruba Proverbs: Guide to Constructive Conflict Resolution in Africa”, 65-66.

¹⁹² Adegaju, A. 2009. “Rhetoric in Conflict-Related Yoruba Proverbs: Guide to Constructive Conflict Resolution in Africa”, 65-66.

¹⁹³ Adegaju, A. 2009. “Rhetoric in Conflict-Related Yoruba Proverbs: Guide to Constructive Conflict Resolution in Africa”, 65-66.

that hostilities did not persist. The process was not merely about resolving the immediate issue, but about restoring relationships and creating a lasting sense of unity and peace.¹⁹⁴

Proverbial wisdom, therefore, served as a cultural tool that not only helps to manage disputes but prevents their recurrence, reflecting its profound impact on the social and moral fabric of Ikale society. Through its use, conflicts were settled and transformed into opportunities for growth, understanding, and communal healing. This reinforces the role of proverbs as more than just words, they are essential instruments of peace, capable of shaping behaviour and fostering a strong, harmonious community.

In Okitipupa, when individuals or families were perceived to have violated their community's deeply rooted customs and traditions, sanctions were often enforced to maintain social order and deter others from engaging in similar behaviours. These violations may include serious offences such as theft, intentional homicide, incest, disrespect toward elders, destruction of property, lying, bearing false witness, poisoning, and sexual violence, including rape. The underlying aim of these sanctions is to prevent such misbehaviour from disrupting the harmony of the community.¹⁹⁵ The penalties could take various forms and were often categorised into two main types: those believed to be imposed by forces and those enforced by the society itself. Spiritual or divine sanctions were thought to manifest as misfortunes such as sudden accidents, severe illness, untimely death, widespread famine, persistent poverty, emotional misery, infertility, or even the loss of children. These were perceived as the wrath of deities or ancestral spirits, meant to punish wrongdoers and serve as a warning to others about the consequences of immoral actions.

On the other hand, societal sanctions were more direct and tangible. The community may impose penalties such as exile, where offenders were forced to leave the community for a specified period, or permanent ostracism, where they were cut off from communal activities and social interactions. Monetary fines, compensation, and restitution were also common, where the offender was required to compensate for damages or make amends for their actions. In some cases, the offender may be required to publicly apologise or perform specific acts of contrition to restore their standing within the community.¹⁹⁶ These sanctions, whether spiritual or societal, served as mechanisms to reinforce cultural norms, maintain social stability, and promote communal

¹⁹⁴ Interview held with Mrs Idowu Akintimehin, Age 60+, Trader, at Erekiti Street, Okitipupa on the 16th of July 2024.

¹⁹⁵ Interview held with Mr John Akintimehin, Age 60+, Retired Teacher, at Erekiti Street, Okitipupa on the 16th of July 2024.

¹⁹⁶ Interview held with Mr John Akintimehin, Age 60+, Retired Teacher

harmony by addressing transgressions in a way that reflects both the moral and practical values of the Okitipupa people.¹⁹⁷

Based on the discussion above, it is clear that Okitipupa town possessed mechanisms for conflict resolution, similar to those found in various indigenous African cultures. The presence of locally established institutions focused on conflict resolution, along with the participation of indigenous figures in these processes, demonstrated the vitality and efficacy of conflict management within African traditional societies. One can infer that indigenous political, social, and religious institutions have developed as complex systems. These institutions not only addressed specific issues pertinent to their roles but also promoted harmonious coexistence within the community by resolving disputes both discreetly and openly.

¹⁹⁷ Interview held with Mr John Akintimehin, Age 60+, Retired Teacher

CHAPTER FOUR

CHANGE AND CONTINUITY IN TRADITIONAL CONFLICT RESOLUTION

MECHANISM IN OKITIPUPA TOWN

Impact of Colonialism on Traditional Conflict Resolution Mechanisms

The nature of society, whether modern or traditional, has always influenced its conflict management and resolution mechanisms. In the case of Okitipupa, the advent of British colonialism significantly altered its indigenous methods of conflict resolution. Before colonial rule, the *Jegun* of Idepe-Okitipupa, supported by the *Ijoye, Ijama and Omaja* (council of chiefs) were the political, cultural, and social administrators of Okitipupa, managing disputes in alignment with the customs and values of their people. However, the imposition of European governance through colonialism introduced new systems that fundamentally reshaped local conflict management structures, incorporating Western legal systems and administrative frameworks.¹⁹⁸ Colonial governance was characterised by bureaucratisation and centralisation, both of which were essential for the efficient control of public affairs. While centralisation enabled the British to maintain effective control over local affairs, bureaucratisation helped insulate colonial policies from local resistance by creating layers of administration that included traditional institutions.¹⁹⁹

Before colonial intervention, conflict resolution in Okitipupa was deeply embedded in the communal structure. Conflicts were generally handled through customary systems led by traditional rulers and elders, who utilised dialogue, mediation, and traditional laws based on customs and traditions to resolve disputes. The traditional leadership played the role of custodians of the law, ensuring that the resolution of conflicts reflected societal norms and maintained social harmony. Punishments for offenders were typically restorative, including communal service or fines, which reinforced community solidarity and accountability.²⁰⁰

With the arrival of the British government in Okitipupa, the colonial administration introduced indirect rule, a governance system that relied on local chiefs and traditional institutions

¹⁹⁸ Falola, T. 2006. "Power, Status, and Influence of Yorùbá Chiefs in Historical Perspective". In Falola, T. and Genova, A. (eds.), *Yoruba Identity and Power Politics*. New York: University of Rochester Press, 161-175.

¹⁹⁹ Dike, K.O. 1960. *Hundred Years of British Rule in Nigeria*. Lagos: Federal Ministry of Information.

²⁰⁰ Falola, T. 2006. Power, Status, and Influence of Yorùbá Chiefs in Historical Perspective. In Falola, T. and Genova, A. (eds.), *Yoruba Identity and Power Politics*. 161-175.

to administer the colony while ensuring British oversight.²⁰¹ This system was aimed at preserving some elements of traditional governance, but it subordinated local rulers to colonial authorities. As Aidelokhai notes, traditional rulers before colonialism were the ultimate authorities in their domains, but colonialism undermined this sovereign authority by positioning the British administrators as the ultimate power in decision-making.²⁰² Upon the British government's arrival in Nigeria, one of their key initiatives was the implementation of English law.²⁰³ They introduced a legal and legislative framework modelled after the British system, which gave the British Crown authority to establish courts and appoint officers responsible for maintaining peace, order, and governance.²⁰⁴ Initially, the Courts of Equity were introduced to address the commercial needs of European traders along the Southeastern Niger Coast.²⁰⁵ As British rule expanded to other regions, such as Lagos and surrounding areas, the jurisdiction of these courts grew accordingly.²⁰⁶ By 1876, the enactment of the Supreme Court Ordinance created a Supreme Court with broad civil and criminal jurisdiction. In 1900, following the establishment of the Protectorate of Southern Nigeria, additional courts were formed, including the Supreme Court of Southern Nigeria, the Commissioner's Court, and Native Courts. These were complemented by other judicial bodies such as Supreme, Provincial, and Cantonment Courts, which were integral to British colonial governance.²⁰⁷

In Okitipupa and across the Old Ondo Province, the British colonial administration introduced a formal court system that functioned primarily as a legal body, with minimal involvement in the political sphere. In contrast, the traditional system of justice in these areas was deeply embedded within the social structure and involved more than just the *Oba's* authority. Justice administration began at the family level, where individuals were part of extended family units known as *Ebi*. Each lineage was organised around a common ancestor, and the family was led by the *Olori-ebi* (the head of the family), typically the oldest male member.²⁰⁸ In the event of

²⁰¹ Abdullahi, W.Z. 2007. *Evolving of A New Role for Traditional Institutions in the Nigerian Constitution Centre For Local Government Development and Research*.

²⁰² Aidelokhai, D.I. 2008. "An Evaluation of The Relevance of Traditional Rulership Institution in the Nigerian State", *Medwell Journals*, 4(3), 78-94.

²⁰³ Taiwo, A. O. 2009. "Tracing Contemporary Africa's Conflict Situation to Colonialism: A Breakdown of Communication Among Natives". *Philosophical Papers and Reviews*, 1(4), 59-66.

²⁰⁴ Asein, J.O. 1998. *Introduction to Nigerian Legal System*. Ibadan: San Bookman Publishers, 150.

²⁰⁵ Asein, J.O. 1998. *Introduction to Nigerian Legal System*. 150

²⁰⁶ Asein, J.O. 1998. *Introduction to Nigerian Legal System*. 151

²⁰⁷ Asein, J.O. 1998. *Introduction to Nigerian Legal System*. 151

²⁰⁸ Afe, A. E. 2012. *The Growth of the Judicial System in the Old Ondo Province, 1915-1976*, Ph.D Thesis, Department of History and International Studies, Ekiti State University, Ado Ekiti.

disputes, it was customary for the family to first address the issue internally. The *Olori-ebi* would take the lead in facilitating discussions and attempting to mediate a peaceful resolution. He, along with other senior family members, would listen to both sides of the conflict and work towards reconciling the parties involved. It was only when the family head was unable to resolve the matter that the case would be escalated to the quarterhead or village head. In most cases, family heads convened meetings to address issues that impacted the family or its members, to maintain harmony within the group. Cases rarely bypassed this internal system unless the family-level mediation failed.²⁰⁹

One of the significant transformations brought by British colonialism in Okitipupa was the creation of a formal legal and enforcement structure, which included the Native Courts which were established by the Native Courts Ordinance of 1900, later expanded by the Native Courts Ordinance of 1914 and further reformed by the Native Courts Ordinance of 1933; the Native Authority Police was empowered by the Native Authority Ordinance of 1916 to establish local policing bodies. This law allowed traditional rulers or colonial-appointed leaders to enforce order within their jurisdictions, particularly through the establishment of the Native Authority Police, also called “Local Police” or “NA Police”; and the Colonial Prisons was governed by the Prisons Ordinance of 1916, which created a prison system to detain individuals awaiting trial and those convicted of crimes by both Native and colonial courts.²¹⁰ Before this, Okitipupa had no formalised prison system, and punishment typically took the form of community-based restitution or reparations.²¹¹ The British government introduced a penal system that mirrored European models, with the establishment of prisons as a means of punishment and control. The formation of Native Courts altered the traditional ways of conflict resolution, as these courts were a key part of the colonial strategy to extend European legal frameworks within local governance.²¹²

The creation of these courts diminished the power of local chiefs, who had previously been the main arbiters of justice through customary law. Under the colonial system, these chiefs were subordinated to the authority of the British colonial officers, with District Officers overseeing their

²⁰⁹ Afe, A. E. 2012. *The Growth of the Judicial System in the Old Ondo Province, 1915-1976*, Ph.D Thesis, Department of History and International Studies, Ekiti State University, Ado Ekiti.

²¹⁰ Unobe E. A. 1989. “Class Formation, State Construction and Customary Law in Colonial Nigeria”, *African Development: A Quarterly Journal of CODESRIA*, Vol. 14. No 4, 33-49.

²¹¹ Interview held with High Chief Omotola Emaye, Age 60+, *Arogun* of Idepe Okitipupa, at Okitipupa on the 16th of July, 2024.

²¹² Unobe E. A. 1989. “Class Formation, State Construction and Customary Law in Colonial Nigeria”, *African Development*, 33-49.

decisions. The chiefs' roles were now limited, as their authority could be challenged or overturned by colonial officials, who had the power to appoint or remove them if they failed to align with British policies.²¹³ This undermined the traditional, community-based mechanisms of conflict resolution, which were more focused on reconciliation than the strict imposition of order seen under the colonial system.

While local chiefs continued to operate within the Native Courts, their autonomy was compromised by the close supervision of British District Officers. These courts, though rooted in customary law, also applied colonial legal principles, reshaping how justice was administered. The British colonial government often codified and modified customary laws to align them with their own administrative and economic goals. This altered the nature of traditional laws, making them tools for colonial governance rather than genuine reflections of indigenous values. Civil and criminal cases were handled by the Native Courts. Every codification of laws, starting with the Native Courts Proclamation of 1900, embraced this principle. However, a close watch was maintained over these Courts, a Provincial Court was established in each of the Provinces, including the Old Ondo Province and these courts were superior courts of record.²¹⁴ Also, each court, regardless of its level, operated under the oversight of a Resident or political officer assigned to the Province. These officers wielded extensive authority, especially in criminal matters, and had broad jurisdiction in civil disputes, including cases between landlords and tenants, *habeas corpus* petitions, and personal contract lawsuits. Typically, civil cases were escalated to the Supreme Court on appeal. A crucial aspect to highlight is that both the administrative management and judicial oversight of the Native Courts were concentrated in the hands of colonial political officers. This essentially gave them control over the traditional chiefs, who frequently served as court members.²¹⁵

In addition, the British colonial system in Okitipupa introduced new administrative roles, such as District Heads, who acted as intermediaries between the colonial government and the local population. Often selected from the ranks of traditional leaders, these District Heads were tasked with upholding colonial policies, managing conflicts, collecting taxes, and maintaining law and order. This shift centralised authority under the District Heads and Native Courts, moving away

²¹³ Interview held with High Chief Omotola Emaye, Age 60+, *Arogun* of Idepe Okitipupa

²¹⁴ Unobe E. A. 1989. "Class Formation, State Construction and Customary Law in Colonial Nigeria", *African Development*, 33-49.

²¹⁵ Unobe E. A. 1989. "Class Formation, State Construction and Customary Law in Colonial Nigeria", *African Development*, 33-49.

from the more communal, decentralised methods of conflict resolution that had existed before the imposition of colonial rule.²¹⁶

A significant area of conflict during the colonial era in Okitipupa was related to land disputes and the transformation of land tenure systems. Before the arrival of the British colonial government, land ownership and rights in Okitipupa were communal.²¹⁷ Land was typically owned by extended families, clans, or communities, and its use was governed by customary laws. Chiefs and elders managed land disputes, ensuring that land was distributed based on lineage, kinship ties, and the needs of the community. In this communal system, the concept of individual land ownership was rare, and land could not be permanently alienated.²¹⁸

However, the arrival of British colonialists in Southern Nigeria during the late nineteenth century marked a significant transformation in the land tenure system. British traders, accustomed to the concept of freehold ownership, began acquiring land parcels in the Lagos colony, operating under the belief that these transactions granted them full ownership rights, including the authority to sell or transfer the land at will. This shift to an English freehold system, established with the signing of the Cession Treaty in 1861, led to profound conflicts between the existing customary land tenure practices and the newly imposed freehold system.²¹⁹

Although the British colonial administration took control of land management through the Cession Treaty, the rights to individual property remained with the local population. To better regulate land transactions, the colonial government enacted the Native Lands Acquisition Proclamation in 1900, which stipulated that any land transaction involving a non-native must receive approval from the High Commissioner.²²⁰ Consequently, only indigenous people could acquire land rights, either directly or indirectly, without the High Commissioner's consent.

In 1906, the Crown Lands Management Proclamation was introduced to oversee all Crown lands, designating the High Commissioner as the sole authority responsible for managing leases, sales, transfers, and other dealings related to Crown lands in Southern Nigeria. Following this, the Native Land Acquisition Ordinance was enacted in 1908 to govern the process of land acquisition from indigenous peoples. This ordinance was subsequently replaced in 1917 by the Native Lands

²¹⁶ Interview held with Chief Jeremiah Akindeyi, 60+, Traditional Political Leader, at Ode Idepe, Okitipupa, on the 15th of July 2024.

²¹⁷ Interview held with Chief Jeremiah Akindeyi, 60+, Traditional Political Leader

²¹⁸ Interview held with Chief Jeremiah Akindeyi, 60+, Traditional Political Leader

²¹⁹ Elias, T. O. 1971. *Nigerian Land Law*. London: Sweet and Maxwell, 11.

²²⁰ Elias, T. O. 1971. *Nigerian Land Law*, 11.

Acquisition Ordinance No. 32, which aimed to tighten regulations around land transfers, ensuring that no foreigner could acquire land rights from natives without the Governor's approval.²²¹ Through these legislative measures, the colonial regime facilitated the transfer of land from indigenous inhabitants to non-natives and foreigners, thereby disrupting the existing indigenous land management systems.

This shift eroded communal landholding systems in Southern Nigeria, including Okitipupa and paved the way for land commodification, which often led to disputes between local communities and colonial authorities or private interests. To manage and resolve land disputes under the new land tenure system, the British relied heavily on the Native Courts, which were now responsible for adjudicating land conflicts. However, these courts operated under the supervision of British officials, who imposed their understanding of property rights, often at odds with local customs. British authorities typically favoured land claims that aligned with their economic interests, such as granting land concessions to plantation owners or companies. This created tensions as local populations resisted these changes, viewing them as encroachments on their communal rights.²²²

In many cases, land disputes arose between indigenous families and colonial settlers or corporations seeking to exploit land for agricultural or infrastructural purposes. When these disputes were taken to the Native Courts, the resolution often reflected the interests of the colonial administration, leading to the disenfranchisement of local communities. Traditional leaders, who previously managed land allocation and disputes, found their authority diminished, as the colonial legal system prioritised written documentation and land titles over oral traditions and customary rights.²²³ Moreover, the British introduced taxes on land and required formal land registration, which many locals could not navigate due to their unfamiliarity with the colonial legal framework. This led to further disputes, as landowners who failed to register their land lost their claims, making it easier for colonial settlers or corporations to take possession of valuable land.²²⁴ The shift towards individual land ownership and the formalisation of land rights thus disrupted the

²²¹ Mamman, A.B. 2004. Land Use Policies Since 1960. Available at <http://www.onlinenigeria.com/land/?blurb=529> Accessed on 19th September, 2024

²²² Udoekanem, N.B., Adoga, D. O., and Onwumere, V.O. 2014. "Land Ownership in Nigeria: Historical Development, Current, Current Issues and Future Expectations", *Journal of Environment Science*, 4, (21), 182-188.

²²³ Interview held with High Chief Omotola Emaye, Age 60+, *Arogun* of Idepe Okitipupa, at Okitipupa on the 16th of July, 2024.

²²⁴ Udoekanem, N.B., Adoga, D. O., and Onwumere, V.O. 2014. "Land Ownership in Nigeria: Historical Development, Current, Current Issues and Future Expectations", (21), 182-188.

traditional land tenure system, sparking a series of land-related conflicts often resolved in favour of the colonial government or private interests.

Furthermore, the British colonial administration introduced new institutions for conflict resolution, superimposing them on pre-existing traditional systems in Okitipupa. Although the British viewed Indigenous courts and laws as inferior, and their principles of justice, equity, and conscience as “barbaric”, they found it expedient to adapt certain aspects of the local systems. Traditional conflict resolution often avoided harsh physical punishments, opting instead for fines, restitution, or public apologies, which the Native Courts adopted. This was partly because these methods were more in line with indigenous conflict resolution customs, and they helped maintain the legitimacy of colonial rule by aligning with local practices.²²⁵ This pragmatic approach helped shape the reactions of the Okitipupa populace and its leadership toward these new colonial structures. The establishment of the Native Authority Police, along with Native Authority Prisons and imprisonment policies, was central to the enforcement of British law. These institutions were designed to punish, rehabilitate, and incapacitate offenders, with aims of deterrence, restitution, and social order. The Police, operating under the oversight of Native Authorities, were tasked with maintaining law and order, often resorting to coercive methods unfamiliar to the traditional justice system of Okitipupa. This shift marginalised traditional rulers and eroded the influence of customary laws.²²⁶

The Native Authority Prisons, in particular, were a direct creation of British colonial authority, aimed at consolidating control in regions where significant resistance to colonial rule existed. Prisons were first introduced in Nigeria by the British colonial government in areas where strong opposition to colonial rule had been encountered, such as the Kano Central Prison, established in 1903 following the British conquest. Similarly, Okitipupa, being a key seat of traditional authority, vehemently resisted British encroachment. The resistance was largely driven by concerns that colonial dominance would undermine the authority of the king, a fear realised after the British victory over Okitipupa in 1897.²²⁷

Despite the conquest, the people of Okitipupa continued to protect the authority of the king's position, resisting colonial interference in local governance. The opposition to British

²²⁵ Interview held with High Chief Omotola Emaye, Age 60+, *Arogun* of Idepe Okitipupa, at Okitipupa on the 16th of July, 2024.

²²⁶ Alemika, E. 1995. “Trends and Conditions of Imprisonment in Nigeria”, *International Journal of Offenders, Therapy and Comparative Criminology*, Vol. 37, No. 2, 147-162.

²²⁷ Alemika, E. 1995. “Trends and Conditions of Imprisonment in Nigeria”, 147-162.

policies and institutions necessitated the establishment of prisons and other coercive measures to maintain control. Following the British proclamation of the Northern Nigeria Protectorate in 1900, the policy of effective occupation was implemented, prioritising colonial governance and the imposition of English legal and institutional frameworks.²²⁸ Okitipupa Prison was built as part of this effort, becoming a holding place for those who defied colonial policies, including tax evaders, saboteurs of colonial infrastructure, and individuals accused of criminal offences. The prison system thus became a key instrument in enforcing British authority over the region.²²⁹ This approach reflected the broader colonial strategy of using coercive infrastructure to ensure compliance with imperial rule and subdue resistance from local populations.²³⁰

Equally, the introduction of the Local Government law in the then-Western Nigeria in 1952 reduced the judicial authority of traditional rulers, transferring most of their adjudicative powers to modern legal structures. This shift relegated traditional leaders to largely ceremonial roles, with their involvement in conflict resolution limited to a few specific matters.²³¹ Despite this, traditional conflict resolution methods remained effective during the colonial period. Issues like inheritance, property disputes, and marital conflicts were still handled by these local authorities. Only when an agreement could not be reached or when one party was dissatisfied with the ruling would the case be escalated to colonial courts.²³²

Aboyeji supports this view, emphasising that the authority of traditional leaders remained intact in the eyes of the general population, who continued to show them respect despite the colonial government's efforts to undermine their power. There was a strong preference for resolving disputes peacefully through traditional mechanisms rather than relying on the colonial justice system, which was seen as intrusive.²³³ Those who chose the modern legal system were often viewed negatively, and perceived as causing unnecessary trouble. Land disputes, particularly

²²⁸ Afe, A. E. 2012. *The Growth of the Judicial System in the Old Ondo Province, 1915-1976*, Ph.D Thesis, Department of History and International Studies, Ekiti State University, Ado Ekiti.

²²⁹ Afe, A. E. 2012. *The Growth of the Judicial System in the Old Ondo Province, 1915-1976*

²³⁰ Afe, A. E. 2012. *The Growth of the Judicial System in the Old Ondo Province, 1915-1976*

²³¹ Ojo, M. O. D. 2013. Symbols of Warning, Conflict, Punishment and War and their Meanings among the Pre-colonial Yoruba Natives: A Case of Aroko. *Antropologija*, 13(1), 1-22.

²³² Interview held with High Chief Onifeso Onabule, Age 70+, Traditionalist, at Ewi-Isale Street, Okitipupa on the 13th of July, 2024.

²³³ Aboyeji, A. J. 2019. Peace and Conflict Management in Traditional Yoruba Society. *Journal of Living Together*, (1), 201-224.

those concerning agricultural land, were commonly resolved through the practice of *isakole*—a form of land rent paid either in cash or agricultural produce.²³⁴

It is worth noting that during the colonial era, social groups played a significant role in the peace and conflict resolution processes in Yorubaland, including Okitipupa. One notable group was the Agbekoya movement, a collective of local cocoa and oil palm farmers with networks across various cities in Yorubaland.²³⁵ This group became central in advocating for farmers' rights, leading to multiple confrontations with colonial authorities and other stakeholders. Many of these disputes revolved around issues such as land ownership and rent payments. While some conflicts were settled peacefully, others escalated into violence. In areas where the Agbekoya held considerable influence like in Ondo, they also took on roles in mediating local disputes.²³⁶ In cases where farmers were unable or unwilling to pay taxes, Agbekoya leaders mediated to find mutually agreeable solutions with local administrators, thereby preventing the escalation of tensions. They acted as a collective voice, defending farmers from punitive actions by the colonial authorities.²³⁷

Another important social organisation was the vigilante group, which had roots in the pre-colonial hunters' guild. They focused on maintaining security and preventing crime and became essential in managing conflicts during the colonial period. The vigilante group worked within traditional conflict resolution frameworks, assisting in the settlement of cases brought before them. Their involvement helped reinforce the community-based approach to conflict resolution, blending traditional methods with emerging colonial dynamics.²³⁸

From the foregoing, it is evident that colonialism in Okitipupa introduced profound changes to the way conflicts were managed and resolved, particularly in the area of land disputes and the land tenure system. The traditional mechanisms of conflict resolution, which were based on communal values and mediation, were supplanted by a colonial system that emphasised centralised control, formal legal institutions, and bureaucratic governance. The introduction of colonial laws that favoured individual land ownership and the commodification of land created

²³⁴ Interview held with High Chief Onifeso Onabule, Age 70+, Traditionalist

²³⁵ Adekunle, J. O. 2009. Agbekoya Peasant Uprising and Rebellion, 1968-1969, in Ness, I. (ed.). *The International Encyclopaedia of Revolution and Protests*. Oxford: John Wiley and Sons, 20.

²³⁶ Adekunle, J. O. 2009. Agbekoya Peasant Uprising and Rebellion, 1968-1969, in Ness, I. (ed.). *The International Encyclopaedia of Revolution and Protests*, 20.

²³⁷ Bello, T. and Mitchell, M. I. 2018. "The Political Economy of Cocoa in Nigeria: A History of Conflict or Cooperation?" *Africa Today*, 64(3), 71-92.

²³⁸ Ojo, M. O. D. 2013. Symbols of Warning, Conflict, Punishment and War and their Meanings among the Pre-colonial Yoruba Natives: A Case of Aroko. *Antropologija*, 13(1), 1-22.

new conflicts, often resolved in ways that favoured British economic interests. Native courts, prisons, and the Native Authority Police became instruments of colonial power, undermining the authority of traditional rulers and reshaping the local political and social landscape. Despite these transformations, elements of customary law persisted, albeit altered by colonial influences.

Post-Independence Legal Reforms and Traditional Mechanisms

Post-independence legal reforms in Okitipupa, like in many parts of Nigeria, were marked by a complex interaction between inherited colonial legal structures and indigenous conflict resolution mechanisms. After Nigeria gained independence in 1960, the new government sought to reform the legal system to reflect its national identity and independence from British influence. However, the challenge of balancing statutory law with customary law remained a central issue, particularly in rural areas like Okitipupa where traditional conflict mechanisms had long been the primary form of dispute resolution.

At the time of independence, Nigeria inherited a dual legal system that combined British-style statutory law with customary laws that had been subordinated during colonial rule.²³⁹ In Okitipupa, as in many parts of Nigeria, the colonial administration introduced formal courts, police forces, and prisons that often marginalised traditional authority structures. The Native Authority Police and Native Courts played central roles in law enforcement and dispute resolution, but these institutions operated largely to support colonial policies, not the interests of local communities.²⁴⁰ After independence, while there was a shift toward Nigerian control of these institutions, the basic framework of British legal principles and their supporting infrastructures remained intact. Consequently, one of the key challenges facing the newly independent Nigerian government was to reform these systems in a way that would align with the aspirations of a free nation, while also reflecting the social and cultural realities of its diverse regions, including Okitipupa.²⁴¹

In the immediate post-independence period, Nigeria embarked on efforts to modernise its legal system. The government sought to consolidate a National legal framework that would promote justice, human rights, and development. One of the earliest reforms was the gradual phasing out of Native Authority Courts, which had been established under British rule to enforce

²³⁹ Mamdani, M. 1996. *Citizen and Subject: Contemporary Africa and the Legacy of Late Colonialism*. Princeton University Press.

²⁴⁰ Afe, A. E. 2012. *The Growth of the Judicial System in the Old Ondo Province, 1915-1976*

²⁴¹ Obilade, A. O. 1979. *The Nigerian Legal System*. Ibadan: Spectrum Books, 12.

colonial law. These courts were criticised for being a tool of colonial coercion, often imposing harsh punishments on local populations. Their replacement with Magistrate Courts was intended to provide more uniform and transparent legal processes, consistent with modern judicial standards.²⁴² The Native Authority Police, which had been instrumental in maintaining colonial control, was merged into a unified National Police Force after independence. This reform was designed to centralise law enforcement and reduce the potential for abuse at the local level. In Okitipupa, the integration of the local police into the National Force shifted the balance of power from traditional rulers to the central government, further diminishing the influence of indigenous leaders in legal matters.

Similarly, land tenure reform was another important area of post-independence legal reform. The 1978 Land Use Act, for instance, sought to nationalise all lands and place them under state control. This reform addressed unequal land access and streamlined land ownership under a more formal legal structure.²⁴³ In Okitipupa, where local chiefs and councils had traditionally settled land disputes, the new legislation challenged the authority of these traditional structures and introduced new tensions between statutory law and customary practices.

The postcolonial era in Okitipupa witnessed the persistence and evolution of various conflicts that had roots in the colonial period but transformed into new forms. These included sociopolitical, religious, resource-based, and inter-ethnic conflicts. In the early years of independence, from 1960 to 1966, political instability plagued the young Nigerian nation. A notable instance of this unrest was the rivalry between prominent Yoruba political figures, which led to violent clashes among their supporters. This turmoil culminated in the infamous *Operation Wetie*, characterised by widespread violence and destruction of property.²⁴⁴ The conflict escalated further, contributing to the 1965 post-election crisis, which in turn set the stage for the January 1966 military coup.²⁴⁵

The primary causes of these conflicts were attributed to the political ambitions of key actors, as well as ethnic rivalries that were deepened by colonial policies aimed at advancing the

²⁴² Obilade, A. O. 1979. *The Nigerian Legal System*, 12

²⁴³ Tunde, A. F. 2010. *The Nigerian Land Use Act: Cases and Materials*. Lagos: Nigerian Institute of Advanced Legal Studies.

²⁴⁴ Basiru, A. S. 2014. Why They Might Have Gone Wild: The Yorubas of Southwestern Nigeria and the Politics of the First Republic. *Inkanyiso, Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 6(1), 23-29.

²⁴⁵ Duyile, W. A. and Oyewale, O. P. 2021. Political Parties, Violent and Culture of Electioneering Protest in South-Western Nigeria: The 1983 Experience. *European Journal of Development studies*, 1(1), 22-28.

self-interests of the British administration. Manipulations by the Federal Government also fueled tensions. The Agbekoya uprising between 1968 and 1969 further exemplified the unrest, as cocoa and palm oil farmers in Ibadan and Ondo protested the imposition of taxes during a period of economic hardship, compounded by diseases affecting their crops. The farmers' grievances were exacerbated by the harsh treatment they received from local agricultural authorities.²⁴⁶

The 1970s, marked by military rule and an economic boom, saw a temporary reduction in large-scale conflicts across Yorubaland, including Okitipupa. However, localised disputes related to land ownership and tenancy became more frequent during this time.²⁴⁷ With the return of democracy in 1979, political conflicts reemerged, particularly following the controversial 1983 elections, which sparked violence similar to that seen in the 1960s, again resulting in an *Operation Wetie*-like scenario. Perceived electoral fraud was a key trigger for the unrest, particularly in Oyo and Ondo states.²⁴⁸

In 1999, Nigeria transitioned once again to democracy and new forms of conflict arose in Okitipupa, including a rise in inter-ethnic violence and the formation of ethnic militias. Clashes between Hausa and Yoruba groups in Ondo, and ongoing farmer-herder conflicts, reflected growing tensions over land and resource control. The herder-farmer clashes were driven by competition for scarce resources like water and grazing land, with violence escalating due to the lack of adequate law enforcement and justice, leading to cycles of retaliatory attacks.²⁴⁹

In addressing these conflicts, both traditional and modern conflict resolution mechanisms were employed. Traditional adjudication practices were adapted to contemporary settings, with syndicated radio and television programs like *Ijoko Ojogbon* and *Agborandun* playing a role in mediating disputes. Local actors, including traditional rulers, vigilante groups, and organisations like the Oodua People's Congress (OPC), were also key in resolving conflicts, using a mix of indigenous conflict resolution strategies and modern methods of Alternative Dispute Resolution

²⁴⁶ Adekunle, J. O. 2009. Agbekoya Peasant Uprising and Rebellion, 1968-1969, in Ness, I. (ed.). *The International Encyclopaedia of Revolution and Protests*. Oxford: John Wiley and Sons, 20.

²⁴⁷ Arowosogbe, J. O. 2019. Hausa-Fulani Pastoralists and Resource Conflicts in Yorubaland. *International Journal of Postcolonial Studies*, 21(8), 1157- 1187.

²⁴⁸ Duyile, W. A. and Oyewale, O. P. 2021. Political Parties, Violent and Culture of Electioneering Protest in South-Western Nigeria: The 1983 Experience. *European Journal of Development studies*, 1(1), 22-28.

²⁴⁹ Interview held with Mr Olatunde Aladepupo, 50+, Civil Servant, at Ode Idepe, Okitipupa, on the 15th of July, 2024.

(ADR).²⁵⁰ These approaches remain relevant in managing the range of conflicts that persist in the region today.

Furthermore, in Nigeria, of which Okitipupa is part, the establishment of a structured legal system, encompassing various courts such as the Magistrate Court, High Court, Court of Appeal, and Supreme Court, provided residents with formal avenues to address and resolve a range of conflicts. These institutions offered a mechanism for individuals and communities to seek justice in matters that were often contentious and deeply personal.²⁵¹ Divorce cases, for instance, became increasingly common in this structured legal environment, as individuals sought to navigate the complexities of marital dissolution through legal channels rather than relying solely on traditional practices. The courts provided a platform for equitable resolution, allowing for considerations of property distribution, child custody, and alimony in accordance with statutory laws. Issues of paternity fraud, which could have significant social and legal implications, were increasingly brought before the courts. This included cases where individuals sought to contest paternity claims for various reasons, such as child support or inheritance rights. The legal system offered a structured approach to resolving these sensitive matters, often involving DNA testing and other forms of evidence to establish biological relationships.²⁵²

Similarly, disputes related to chieftaincy often found their way into the courts, where the legitimacy of claims to traditional titles and the authority of chiefs could be contested. The legal system offered a means to adjudicate such matters, ensuring that decisions were based on established laws rather than solely on traditional customs, which could be subject to manipulation or bias. Land and boundary disputes, a frequent source of conflict in many communities, also saw an increased reliance on the courts for resolution.²⁵³ As urbanisation and population growth intensified competition for land, residents of Okitipupa turned to the legal system to clarify ownership and establish boundaries, often utilising legal documentation and expert testimony to support their claims. The courts played a crucial role in adjudicating these conflicts, ensuring that decisions were grounded in legal principles and the rule of law.

Overall, the formal legal framework in Okitipupa empowered individuals to seek justice through established legal procedures, thereby reducing reliance on informal or traditional conflict

²⁵⁰ Interview held with Mr Olatunde Aladepupo, 50+, Civil Servant.

²⁵¹ Interview held with Mr Olatunde Aladepupo, 50+, Civil Servant.

²⁵² Interview held with Mr Olatunde Aladepupo, 50+, Civil Servant.

²⁵³ Interview held with Mr Olatunde Aladepupo, 50+, Civil Servant.

resolution mechanisms. This shift not only reflected changing societal norms but also highlighted the importance of the legal system in promoting fairness and accountability within the community.

Adaptation of Traditional Conflict Mechanism in Contemporary Okitipupa

The integration of traditional conflict resolution mechanisms with contemporary approaches in Okitipupa reflects a dynamic adaptation to the evolving social landscape. This integration involves addressing the deficiencies of existing conflict management strategies, reviving beneficial traditional values that had been overlooked, and establishing a national security policy that synergises modern and traditional practices. Many traditional institutions, such as guilds and community guards that historically supported the political economy of Okitipupa, had been marginalised without thorough evaluation, highlighting the need for a balanced approach to conflict resolution.

Despite the challenges posed by colonial influences and modernisation, traditional institutions remain crucial in conflict resolution within Okitipupa. The *Jegun* of Idepe-Okitipupa serves as the central traditional authority, responsible for maintaining social order. Community members often seek the king's intervention during disputes, demonstrating respect for traditional authority, although serious crimes such as murder, theft, human trafficking, and drug trafficking fall outside *Jegun's* jurisdiction. This indicates a collaborative relationship between traditional rulers and contemporary law enforcement agencies, showcasing a blended approach to governance.²⁵⁴

Traditional rulers and chiefs serve as the esteemed leaders and guardians of Okitipupa's rich cultural heritage, commanding immense respect from their communities both locally and beyond. Their words are regarded as law, and their counsel is valued and heeded by the populace. As impartial arbitrators, traditional rulers are often sought for their wisdom in adjudicating disputes and resolving conflicts. They play a crucial role in mediating issues among community members, particularly in addressing land disputes, inter-community tensions, and religious conflicts before they escalate into violence.²⁵⁵ Land disputes are a significant source of conflict in Okitipupa, as land is vital for wealth creation and sustenance through both subsistence and

²⁵⁴ Interview held with Chief Abel Akindokun, Age 60+, *Yepata* of Okitipupa, at Araromi-Lisa in Okitipupa on the 16th of July, 2024.

²⁵⁵ Interview held with Chief Abel Akindokun, Age 60+, *Yepata* of Okitipupa

commercial agriculture. Recognising the importance of their role, the government often relies on the *Jegun* of Idepe-Okitipupa and his chiefs to maintain peace within the community. The *Jegun* actively works to resolve hostilities between individuals, ensuring that tensions do not escalate into broader communal crises. By doing so, traditional rulers contribute to the stability and harmony of Okitipupa, safeguarding the community's well-being and fostering a spirit of cooperation among its members.²⁵⁶

Elders (*Agba*) also play a critical role in the conflict resolution processes in Okitipupa. Traditionally, African societies have relied on the wisdom and experience of elders to mediate disputes and foster peace. These respected figures utilise indigenous knowledge and customary practices, often convening community-based justice mechanisms to resolve conflicts.²⁵⁷ Elders and traditional councils still played a significant role in mediating chieftaincy disputes. They often convened meetings to discuss grievances, relying on established customs and precedents to resolve conflicts. The input of respected figures in the community was crucial to legitimising the resolution process. The government sometimes appointed panels to investigate and adjudicate chieftaincy-related disputes, balancing traditional customs with modern legal frameworks. Despite the disruptions caused by colonial legacies, the acknowledgement of elders' roles in justice and conflict resolution remains significant in contemporary Okitipupa, underscoring their importance in promoting social cohesion.

In the same vein, some customary courts were formally incorporated into the Nigerian legal system, allowing them to operate under statutory law while retaining their focus on traditional norms and values. This has helped bridge the gap between indigenous conflict resolution mechanisms and modern legal frameworks. Also, during judicial processes in the courtroom, witnesses and defendants were commonly questioned about their religious affiliations, whether modern or traditional. They were often required to take an oath using a religious instrument associated with their belief system. For instance, a traditional worshipper might swear an oath with a cutlass, invoking the god of iron's power to enforce truthfulness in their testimony. This practice underscores the respect afforded to traditional conflict resolution mechanisms in Okitipupa, highlighting their integral role in the legal process and community values.²⁵⁸

²⁵⁶ Interview held with Chief Abel Akindokun, Age 60+, *Yepata* of Okitipupa

²⁵⁷ Interview held with Chief Abel Akindokun, Age 60+, *Yepata* of Okitipupa

²⁵⁸ Interview held with Chief Abel Akindokun, Age 60+, *Yepata* of Okitipupa

The Nigerian government has increasingly promoted Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) mechanisms as a way to reduce the burden on formal courts and offer more culturally appropriate solutions to disputes. In Okitipupa, ADR has provided a formalised structure for resolving conflicts through mediation and arbitration, in line with the community's traditional practices. In contemporary Okitipupa, the use of traditional security outfits, such as *Amotekun*, illustrates an innovative response to local security challenges. Established on January 9, 2020, by the governors of the six southwestern states of Nigeria, *Amotekun* was conceived as a Regional initiative to combat increasing insecurity and enhance local governance. The initiative arose from a security summit in Ibadan, where it was decided that each state would contribute resources to support the new security framework.²⁵⁹ *Amotekun* comprises local hunters, members of the Oodua Peoples Congress (OPC), *Agbekoya*, and the Nigeria Security and Civil Defence Corps (NSCDC), reflecting a grassroots effort to address security concerns through a community-oriented lens.

The rise of ethnic and regional militias, such as the OPC, further illustrates the shifting dynamics in conflict resolution in Okitipupa. Formed in 1994 in response to perceived political marginalisation, the OPC initially focused on advocating for Yoruba autonomy and cultural promotion.²⁶⁰ Over time, it has evolved into a multifaceted organisation engaged in vigilantism and crime prevention, highlighting the interplay between political activism and security efforts within the region. Vigilantism, which has roots in the pre-colonial era, continues to manifest in Okitipupa through various self-defence groups. During colonial times, some independent local communities maintained defence mechanisms to protect their territories. Today, the proliferation of vigilante groups plays a crucial role in conflict resolution and community safety, often complementing the efforts of traditional and formal security systems.²⁶¹

The coexistence of traditional and modern conflict resolution mechanisms in Okitipupa exemplifies a holistic approach to governance and social stability. During the early post-colonial period, traditional rulers had representation in parliament, and calls for integrating these institutions into modern governance structures remain relevant. The recognition and official

²⁵⁹ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Amotekun#:~:text=The%20Western%20Nigeria%20Security%20Network,curbing%20insecurity%20in%20the%20region>. Accessed on the 19th October, 2024

²⁶⁰ <https://www.hrw.org/report/2003/02/28/oodua-peoples-congress-opc/fighting-violence-violence> Accessed on the 19th October, 2024

²⁶¹ Interview held with Chief Abel Akindokun, Age 60+, *Yepata* of Okitipupa

adoption of traditional conflict management practices not only promote peace but also foster development in Okitipupa, illustrating the enduring significance of these systems in addressing contemporary challenges.

Continuities in Traditional Conflict Resolution Mechanisms

Continuities in traditional conflict resolution mechanisms in Okitipupa, as well as in other Nigerian communities, reflect the enduring significance of cultural heritage and community-based approaches to resolving disputes. In Okitipupa, traditional methods remain indispensable for maintaining social cohesion, demonstrating the community's deep connection to its past. Despite modernisation and legal reforms, these mechanisms have stood the test of time, showcasing the respect and value placed on traditional authority and practices.

A distinguishing feature of the traditional conflict resolution system, which is also evident in Okitipupa, is the emphasis on reconciliation over the strict establishment of guilt. Unlike the Western legal system, which often prioritises assigning blame and determining guilt, the traditional resolution system, especially in family or community disputes, is more focused on finding enduring solutions while sustaining harmony. Mediators or arbiters, such as elders and community leaders, aim to foster camaraderie, seeking to reconcile the parties involved rather than declaring one guilty and vindicating the other. In cases deemed avoidable, trivial, or unnecessary, the goal is to encourage forgiveness and mutual understanding, leading to a win-win outcome. This approach highlighted the community's preference for preserving relationships and social cohesion over punitive measures.²⁶²

The pivotal role of community leaders and elders in conflict resolution is a key continuity in Okitipupa. These individuals, with their deep knowledge of traditional customs and practices, continue to mediate disputes and maintain peace. Their involvement complements modern government and security agencies, creating a balance between traditional and contemporary approaches. The king, *Jegun* of Idepe-Okitipupa, possessed a deep understanding of societal values, ethics, and the traditional methods of conflict resolution that have been passed down through generations. His familiarity with local norms ensures that conflicts are managed in a culturally sensitive manner, fostering trust and legitimacy in the community.²⁶³

²⁶² Interview held with Mr Peter Ayelabola, Age 50+, Civil Servant, at Araromi-Lisa in Okitipupa on the 16th of July, 2024.

²⁶³ Interview held with Mr Peter Ayelabola, Age 50+, Civil Servant

In Okitipupa, customary laws and norms still guide dispute resolution processes. Traditional rulers play a central role in settling conflicts, whether between individuals or within the community, by using laws and customs unique to the people of the town. The respect accorded to these laws highlights their continued relevance, especially in resolving disputes related to land, family, and other communal matters. These customary laws ensure that solutions are tailored to the specific needs and values of the community, preserving cultural continuity in conflict resolution practices.²⁶⁴ Community involvement remained integral to traditional conflict resolution in Okitipupa. Elders, chiefs, and other community members are actively involved in mediating disputes and fostering collective participation and consensus. This inclusive approach not only strengthened the resolution process but also reinforced communal bonds and societal values. The involvement of the community in conflict resolution fostered a sense of shared responsibility, ensuring that the resolutions reached were accepted and adhered to by all parties involved.²⁶⁵

One of the most enduring practices in Okitipupa's conflict resolution mechanism is the use of symbolic sanctions, such as oath-taking and rituals. Oath-taking is particularly effective in reinforcing peace agreements and ensuring truthfulness in disputes. For instance, when parties agree to a settlement, they may be required to swear before deities, such as *Ayelala* (guardian of social morality), *Sango* (god of thunder) and *Ogun*, the god of iron, symbolising their commitment to the terms of the resolution.²⁶⁶ This ritual serves as a powerful deterrent against dishonesty, as violating the oath is believed to invoke the wrath of the gods. The continued use of such symbolic practices underscores the deep respect for traditional conflict resolution methods in the town. Moreover, traditional sanctions, such as rituals and curses, also play a crucial role in ensuring compliance with decisions made by traditional authorities. These sanctions act as cultural safeguards, ensuring that individuals adhere to the resolutions reached during mediation, thus maintaining order and harmony in the community.²⁶⁷

Many residents of Okitipupa, particularly in rural areas, continued to prefer traditional conflict resolution mechanisms over the formal legal system. This was due in part to the accessibility of traditional institutions, which were embedded in the community and understood local norms, as well as administrative and litigation costs, and dissatisfaction with the perceived

²⁶⁴ Interview held with Mr Peter Ayelabola, Age 50+, Civil Servant

²⁶⁵ Interview held with Mr Peter Ayelabola, Age 50+, Civil Servant

²⁶⁶ Interview held with Chief Akanni Agbede, Age 70, Traditionalist, at Alo Street, Okitipupa on the 17th of July, 2024.

²⁶⁷ Interview held with Chief Akanni Agbede, Age 70, Traditionalist

impersonality and rigidity of the formal courts. As a result, even as legal reforms were implemented, many disputes continued to be resolved outside the formal judicial system. The enduring role of traditional conflict resolution mechanisms in Okitipupa reflects the resilience of these practices in addressing contemporary challenges. Despite the introduction of modern legal systems, traditional methods continue to serve as effective tools for resolving conflicts, especially in areas related to land, family, and other communal matters. This blending of traditional and modern approaches ensures that Okitipupa's rich cultural heritage remains a vital part of its social fabric, while also adapting to the demands of modern governance.

Ultimately, the continuity of traditional conflict resolution mechanisms in Okitipupa highlighted the community's ability to preserve its cultural heritage while adapting to modern challenges. From the pivotal role of traditional rulers and elders to the use of customary law and symbolic sanctions, these practices provide effective and culturally sensitive solutions that foster peace and social cohesion. By emphasising reconciliation over punishment, Okitipupa's conflict resolution system ensures that relationships are preserved, promoting long-term harmony and stability within the community.

Challenges Facing Traditional Conflict Resolution Mechanisms

Traditional conflict resolution mechanisms in Okitipupa, while still relevant, face significant challenges in the contemporary era. One of the major challenges to the advancement of the traditional method of dispute resolution in Okitipupa was the introduction of the tripartite validity test by the received English law as a basis for the application of customary laws in Nigeria. The emergence of the Independence Constitution of 1960 marked a significant shift in the roles of traditional rulers in Nigeria.²⁶⁸ While the Council of Chiefs in the Northern Region and the Minority Councils in the Eastern and Western Regions aimed to enhance the participation of traditional leaders, their influence within federal and regional legislatures was diminished, giving way to appointed chiefs. The Republican Constitution of 1963 redefined the roles of traditional rulers, allowing them to serve as members of parliament as outlined in Section 69, which empowered Parliament to legislate for the peace and good governance of Nigeria.

²⁶⁸ Nworah, U. 2007. "The Role of Traditional Rulers in an Emerging Democratic Nigeria" A paper presented at the 3 – Day National Stakeholders' Workshop on The Role of Traditional Institutions in The Three Tiers of Government Holding at The Abuja International Conference Centre. 11th, 12th And 13th November 2007.

However, subsequent constitutional reforms, particularly the 1979 Constitution, relegated traditional rulers to advisory roles. They became largely symbolic figures, participating only as members of the Council of State at the federal level and the Council of Chiefs at the state level, without any administrative authority. According to Part I of the Third Schedule of the 1979 Constitution, these councils were tasked with advising the Governor on matters concerning customary law, cultural affairs, inter-communal relations, and chieftaincy issues, along with public order when requested. Unfortunately, the 1999 Constitution further marginalised traditional rulers by omitting any formal roles for them, significantly limiting their capacity to act as effective institutions for conflict resolution and the enforcement of judgments. This erosion of power hindered their ability to influence governance and maintain social order within their communities, undermining the traditional structures that had previously played crucial roles in local governance and conflict management.²⁶⁹

Similarly, the incompatibility between traditional mechanisms and Nigeria's formal legal system poses a significant challenge to the continuity and effectiveness of Indigenous conflict resolution. The formal legal system, with its codified laws and structured courts, was introduced during the colonial period and solidified in post-colonial Nigeria, gradually displacing many indigenous methods that had been used for generations. These two systems often operate under very different principles, leading to confusion, jurisdictional disputes, and legal contradictions. One key area of incompatibility lies in the fundamentally different approaches to justice.²⁷⁰ Traditional conflict resolution mechanisms in places like Okitipupa are often focused on restorative justice, community cohesion, and reconciliation rather than determining guilt or innocence. In contrast, the formal legal system is largely adversarial, seeking to establish liability, enforce penalties, and follow procedural justice. This disparity in objectives often creates tension when cases that might have been peacefully resolved through communal mediation are escalated to the courts, where rigid legal codes take precedence.²⁷¹

This incompatibility is especially pronounced when decisions made by traditional leaders conflict with the Nigerian constitution or human rights frameworks. For example, traditional laws governing land ownership, inheritance, or family disputes may reflect customary practices that are

²⁶⁹ Nworah, U. 2007. "The Role of Traditional Rulers in an Emerging Democratic Nigeria".

²⁷⁰ Akinwumi, O. 2015. "The Role of Traditional Rulers in Conflict Resolution in Nigeria: A Study of the Yoruba People". *African Journal of Political Science and International Relations*, 9(2), 35-45.

²⁷¹ Interview held with Mr Peter Ayelabola, Age 50+, Civil Servant, at Araromi-Lisa in Okitipupa on the 16th of July, 2024.

centuries old, but these laws sometimes clash with statutory laws that are more modern and aligned with international human rights standards. Customary laws, for instance, may follow patrilineal inheritance systems that limit women's rights to own or inherit land, while Nigeria's constitution provides for gender equality. This legal contradiction often places individuals—especially marginalised groups like women—in difficult positions, where a choice must be made between adhering to traditional customs and asserting their rights under the formal legal system.²⁷²

Moreover, disputes over land ownership are particularly prone to jurisdictional conflicts. Traditional leaders may resolve land disputes based on customary tenure systems, which are recognised within the community but are not always legally binding under Nigerian statutory law.²⁷³ When these decisions are contested in formal courts, the outcomes may be reversed, causing confusion and undermining the authority of traditional rulers. In some cases, parties dissatisfied with traditional rulings may bypass these indigenous systems entirely and seek recourse in the formal legal system, thereby weakening the traditional institutions' capacity to resolve conflicts.

In family matters, the incompatibility between traditional and statutory laws often also leads to confusion. For instance, issues related to marriage, divorce, and child custody may be handled according to customary practices in traditional systems, which often emphasise collective decision-making by family members and community elders. However, the formal legal system prioritised individual rights and procedural rules, such as the best interests of the child in custody cases. These differing priorities resulted in conflicting rulings, as well as disputes over which system holds ultimate authority over such matters.²⁷⁴

Another challenge is the lack of formal documentation and institutional support for traditional conflict resolution methods. Since these mechanisms are often based on oral traditions and customary laws, the absence of written records makes it difficult to standardise practices or ensure consistency. This creates further complications when these rulings are challenged in formal courts. The lack of written records or codification of customary laws makes it difficult to standardise these practices or ensure their enforceability in broader legal contexts.²⁷⁵ Without

²⁷² Anifowose, R. 2018. “Women, Land and Customary Law in Nigeria: Issues and Challenges”. *Women’s Studies International Forum*, 71, 17-25.

²⁷³ Otite, O. 2005. *Ethnic Pluralism and Ethnic Conflict in Nigeria*. Ibadan: Spectrum Books, 32.

²⁷⁴ Interview held with Mr Benedict Ayadi, Age 60+, Elder Statesman, at Abusoro in Okitipupa on the 17th of July, 2024.

²⁷⁵ Barrows, L., and Bo, G. 2010. “Conflict Resolution in Africa: The Role of Customary Mechanisms”. In L. Barrows and G. Bo (Eds.), *Cultural Approaches to Conflict Resolution* Nairobi: African Studies Centre, (50-70).

proper documentation, traditional rulings may be dismissed or deemed invalid by formal courts, further eroding trust in indigenous mechanisms and their relevance in contemporary Nigerian society. Furthermore, traditional rulings may not be recognised by the state's legal system, limiting their enforceability in broader disputes that extend beyond the community.

Another pressing issue is the gradual erosion of respect and authority accorded to traditional rulers and elders. As modernisation, urbanisation, and the spread of Western education continue to influence the community, younger generations often perceive traditional leaders as outdated and less capable of addressing complex, modern problems. This has led to a diminishing role for these leaders, further compounded by the rise of governmental institutions and formal legal systems that often overshadow indigenous practices.²⁷⁶ Urbanisation and social change have also significantly weakened traditional conflict resolution. As Okitipupa modernises and grows, urbanisation introduces diverse populations and new social dynamics that erode the close-knit communal ties essential for traditional dispute resolution. In rural areas, traditional leaders command respect and have a deep understanding of their people, but in urban settings, their influence is diminished. Additionally, the increased mobility of people and exposure to different cultures has weakened the communal bonds that sustain these practices.²⁷⁷

The influence of religion, particularly the spread of Christianity and Islam, has also had a profound effect on traditional conflict resolution in Okitipupa. Many adherents of these faiths reject traditional practices like oath-taking before deities or the use of rituals, considering them incompatible with their religious beliefs. As a result, religious individuals preferred to resolve disputes through religious or formal legal systems, leading to a decline in the use of traditional mechanisms.²⁷⁸

Economic and political pressures further compromise the effectiveness of traditional conflict resolution. Traditional rulers and elders are sometimes subjected to political or economic influences that can undermine their impartiality. In cases involving land disputes or communal resources, powerful political or business interests may manipulate the decisions of traditional leaders, leading to perceptions of bias and corruption.²⁷⁹ This eroded trust in traditional mechanisms and weakened their ability to resolve disputes fairly. In the present day where truth

²⁷⁶ Interview held with Mr Benedict Ayadi, Age 60+, Elder Statesman

²⁷⁷ Interview held with Mr Benedict Ayadi, Age 60+, Elder Statesman

²⁷⁸ Interview held with Mr Benedict Ayadi, Age 60+, Elder Statesman

²⁷⁹ Interview held with Mr Benedict Ayadi, Age 60+, Elder Statesman

has become a scarce commodity in Nigeria, most elders, chiefs, and village heads among others were likely to be biased in their decisions because of corruption and favouritism that had permeated all sectors of the people's lives.

Lastly, globalisation has introduced new influences, including international norms on human rights, gender equality, and democracy, which challenge traditional methods of conflict resolution. As Okitipupa becomes increasingly integrated into the global economy and society, these external pressures force a reevaluation of traditional practices that may no longer align with global standards.

Traditional conflict resolution mechanisms in Okitipupa are facing numerous challenges in today's world. From the erosion of traditional authority and the rise of formal legal systems to urbanisation, religious influence, and globalisation, these forces are reshaping how conflicts are managed. While these methods remain valuable, they must adapt to the changing social, economic, and political landscape to remain relevant and effective in resolving disputes. For traditional systems to remain effective and respected, there must be some form of harmonisation with formal legal structures that ensures the protection of human rights while preserving the valuable elements of indigenous practices.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

Summary

The study of traditional conflict resolution mechanisms in Okitipupa underscores the enduring importance of indigenous practices in resolving disputes and maintaining peace within the community. Despite the profound changes brought about by colonialism, modernisation, and the integration of Western legal systems, many elements of traditional conflict resolution remain deeply embedded in the community's cultural and social fabric. Institutions such as community

leaders, elders, and customary law continue to play a critical role in mediating disputes, ensuring justice, and upholding social harmony.

This research explored the historical evolution and cultural significance of conflict resolution mechanisms in Okitipupa, a town located in Ondo State, up to the year 2022. Against the backdrop of the evolving nature of traditional conflict resolution methods across Nigerian communities, this study emphasises the enduring relevance of these time-honoured practices. It highlights the cultural values that sustain traditional institutions, focusing on their pivotal role in fostering social cohesion and communal unity. The first chapter provided a background of the traditional judicial systems of Yorubaland, offering a foundation for understanding the mechanisms at play in Okitipupa. The second chapter traced the early history of the Okitipupa people, detailing their migration, settlement, and the geographical environment of their current location. This section also examined the pre-colonial political structure, social organisation, customs, religion, and economic activities of the Okitipupa people.

The third chapter analysed the traditional conflict resolution mechanisms in Okitipupa, detailing the causes and patterns of conflicts, the key institutions and actors involved, and the various methods employed to resolve disputes. In the fourth chapter, the study explored the changes and continuities in these mechanisms, revealing the significant but lasting influence of colonialism on the conflict resolution process in Okitipupa. One of the defining features of traditional conflict resolution in the town is its emphasis on communal involvement and consensus-building. Unlike the Western legal system, which often seeks to establish guilt and impose punishment, Okitipupa's traditional mechanisms prioritise reconciliation and the restoration of harmony within the community. This is achieved through dialogue, mediation, and symbolic sanctions, such as oath-taking, which carry deep cultural significance and are believed to be divinely enforced. In conflicts involving family or minor issues, mediators focus on finding lasting solutions rather than apportioning blame, aiming for a win-win resolution.

However, traditional conflict resolution mechanisms in Okitipupa face several challenges in the modern era. The influence of formal legal systems has introduced tensions, especially when decisions made by traditional leaders clash with statutory laws or constitutional rights, leading to confusion over jurisdiction. Traditional mechanisms are often marginalised in cases involving human rights, gender equality, or serious crimes, as their practices may not always align with

contemporary legal standards. Additionally, the lack of formal recognition and resources for traditional institutions weakens their effectiveness in addressing conflicts.

External factors such as urbanisation, economic shifts, and changing social dynamics have also impacted the authority of traditional leaders. Younger generations, in particular, may view these mechanisms as outdated or ineffective, opting instead for formal legal channels. The interaction between traditional and modern approaches has created opportunities for collaboration, such as the integration of vigilante groups like *Amotekun*, but also underscores the need for a more coherent alignment between these two systems to ensure their continued relevance and effectiveness in resolving conflicts.

Conclusion

From the foregoing, it is evident that traditional conflict resolution mechanisms are deeply ingrained in Okitipupa's culture, just as they are in many African indigenous cultural systems. The existence of homegrown institutions anchored in conflict resolution, along with the active involvement of indigenous leaders, attests to the vibrancy and effectiveness of these mechanisms in addressing disputes. Indigenous political, social, and religious institutions evolved as multidimensional structures, not only addressing matters of relevance to the community's existence but also functioning as key tools for fostering peaceful coexistence. They resolve conflicts both overtly and covertly, maintaining social order and harmony.

This research has revealed the effectiveness of indigenous conflict resolution methods, showing that the introduction of Western legal frameworks has not diminished the value of traditional systems. Instead, it has highlighted the flexibility and strength of these indigenous forms, which have adapted to the changing realities of African societies, including Okitipupa. The continuity and adaptation of traditional conflict resolution mechanisms in Okitipupa reflect the resilience of these indigenous justice systems, which remain relevant in the lives of the people. Community leaders, elders, and traditional rulers continue to command respect, and their culturally rooted methods offer a viable alternative to the often rigid and alienating formal legal processes.

However, to ensure that traditional mechanisms remain effective in the long term, their limitations must be recognised. This includes addressing incompatibilities with formal legal systems, particularly in areas where traditional methods may conflict with modern legal standards, such as human rights and gender equity. There is a need for these mechanisms to evolve and adapt to contemporary standards of justice, while still preserving their cultural essence. A synergistic

approach, in which traditional and formal legal systems complement each other, could offer a sustainable solution for conflict management in Okitipupa and other Nigerian communities. By embracing the strengths of both systems, the community can create a more inclusive and effective framework for conflict resolution, ensuring the preservation of cultural heritage while addressing modern societal needs.

Additionally, attention must be drawn to the role of women in conflict resolution, a traditionally silent but profoundly influential element. While often excluded from visible political and social engagements, women play a crucial role in sustaining peace within society.

In conclusion, traditional conflict resolution mechanisms in Okitipupa remain a vital component of the community's social structure. With thoughtful integration into the modern legal framework, these mechanisms have the potential to bridge the gap between cultural practices and formal legal systems. This fusion can ensure that peace, justice, and social cohesion are maintained, adapting these valuable traditions for future generations.

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Primary Sources

Interviews

The under-listed individuals were interviewed on several occasions, and the details of the interviews were taken down as follows.

S/	Name	Age	Status/Occupation	Place of Interview	Date of Interview
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N					
1	Adelokiki Patrick	40+	Civil Rights Activist	Okitipupa	16 th July 2024
2	Chief Abel Akindokun	60+	<i>Yepata</i> of Idepe Okitipupa	Araromi-Lisa, Okitipupa	16 th July 2024
3	Chief Adeola Akinloye	70	Traditionalist	Ewi-Isale, Okitipupa	14 th March 2024
4	Chief Akanni Agbede	70+	Traditionalist	Alo Street, Okitipupa	17 th March 2024
5	Chief Jeremiah Akindeyi	60+	Traditional Political Leader	Ode Idepe, Okitipupa	15 th July 2024
6	Chief Matthew Asade	60+	Traditional Political Leader	Olorode Quatres, Ode-Idepe, Okitipupa	14 th March 2024
7	Chief Mrs Osutade Kehinde	50+	Traditional Political Leader	Okesare, Okitipupa	16 th July 2024
8	Chief Osifeso Onabule	72	Traditionalist	Ewi Oke Street, Okitipupa	14 th March 2024
9	Chief Olaniyan Egburen	60+	Traditional Political Leader	Adegolu, Okitipupa	14 th March 2024
10	High Chief Isaac Medunoye	74	Traditional Spiritual Leader	Medunoye's Compound, Aja Quarters, Okitipupa	15 th March 2024
11	High Chief Omotola Emaye	63	<i>Arogun</i> of Idepe Okitipupa	Okitipupa	16 th July 2024
12	Mr Adeniyi Ogundairo	67	Retired Civil Servant	Araromi-Lisa, Okitipupa	16 th July 2024
13	Mr Akingbe Ayodeji	47	Farming	Ogbole Street, Okitipupa	12 th March 2024
14	Mr Balo Lanre	72	Elder Stateman	Jokodo Street, Okitipupa	16 th March 2024
15	Mr John Akintimehin	60+	Retired Teacher	Erekiti Street, Okitipupa	16 th July 2024
16	Mr Kunle Olatumile	65	Teaching	Ope Oluwa Street, Ode-Idepe	15 th March 2024
17	Mr Obeda Samuel	60+	Palm Oil Extracting	Alanse Street, Okitipupa	17 th March 2024
18	Mr Olatunde Aladepupo	50+	Security Personnel	Ode Idepe, Okitipupa	15 th July 2024
19	Mr Peter Ayelabola	50+	Security Personnel	Araromi-Lisa, Okitipupa	16 th July 2024
20	Mr Samuel Liyansan-Ajaka	67	Retired Surveyor	Agbabu Street, Okitipupa	15 th July 2024
21	Mr Timothy Liyansan Ajaka	62	Land Agent	Agbabu Street, Okitipupa	15 th July 2024
22	Mr Odunwo	61	Trading	Ojan Street, Okitipupa	16 th March 2024

	Dayo				
23	Mr Stephen Dapo	70	Farming	Alo Street, Okitipupa	17 th March 2024
24	Mrs Idowu Akintimehin	50+	Trading	Erekiti Street, Okitipupa	16 th July 2024
25	Mrs Ogunmehin Toyin	47	Trading	Okitipupa Market	17 th March 2024
26	Mrs Olotu Esther	40+	Trading	Ewi-Oke Street, Okitipupa	14 th March 2024
27	Mrs Olorunfemi Felicia	56	Trading	Okitipupa Market	17 th March 2024
28	Pa Benedict Ayadi	76	Elder Statesman	Abusoro Street, Okitipupa	16 th March 2024

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